

Curiosity's Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator's Notebook: Sols 3424–3547

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Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Technical Report 0032

Cover photo

MAHLI view of the Avanavero sample extraction hole, created by Curiosity's drill on Sol 3512. The hole diameter is about 1.6 cm. The image was obtained on Sol 3528 and is illuminated by sunlight from the left, this is MAHLI image 3528MH0007740011203968C00.

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7.1 Definitions and conventions

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Acknowledgements

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Note that pages are not numbered in this document because all of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, and *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* were inserted separately after creation using a word processing tool that differs from the one used for the text.

Abstract

Covering the time between Curiosity’s 3424th and 3547th Martian days (sols) of operations in northern Gale crater, Mars, this document is a compilation of the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities conducted during that period. The report includes brief sol-by-sol notes—written as the mission unfolded—regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used and significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation. The document, further, contains information regarding range and scale (camera working distance and scale of in-focus elements of an image); the parent images, range, and scale information associated with each MAHLI focus merge product created onboard the instrument; and a description of the purpose and intent behind acquisition of each MAHLI image and creation of each onboard focus merge product. The MSL science team and rover engineers routinely used the information contained in this report during the course of the mission for tactical planning, strategic planning, and scientific analysis.

1 Introduction

1.1 Introduction and purpose

This document is a compilation of the Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Team’s notes and information about MAHLI images and activities that occurred during the Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) mission between Sols 3424 and 3547.

MAHLI is a 2-megapixel color camera with a focusable macro lens mounted on the turret at the end of a robotic arm aboard NASA’s MSL rover, Curiosity (Edgett *et al.* 2012). The rover landed and began operation in northern Gale crater, Mars, on 6 August 2012 (Vasavada *et al.* 2014).

Each *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook* covers a specific period corresponding to a release of MAHLI data to the NASA Planetary Data System (PDS) Imaging Node (<http://pds-imaging.jpl.nasa.gov/>). As some MAHLI data can arrive from Mars months or years after a given release period, the publication of these reports typically lags behind the PDS release schedule by a period that varies from one occasion to the next, depending largely on when data acquired during that period arrive on Earth and when we have time to complete the *Principal Investigator’s Notebook* report.

This report, *Curiosity’s Mars Hand Lens Imager (MAHLI) Mars Science Laboratory (MSL) Principal Investigator’s Notebook: Sols 3424–3547*, corresponds to MAHLI data Release 31 in the NASA PDS archives. These are data acquired 24 March 2022 through 30 July 2022.

1.2 Versions and change log

The enclosed materials were compiled as the MSL mission unfolded. That being the case, we might sometimes have made errors. The reader should be aware that this report might be corrected via release of a new version in the future.

A new version would also be created if new data from this report’s period (Martian sols) are received from the instrument after an earlier version has been made available. This can occur because MAHLI can store data onboard the instrument for an indefinite period of time after acquisition. As a result, images are archived with the NASA PDS on the basis of when they are received on Earth, not when they are acquired on Mars.

Covering the Sol 3424 through 3547 period, this document is Version 1.

If this were a later version, this section would document the changes made relative to the previous.

2 Instrument activities for this period

This section captures day-by-day or sol-by-sol notes written by the MAHLI Team, as the mission unfolded, regarding how the MAHLI instrument was used or significant events that occurred which impacted the MAHLI instrument or investigation.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3424 – 3547						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Driving to Hartle Loup on the Greenheugh Pediment	25 Mar 22	3424	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3423 were merged.
At Hartle Loup on the Greenheugh Pediment	26 Mar 22	3425	13	74	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Donkey_Trail and the target Burn Mouth.
	28 Mar 22	3427	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3425 were merged.
	29 Mar 22	3428	14	124	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Venlaw, on which MAHLI acquired a 1x6 mosaic, and the target Broadfell.
	30 Mar 22	3429	0	0	12	Focus stack images from Sol 3428 were merged.
At Hartle Loup on the Greenheugh Pediment	02 Apr 22	3432	13	73	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Blue_Anchor and Baa.
	03 Apr 22	3433	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3432 were merged.
Traversing East on the Greenheugh pediment	06 Apr 22	3436	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Broo and the focus stack images were merged.
Near Knap of Howar on the Greenheugh Pediment	09 Apr 22	3439	12	100	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Lodberrie and Sneuga and acquired a 1x3 mosaic from ~5 cm standoff on the target Inchbonny.
	10 Apr 22	3440	0	0	9	Focus stack images from Sol 3439 were merged.
At Feorachas on the Greenheugh Pediment	12 Apr 22	3442	15	102	9	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Brackenberry and the targets Skidbladner and Up_Helly_Aa. The focus stack images were also merged.
	14 Apr 22	3444	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Dun and the focus stack images were merged.
Descending off the Greenheugh pediment	17 Apr 22/ 18 Apr 22	3447	8	49	4	MAHLI imaged the targets Spiggie_Beach and Bains Beach as well as the wheel-rock contact of the rover left front wheel that was obstructing mobility. The focus stack images were also merged.
	19 Apr 22/ 20 Apr 22	3449	4	24	2	MAHLI imaged the target Runn and the REMS UV Sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.
Driving towards Avanavero Drill Site	22 Apr 22	3451	11	97	8	MAHLI imaged the target Rumlblings, the DRT-brushed target Shandon and the target Nesting. The focus stack images were also merged.
	24 Apr 22	3453	12	79	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Delting and the target Rumlblings. MAHLI also imaged the rover left front wheel as a follow-up to the imaging acquired on Sol 3447.
	25 Apr 22	3454	0	0	6	The focus stack images from Sol 3453 were merged.
	27 Apr 22	3456	3	23	2	MAHLI imaged the target Colla_Firth and the focus stack images were merged.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3424 – 3547						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
Driving towards Avanavero Drill Site	29 Apr 22	3458	7	56	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Orton_Scar and Cow_Head and the focus stack images were merged.
	30 Apr 22	3459	10	65	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Castlecraig and Cat_Firth.
Driving towards Avanavero Drill Site	02 May 22	3461	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3459 were merged.
	03 May 22	3462	7	54	5	MAHLI imaged the targets Gran_Sabana and Berbice and the focus stack images were merged.
	06 May 22	3465	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the targets Firina (2x1 mosaic) and Bartica and the focus stack images were merged.
	07 May 22	3466	12	72	6	MAHLI imaged the targets Bonfim, Kurupukari (4x1 mosaic) and Oshi and the focus stack images were merged.
	10 May 22	3469	6	44	4	MAHLI imaged the targets El_Oso and Parima and the focus stack images were also merged.
	12 May 22	3471	10	60	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Pastora and the target Tama_Tama.
	13 May 22	3472	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3471 were merged.
	14 May 22	3473	7	54	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target San_Pedro and the target Pedra_Pintada.
	15 May 22	3474	0	0	5	Focus stack images from Sol 3473 were merged.
	17 May 22	3476	3	24	2	MAHLI imaged the target Aratana and the focus stack images were merged.
	19 May 22	3478	10	92	9	MAHLI acquired a 3x2 mosaic on the target Las_Claritas prior to brushing and then MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Las_Claritas. The focus stack images were also merged.
	21 May 22	3480	10	76	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Maple_Creek and Apoteri as well as the DRT-brushed target Bamboo_Creek.
	22 May 22	3481	0	0	7	Focus stack images from Sol 3480 were merged.
	24 May 22	3483	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Imataca and the focus stack images were merged.
26 May 22	3485	5	50	5	MAHLI imaged the target Cabo_Sobral, which included a 3x1 mosaic, and the focus stack images were merged.	
30 May 22	3488	9	50	4	MAHLI imaged the non-brushed region of the target Pitinga as well as the DRT-brushed region of the target Pitinga. The focus stack images were also merged.	
Driving towards Avanavero Drill Site	02 Jun 22	3491	8	64	6	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Parepona and the target Cabadiscana. The focus stack images were also merged.
	03 Jun 22	3492	20	20	0	MAHLI imaged $\geq 360^\circ$ of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.
	04 Jun 22	3493	11	78	7	MAHLI acquired a 4x1 mosaic on the target Tabaco and imaged the DRT-brushed target Issano. The focus stack images were also merged.
	14 Jun 22	3503	9	100	8	MAHLI imaged the ChemCam RWEB window and internal hardware, the target Wandapa, on which a 3x1 mosaic was acquired, and the DRT-brushed target Omai. The focus stack images were also merged.
	16 Jun 22	3505	6	34	1	MAHLI imaged the target Tipuru, the sky, with the dust cover open and closed for flat fielding, and the REMS UV Sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.
	19 Jun 22	3508	9	83	7	MAHLI imaged the targets Kukui, Salto_Angel, and Opadai. The focus stack images were also merged.
At Avanavero Drill Site	22 Jun 22	3511	8	48	4	MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Avanavero before and after DRT and after a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.
	23 Jun 22	3512	1	2	0	Drill preparation activities at the planned Avanavero sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Avanavero sample discard pile.

MAHLI Activities During Sols 3424 – 3547						
milestone or field site	date (UTC)	Sol	camera positions	Parent images	Onboard focus merges	Notes
At Avanavero Drill Site	10 Jul 22	3528	3	6	0	MAHLI imaged the Avanavero drill hole and cuttings.
	12 Jul 22	3530	4	24	2	MAHLI imaged the Avanavero drill cuttings and the target La_Laja. The focus stack images were also merged.
Heading towards Paraitepuy Pass	13 Jul 22	3531	4	32	3	MAHLI imaged the target Uai Uai and the focus stack images were merged.
	14 Jul 22	3532	11	97	0	MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Seringa, the target La_Manare, and the target Caruai.
	15 Jul 22	3533	0	0	8	The focus stack images from Sol 3532 were merged.
	16 Jul 22	3534	11	102	0	MAHLI imaged the target Monte_Caburai and acquired a 2x3 mosaic on the boulder Ilha_Novo_Destino.
	17 Jul 22	3535	4	5	0	At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
	18 Jul 22	3536	0	0	10	Focus stack images from Sol 3534 were merged.
	19 Jul 22	3537	3	22	2	MAHLI imaged the target Cerro_Raya and the focus stack images were merged.
	21 Jul 22	3539	7	45	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Surama and Amajari as well as the wheel-surface interface of the rover right middle wheel.
	22 Jul 22	3540	0	0	4	Focus stack images from Sol 3539 were merged.
	23 Jul 22	3541	9	66	0	MAHLI imaged the targets Benhori_Bumoko and Serra_da_Mocidade as well as the DRT-brushed target Motocuruna.
	25 Jul 22	3543	0	0	6	Focus stack images from Sol 3541 were merged.
	26 Jul 22	3544	3	30	3	MAHLI imaged the target Tumereng and the focus stack images were merged.
28 Jul 22	3546	7	56	0	MAHLI imaged the target Simoni and the DRT-brushed target Lilas.	
29 Jul 22	3547	0	0	10	Focus stack images from Sol 3546 were merged.	

3 Helpful tips

3.1 MAHLI instrument and investigation

Please refer to Edgett *et al.* (2012) for a description of the MAHLI instrument and investigation, Edgett *et al.* (2015) for information about the characterization and calibration of the instrument, and Yingst *et al.* (2016) for some of the lessons learned after ~1.5 Mars years of surface operations. Additional information on how the instrument and data have been used is in the paper by Minitti *et al.* (2013) and the extended abstract by Garvin *et al.* (2017).

3.2 MAHLI image IDs

MAHLI images and onboard focus merge products are identified by their image IDs. The following figure describes the information content of these IDs.

Note that raw images released within minutes of receipt on Earth to the public via the JPL-Caltech web site (<http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/>) do not necessarily have the correct, final, archival image IDs.

MAHLI Image IDs

- This is the only official, correct, archival image ID scheme.
- Raw Images released rapidly at <http://mars.jpl.nasa.gov/msl/multimedia/raw/> do not always give you the correct, archival image ID.

0132MH0001580010101221C00

sol → 0132

camera
MH = MAHLI → MH

CDPID
a.k.a. MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID → 000158001

product type
as received from Mars → C00

sequence ID → 000158001

order in sequence
usually, first = 0, second = 1, etc. → 0101

CDPID counter
How many times the following CDPID has been used since landing → 101

version
version received on Earth
0 = parent image on Mars → 221

GOP counter
for video Group of Pictures (JPEG video frames) → C00

Note that, for onboard focus merge products, the sol is the sol that the merge took place. This is **not** always on the same sol that the parent images were acquired.

The MAHLI team pays most attention to the items in yellow. In a focus stack, the images are acquired in order of increasing CDPID.

Product type tells you about the image as received from Mars; not necessarily the image you are looking at, if it has been further processed, uncompressed, or recompressed on Earth.

The NASA PDS archives include documentation that describes the MAHLI image ID and file naming scheme and the nature of the archived Experiment Data Record (EDR) and Reduced Data Record (RDR) products (Malin *et al.*, 2013).

The EDR products, the raw data product, have the following file name scheme:

- 1 **[Image ID]_XXXX** – these are always 8-bit images except for the 16-bit products (type A) returned from MAHLI for calibration purposes.

The RDR products are of the following nature:

- 2 **[Image ID]_DRXX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated color images,
- 3 **[Image ID]_DRLX** – 16-bit depth (per band) relative radiometric calibrated and geometric calibrated color images,
- 4 **[Image ID]_DRCX** – 8-bit relative radiometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied, and
- 5 **[Image ID]_DRCL** – 8-bit relative radiometric and geometric calibrated images for which a color correction has been applied.

The following table describes the variety of image types (raw, lossless, JPEG, focus merge, thumbnail, *etc.*). Malin *et al.* (2013) described these in greater detail.

product type	product format
A	raster 16-bit image
B	raster 8-bit image
C	lossless compressed image
D	JPEG grayscale image
E	JPEG 4:2:2 color image
F	JPEG 4:4:4 color image
G	raster thumbnail of parent image
H	JPEG gray thumbnail of parent image
I	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of parent image
J	raster 8-bit video frame
K	lossless compressed video frame
L	JPEG grayscale video frame
M	JPEG 4:2:2 color video frame
N	JPEG 4:4:4 color video frame
O	raster 8-bit thumbnail of video frame
P	JPEG gray thumbnail of video frame
Q	JPEG 4:4:4 thumbnail of video frame
R	focus merge best focus image product
S	focus merge range map product
T	focus merge best focus thumbnail
U	focus merge range map thumbnail

Types R and T are JPEG 4:4:4; S and U are JPEG grayscale products.

3.3 MAHLI LED positions

The MAHLI camera head has two groups of two white light LEDs (Edgett *et al.* 2012), called Group 1 and Group 2. For reference, the figure below shows their location on the camera head and how these locations translate to positions relative to pixel 0,0 (column 0, row 0) on the MAHLI CCD. In addition, MAHLI has two 365 nm ultraviolet (UV) LEDs, also shown in the figure. Each group of two LEDs (Group 1, Group 2, and UV) can be operated together or independently with each of the other two groups. When the LEDs are used, which group was operated is reported in the RATIONALE_DESC description of the image intent and purpose (Section 6).

MAHLI image TVC_MH0809080020000032B00, left, shows the violet and white reflections of the UV and Group 1 and Group 2 white light LEDs, indicating their location in relation to the CCD's pixel at column 0, row 0. The photograph on the right shows the camera head with its dust cover open and LEDs labeled.

4 Camera range and scale information

4.1 Purpose and description

MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* (or “Distance and Scale Information Sheets”) describe **(a)** the distance between the MAHLI camera and an imaged target, and **(b)** the scale of in-focus features in the image, based on knowledge of that distance. Usually, these are determined using the camera’s stepper motor count focus position (Edgett *et al.* 2015).

These information sheets were created only for cases in which there was a need. Cases for which they are not usually created include those when the only MAHLI image(s) acquired on a given sol are **(a)** views of the landscape, focused at infinity; **(b)** intended to make a rover self-portrait mosaic; **(c)** sky flat field calibration data; or **(d)** routinely-acquired images of the rover wheels for inspection purposes.

For the Sol 3424–3547 period, *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were created for the following **Sols: 3425, 3428, 3432, 3436, 3439, 3442, 3444, 3447, 3449, 3451, 3453, 3456, 3458, 3459, 3462, 3465, 3466, 3469, 3471, 3473, 3476, 3478, 3480, 3483, 3485, 3488, 3491, 3492, 3493, 3503, 3505, 3508, 3511, 3512, 3528, 3530, 3531, 3532, 3534, 3535, 3537, 3539, 3541, 3544, 3546.**

The origin of the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was in the need for a rapid, tactical response from the MAHLI team to the Curiosity Rover Planners—the engineers tasked with operating the rover’s mobility and robotic arm systems—for range-finding and image scale information derived from MAHLI’s autofocus and focus merge capabilities. As described by Minitti *et al.* (2013), during the rover’s first sample extraction campaign, conducted at the Rocknest eolian sand deposit in October–November 2012, the engineers elected to use MAHLI autofocus sub-frames to confirm their estimates of the range to the sand surface for subsequent scoop placement (Anderson *et al.* 2015). These *Range and Scale Information Sheets* were borne of that effort to provide the information almost as soon as the data arrived on Earth.

Presented in this section are the latest versions of the *Range and Scale Information Sheets*, for the above stated sols, as of the date of this *MAHLI Technical Report* publication. Most of these sheets were actively used during the MSL mission for tactical and strategic planning, as well as for the scientific analyses. Note that some of the sheets exhibit slightly different formatting from each other, as the formatting and content evolved over time.

The image IDs presented in these Information Sheets are the identifiers of the best, least-compressed version of the image received from Mars for a given camera position for the stated purpose (autofocus, imaging, range-finding, etc.). In cases for which only a thumbnail version of the image was received, the image ID is colored orange.

4.2 Formulae

4.2.1 Working distance

The working distance (d_w , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* was computed from the empirical relationship between working distance and motor count for the flight unit MAHLI when the dust cover is open (m_{open}) described by Edgett *et al.* (2015):

$$d_w = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (1)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For the dust cover closed case (m_{closed}), Edgett *et al.* (2015) found that m_{closed} is related to m_{open} as follows:

$$m_{closed} = 17075 - m_{open}. \quad (2)$$

4.2.2 Standoff distance (RP distance; MAHLI toolframe +X distance)

The standoff distance (d_s , in centimeters) presented in the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* is 1.9 cm less than the MAHLI working distance (Edgett *et al.* 2015). Note that “standoff distance” is equivalent to “RP distance” and “MAHLI toolframe +X distance”; see **Section 7.1**). It is determined by subtracting 1.9 cm from the working distance (d_w) computed from motor count:

$$d_s = d_w - 1.9 \text{ cm} \quad (3)$$

4.2.3 Distance or range uncertainty estimate

Estimation approach applied to the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

For the Sol 0–945 period (except Sol 687), the uncertainty in distance (whether expressed as d_w or d_s) was estimated using an early version of our team’s understanding (Edgett *et al.* 2013) of the flight unit MAHLI depth of field (DOF; d_{old_DOF} , in centimeters) as a function of working distance (d_w).

The method for estimating the far range of the DOF, d_{old_far} , was:

$$d_{old_far} = ad_w^5 - bd_w^4 + cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 + ed_w - f \quad (4)$$

in which $a = 2.067963396 \times 10^{-10}$, $b = 5.81503025785 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 1.55563715379086 \times 10^{-5}$, $d = 1.78558768966003 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 7.87243271888297 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 3.57047935299353 \times 10^{-2}$.

The method for estimating the near range of the DOF, d_{old_near} , was:

$$d_{old_near} = -(ad_w^5 + bd_w^4 - cd_w^3 + dd_w^2 - ed_w + f) \quad (5)$$

in which $a = -9.6497783 \times 10^{-12}$, $b = 1.06050131902 \times 10^{-8}$, $c = 5.8615047292452 \times 10^{-6}$, $d = 2.42284468424977 \times 10^{-3}$, $e = 4.28714139095939 \times 10^{-3}$, and $f = 7.534391000189 \times 10^{-4}$.

The MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* added the absolute values of the near and far DOF, then divided by two, to provide an overall uncertainty, $\pm d_{old_DOF}$, in centimeters:

$$\pm d_{old_DOF} = ((-d_{old_near}) + d_{old_far})/2 \quad (6)$$

The $\pm d_{old_DOF}$ estimate was sufficient for using MAHLI as a range finder for subsequent scoop placement during the Rocknest sample extraction campaign (Minitti *et al.* 2013; Anderson *et al.* 2015).

Improved estimation method, used for Sol 687 and after Sol 945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*

Later analysis refined our DOF estimate (Edgett *et al.* 2015), but these results arrived too late to be incorporated into most of the Sol 0–945 *Range and Scale Information Sheets*. That said, for small working distances (e.g., < 20 cm), the results are about the same. As a function of dust cover open focus motor count (m_{open}), the near (d_{near}) and far (d_{far}) depth of field can be expressed, in centimeters, as:

$$d_{near} \text{ or } d_{far} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (7)$$

in which, for d_{near} , $a = 1.03565$, $b = -11.9083$, $c = 2.82403 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.29003 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.34332 \times 10^{-12}$; and, for d_{far} , $a = 1.03438$, $b = -11.4118$, $c = 2.69297 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.17752 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.02494 \times 10^{-12}$.

4.2.4 Pixel scale

The estimated pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel) is based on working distance (d_w) and applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. We estimate the scale from the working distance (d_w) as described by Edgett *et al.* (2012):

$$p = 6.9001 + 3.5201d_w. \quad (8)$$

4.2.5 Pixel scale uncertainty estimate

No estimation applied to the Sol 0–998 range and scale information sheets

No estimate of pixel scale uncertainty was applied to the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* until Sol 999.

Estimation approach

Pixel scale uncertainty (p_{far} , p_{near} , $\pm p_{uncertainty}$, in μm per pixel) can be estimated based on the depth of field (d_{far} , d_{near} , in centimeters; **Equation 7**) and pixel scale (p , in μm per pixel, **Equation 8**) as determined from working distance (d_w , in centimeters; **Equation 1**). The uncertainty applies only to the in-focus portions of a given image. The uncertainty can be estimated as follows (please round $\pm p_{uncertainty}$ to the nearest 0.1 μm per pixel):

$$p_{far} = (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{far})) - p, \quad (9)$$

$$p_{near} = p - (6.9001 + 3.5201(d_w + d_{near})), \text{ and} \quad (10)$$

$$\pm p_{uncertainty} = (p_{far} + p_{near})/2. \quad (11)$$

4.2.6 Image dimensions estimate

The image dimension estimates described in the MAHLI *Range and Scale Information Sheets* are computed by multiplying the estimated pixel scale (p) by the number of horizontal (columns) and vertical (rows) covered by the image. This simplistic approach, of course, assumes that the target is a plane parallel to the CCD.

Sol 3425 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Donkey_Trail - before DRT													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3425MH0001900011201629C00	1629	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3425MH0001220011201631C00	1631	14049	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6

target named Burn_Mouth- quantitative relief model (QRM) data															
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3425MH0001900011201633C00	1633	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00173	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3425MH0001730011201635C00	1635	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3427MH0001630001201712R00				range map product:						3427MH0001630001201713S00	
mhl00173	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3425MH0001730011201645C00	1645	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3427MH0001630001201710R00				range map product:						3427MH0001630001201711S00	
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 3		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3425MH0007050011201655C00	1655	14009	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 4		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3425MH0007050011201657C00	1657	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 5		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3425MH0007050011201659C00	1659	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhl00838	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3425MH0008380011201661C00	1661	15132	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3427MH0001630001201708R00				range map product:						3427MH0001630001201709S00	

target named Donkey_Trail - after DRT															
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3425MH0001900011201671C00	1671	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3425MH0001680011201673C00	1673	14047	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3427MH0001630001201706R00				range map product:						3427MH0001630001201707S00	
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3425MH0001680011201683C00	1683	14047	6.5	4.6	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3427MH0001630001201704R00				range map product:						3427MH0001630001201705S00	
mhl00743	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3425MH0007430011201693C00	1693	15236	2.6	0.7	0.0	0.1	16.0	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	1.9		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3427MH0001630001201702R00				range map product:						3427MH0001630001201703S00	

Sol 3428 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Venlaw - after DRT															
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3428MH0001900011201715C00	1715	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3428MH0002990011201717C00	1717	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201860R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201861S00
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3428MH0002990011201727C00	1727	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201858R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201859S00
mhl00302	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3428MH0003020011201737C00	1737	14651	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201856R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201857S00

target named Venlaw - a 1 x 6 mosaic															
mhl00342	position 1 of 6		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3428MH0003420011201747C00	1747	13555	11.1	9.2	-0.4	0.3	45.8	1.2	1608	1198	7.4	5.5		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201854R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201855S00
mhl00342	position 2 of 6		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3428MH0003420011201757C00	1757	13560	11.0	9.1	-0.4	0.3	45.6	1.2	1608	1198	7.3	5.5		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201852R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201853S00
mhl00342	position 3 of 6		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3428MH0003420011201767C00	1767	13580	10.7	8.8	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.3		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201850R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201851S00
mhl00342	position 4 of 6		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3428MH0003420011201777C00	1777	13602	10.4	8.5	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	1608	1198	7.0	5.2		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201848R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201849S00
mhl00342	position 5 of 6		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3428MH0003420011201787C00	1787	13730	9.0	7.1	-0.3	0.2	38.7	0.9	1608	1198	6.2	4.6		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201846R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201847S00
mhl00342	position 6 of 6		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	Note: The standoff distance ended up being closer than anticipated; thus the camera was unable to find focus using the commanded autofocus range. The range and scale reported below are for the parts of the image that are in-focus at this motor count.														
	3428MH0003420011201797C00	1797	13878	7.7	5.8	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	1608	1198	5.5	4.1		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201844R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201845S00	

target named Broadfell															
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3428MH0001900011201807C00	1807	13015	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1		
mhl00308	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3428MH0003080011201809C00	1809	13943	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201842R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201843S00
mhl00308	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3428MH0003080011201819C00	1819	13962	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201840R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201841S00
mhl00716	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3428MH0007160011201829C00	1829	14955	3.1	1.2	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	1608	1198	2.9	2.1		
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3429MH0004580001201838R00				range map product:						3429MH0004580001201839S00

Sol 3432 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Blue_Anchor- quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3432MH0007060011201863C00	1863	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhli00708	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0007080011201866C00	1866	13963	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201943R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201944S00								
mhli00708	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0007080011201877C00	1877	13921	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201941R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201942S00								
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0007050011201888C00	1888	13955	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0007050011201890C00	1890	13983	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0007050011201892C00	1892	13963	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
mhli00795	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3432MH0007950011201894C00	1894	14616	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201939R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201940S00								

target named Baa - quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3432MH0007060011201905C00	1905	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
mhli00803	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0008030011201908C00	1908	14185	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201937R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201938S00								
mhli00803	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0008030011201919C00	1919	14173	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201935R00			<i>range map product:</i> 3433MH0002270001201936S00								
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0007050011201930C00	1930	14178	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0007050011201932C00	1932	14190	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.2
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3432MH0007050011201934C00	1934	14189	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3

last update: 08_April_2022

Sol 3436 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Broo**

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3436MH0001900011201946C00	1946	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3436MH0001680011201948C00	1948	14039	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product: 3436MH0001930001201981R00			range map product: 3436MH0001930001201982S00								
mhl00168	medium-r resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3436MH0001680011201958C00	1958	14042	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product: 3436MH0001930001201979R00			range map product: 3436MH0001930001201980S00								
mhl00302	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3436MH0003020011201968C00	1968	14764	3.6	1.7	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.3
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product: 3436MH0001930001201977R00			range map product: 3436MH0001930001201978S00								

Sol 3439 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Lodberrie**

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3439MH0007060011201984C00	1985	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2	
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3439MH0007230011201987C00	1987	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202099R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202100S00
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3439MH0007230011201998C00	1998	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202097R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202098S00
mhl00746	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3439MH0007460011202009C00	2009	14687	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202095R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202096S00

target named **Sneuga**

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3439MH0001900011202020C00	2020	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1	
mhl00152	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3439MH0001520011202022C00	2022	13977	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202093R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202094S00
mhl00152	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3439MH0001520011202032C00	2032	13983	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202091R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202092S00
mhl00176	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3439MH0001760011202042C00	2042	14623	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202089R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202090S00

target named **Inchbonny - a 1 x 3 mosaic from 5 cm standoff**

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3439MH0001900011202052C00	2052	13053	24.5	22.6	-1.5	1.7	93.1	5.7	1608	1198	15.0	11.2	
mhl00299	position 1 of 3	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3439MH0002990011202054C00	2054	14181	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202087R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202088S00
mhl00299	position 2 of 3	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3439MH0002990011202064C00	2064	14063	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202085R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202086S00
mhl00299	position 3 of 3	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3439MH0002990011202074C00	2074	14012	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3440MH0005360001202083R00				range map product:					3440MH0005360001202084S00

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Brackenberry - before DRT													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3442MH0001900011202102C00	2102	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0
mhl00122	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3442MH0001220011202104C00	2104	13969	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8

target named Brackenberry - after DRT															
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3442MH0001900011202106C00	2106	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3442MH0001680011202108C00	2108	13967	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202219R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202220S00	
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3442MH0001680011202118C00	2118	13974	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202217R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202218S00	
mhl00302	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3442MH0003020011202128C00	2128	14600	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202215R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202216S00	

target named Skidbladner - 2x1 mosaic from 25 cm															
mhl00190	position 1 of 2		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3442MH0001900011202138C00	2138	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8		
mhl00190	position 2 of 2		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3442MH0001900011202140C00	2140	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2		
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3442MH0001730011202142C00	2142	13961	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202213R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202214S00	
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3442MH0001730011202152C00	2152	13956	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202211R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202212S00	
mhl00184	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3442MH0001840011202162C00	2162	14607	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202209R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202210S00	

target named Up_Helly_Aa															
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3442MH0001900011202172C00	2172	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhl00224	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3442MH0002240011202174C00	2174	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202207R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202208S00	
mhl00224	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3442MH0002240011202184C00	2184	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202205R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202206S00	
mhl00176	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3442MH0001760011202194C00	2194	14652	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3442MH0005360001202203R00				range map product:						3442MH0005360001202204S00	

last update: 15_April_2022

Sol 3444 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Dun													
mhl00172	context view		intended standoff - 20 cm										
	3444MH0001720011202222C00	2222	13108	21.9	20.0	-1.2	1.3	83.9	4.5	1608	1198	13.5	10.0
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3444MH0003060011202224C00	2224	13968	7.1	5.2	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3444MH0001930001202257R00			range map product: 3444MH0001930001202258S00							
mhl00306	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3444MH0003060011202234C00	2234	13977	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3444MH0001930001202255R00			range map product: 3444MH0001930001202256S00							
mhl00311	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3444MH0003110011202244C00	2244	14610	4.1	2.2	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	1608	1198	3.4	2.5
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product: 3444MH0001930001202253R00			range map product: 3444MH0001930001202254S00							

Sol 3447 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Spiggie_Beach

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3447MH0001900011202260C00	2260	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7	
mhl00297	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3447MH0002970011202262C00	2262	14151	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3447MH0008170001202314R00				range map product:					3447MH0008170001202315S00
mhl00297	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3447MH0002970011202272C00	2272	14117	6.1	4.2	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3447MH0008170001202312R00				range map product:					3447MH0008170001202313S00

target named Bains_Beach

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3447MH0007060011202282C00	2282	13042	25.1	23.2	-1.6	1.8	95.2	5.9	1608	1198	15.3	11.4	
mhl00740	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3447MH0007400011202285C00	2285	14281	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3447MH0008170001202310R00				range map product:					3447MH0008170001202311S00
mhl00740	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3447MH0007400011202296C00	2296	14287	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3447MH0008170001202308R00				range map product:					3447MH0008170001202309S00

left front rover wheel/rock contact – mobility obstruction assessment

mhl00262	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to wheel-rock contact: ~112 cm											
	3447MH0002620001202306E01	2306	12660	~113	~111	~-27	~50	~400	~135	1608	1198	~64	~48
mhl00262	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to wheel-rock contact: ~112 cm											
	3447MH0002620001202307E01	2307	12660	~113	~111	~-27	~50	~400	~135	1608	1198	~64	~48

last update: 20_April_2022

Sol 3449 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named *Runn*

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3449MH0001900011202317C00	2317	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3449MH0002240011202319C00	2319	14027	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3449MH0002650001202342R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3449MH0002650001202343S00				
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3449MH0002240011202329C00	2329	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3449MH0002650001202340R00				<i>range map product:</i>		3449MH0002650001202341S00				

REMS UV sensor

mhli00095	standard viewing position	intended standoff: ~15 cm											
	3449MH0000950011202339C00	2339	13259	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.8	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Rumbblings

mhl00842	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3451MH0008420011202345C00	2345	13036	25.4	23.5	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.5		
mhl00843	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3451MH0008430011202348C00	2348	14221	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3451MH0001700001202455R00				range map product:					3451MH0001700001202456S00	
mhl00843	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3451MH0008430011202359C00	2359	14212	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3451MH0001700001202453R00				range map product:					3451MH0001700001202454S00	

target named Shandon - after DRT

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3451MH0007060011202370C00	2370	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3451MH0007630011202373C00	2373	13989	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3451MH0001700001202451R00				range map product:					3451MH0001700001202452S00	
mhl00763	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3451MH0007630011202384C00	2384	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3451MH0001700001202449R00				range map product:					3451MH0001700001202450S00	
mhl00824	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm													
	3451MH0008240011202395C00	2395	14648	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3451MH0001700001202447R00				range map product:					3451MH0001700001202448S00	

target named Nesting

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3451MH0007060011202406C00	2406	13005	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3		
mhl00699	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3451MH0006990011202409C00	2409	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3451MH0001700001202445R00				range map product:					3451MH0001700001202446S00	
mhl00699	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3451MH0006990011202420C00	2420	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3451MH0001700001202443R00				range map product:					3451MH0001700001202444S00	
mhl00824	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm													
	3451MH0008240011202431C00	2431	14718	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3451MH0001700001202441R00				range map product:					3451MH0001700001202442S00	

Sol 3453 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named *Delting* - after DRT - quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3453MH0007060011202458C00	2458	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00763	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3453MH0007630011202461C00	2461	13998	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202546R00					<i>range map product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202547S00				
mhli00763	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3453MH0007630011202472C00	2472	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202544R00					<i>range map product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202545S00				
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3453MH0007050011202483C00	2483	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3453MH0007050011202485C00	2485	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3453MH0007050011202487C00	2487	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00813	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3453MH0008130011202489C00	2489	14691	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202542R00					<i>range map product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202543S00				

target named *Rumblings*

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3453MH0007060011202500C00	2500	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3453MH0007090011202503C00	2503	14026	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202540R00					<i>range map product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202541S00				
mhli00709	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3453MH0007090011202514C00	2514	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202538R00					<i>range map product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202539S00				
mhli00711	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3453MH0007110011202525C00	2525	14737	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>	<i>best focus product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202536R00					<i>range map product:</i>	3454MH0001630001202537S00				

left front rover wheel – Sol 3447 mobility obstruction assessment follow-up

mhli00262	left (port) front wheel	intended distance to wheel: ~112 cm											
	3453MH0002620001202535E02	2535	12660	~113	~111	~-27	~50	~400	~135	1608	1198	~64	~48

last update: 27_April_2022

Sol 3456 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Colla_Firth													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3456MH0007060011202549C00	2549	13025	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3456MH0001820011202552C00	2552	14062	6.5	4.6	-0.1	0.1	29.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.5
		corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3456MH0002650001202573R00				range map product:		3456MH0002650001202574S00			
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3456MH0001820011202562C00	2562	14064	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.5
		corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3456MH0002650001202571R00				range map product:		3456MH0002650001202572S00			

last update: 29_April_2022

Sol 3458 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Orton_Scar													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3458MH0007060011202576C00	2576	13036	25.4	23.5	-1.6	1.8	96.3	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.5
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3458MH0001730011202579C00	2579	14172	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3458MH0002270001202639R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3458MH0002270001202640S00				
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3458MH0001730011202589C00	2589	14192	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.2
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3458MH0002270001202637R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3458MH0002270001202638S00				

target named Cow_Head													
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3458MH0007060011202599C00	2599	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3458MH0001820011202602C00	2602	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3458MH0002270001202635R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3458MH0002270001202636S00				
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3458MH0001820011202612C00	2612	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3458MH0002270001202633R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3458MH0002270001202634S00				
mhl00176	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3458MH0001760011202622C00	2622	14692	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3458MH0002270001202631R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3458MH0002270001202632S00				

Sol 3459 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named CastleCraig - quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhli00845	context view	intended standoff - 20 cm													
	3459MH0008450011202642C00	2642	13104	22.0	20.1	-1.2	1.4	84.5	4.6	1608	1198	13.6	10.1		
mhli00740	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3459MH0007400011202645C00	2645	13931	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>			3461MH0002270001202714R00				<i>range map product:</i>					3461MH0002270001202715S00	
mhli00740	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3459MH0007400011202656C00	2656	13924	7.4	5.5	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>			3461MH0002270001202712R00				<i>range map product:</i>					3461MH0002270001202713S00	
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3459MH0007050011202667C00	2667	13930	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9		
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3459MH0007050011202669C00	2669	13944	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3459MH0007050011202671C00	2671	13933	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9		
mhli00844	high resolution view	intended standoff - 3 cm													
	3459MH0008440011202673C00	2673	14277	5.3	3.4	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.1		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>			3461MH0002270001202710R00				<i>range map product:</i>					3461MH0002270001202711S00	

target named Cat_Firth

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3459MH0007060011202684C00	2684	13016	26.6	24.7	-1.8	2.0	100.5	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.0		
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3459MH0001820011202687C00	2687	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>			3461MH0002270001202708R00				<i>range map product:</i>					3461MH0002270001202709S00	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3459MH0001820011202697C00	2697	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>			3461MH0002270001202706R00				<i>range map product:</i>					3461MH0002270001202707S00	

Sol 3462 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Gran_Sabana**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3462MH0001900011202717C00	2717	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3462MH0002990011202719C00	2719	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3462MH0002270001202778R00				range map product:					3462MH0002270001202779S00
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3462MH0002990011202729C00	2729	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3462MH0002270001202776R00				range map product:					3462MH0002270001202777S00
mhli00311	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3462MH0003110011202739C00	2739	14733	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3462MH0002270001202774R00				range map product:					3462MH0002270001202775S00

target named **Berbice**

mhli00172	context view	intended standoff - 20 cm												
	3462MH0001720011202749C00	2749	13109	21.8	19.9	-1.2	1.3	83.7	4.5	1608	1198	13.5	10.0	
mhli00363	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3462MH0003630011202751C00	2751	13938	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3462MH0002270001202772R00				range map product:					3462MH0002270001202773S00
mhli00363	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3462MH0003630011202761C00	2761	13927	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	3.9	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3462MH0002270001202770R00				range map product:					3462MH0002270001202771S00

Sol 3465 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)		

target named Firina - a 2 x 1 mosaic

mhli00846	position 1 of 2	intended standoff - 20 cm											
	3465MH0008460011202781C00	2781	13103	22.1	20.2	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	1608	1198	13.6	10.1
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3465MH0001930001202816R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3465MH0001930001202817S00					
mhli00846	position 2 of 2	intended standoff - 20 cm											
	3465MH0008460011202791C00	2791	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3465MH0001930001202814R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3465MH0001930001202815S00					

target named Bartica

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3465MH0001900011202801C00	2801	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6
mhli00224	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3465MH0002240011202803C00	2803	14178	5.8	3.9	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3465MH0001930001202812R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3465MH0001930001202813S00					

Sol 3466 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Bonfim

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3466MH0001900011202819C00	2819	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3466MH0001730011202821C00	2821	14029	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3466MH0001630001202900R00				range map product:					3466MH0001202901S00	
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3466MH0001730011202831C00	2831	14031	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3466MH0001630001202898R00				range map product:					3466MH0001630001202895S00	
mhl00176	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm													
	3466MH0001760011202841C00	2841	14739	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3466MH0001630001202896R00				range map product:					3466MH0001630001202897S00	

target named Kurupukari - a 4 x 1 mosaic

mhl00190	position 1 of 4	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3466MH0001900011202851C00	2851	13059	24.2	22.3	-1.5	1.6	92.0	5.5	1608	1198	14.8	11.0
mhl00190	position 2 of 4	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3466MH0001900011202853C00	2853	13049	24.7	22.8	-1.5	1.7	93.8	5.8	1608	1198	15.1	11.2
mhl00190	position 3 of 4	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3466MH0001900011202855C00	2855	13049	24.7	22.8	-1.5	1.7	93.8	5.8	1608	1198	15.1	11.2
mhl00190	position 4 of 4	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3466MH0001900011202857C00	2857	13055	24.4	22.5	-1.5	1.7	92.7	5.6	1608	1198	14.9	11.1

target named Oshi

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3466MH0001900011202859C00	2859	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3466MH0001820011202861C00	2861	13993	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3466MH0001630001202894R00				range map product:					3466MH0001630001202895S00	
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3466MH0001820011202871C00	2871	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3466MH0001630001202892R00				range map product:					3466MH0001630001202893S00	
mhl00426	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	3466MH0004260011202881C00	2881	15070	2.9	1.0	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3466MH0001630001202890R00				range map product:					3466MH0001630001202891S00	

Sol 3469 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **El_Oso**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3469MH0001900011202903C00	2903	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3469MH0002240011202905C00	2905	14041	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.1	0.5	1608	1198	4.8	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3469MH0001530001202952R00				range map product:					3469MH0001530001202953S00	
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3469MH0002240011202915C00	2915	14077	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3469MH0001530001202950R00				range map product:					3469MH0001530001202951S00	

target named **Parima**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3469MH0001900011202925C00	2925	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3469MH0001730011202927C00	2927	14035	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3469MH0001530001202948R00				range map product:					3469MH0001530001202949S00	
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3469MH0001730011202937C00	2937	14034	6.6	4.7	-0.2	0.1	30.2	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3469MH0001530001202946R00				range map product:					3469MH0001530001202947S00	

Sol 3471 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named *Pastora* - after DRT - quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3471MH0001900011202955C00	2955	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhli00173	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3471MH0001730011202957C00	2957	13991	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3472MH0002270001203022R00				range map product:					3472MH0002270001203023S00	
mhli00173	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3471MH0001730011202967C00	2967	13994	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3472MH0002270001203020R00				range map product:					3472MH0002270001203021S00	
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3471MH0007050011202977C00	2977	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3471MH0007050011202979C00	2979	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3471MH0007050011202981C00	2981	13988	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
mhli00174	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm													
	3471MH0001740011202983C00	2983	14651	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3472MH0002270001203018R00				range map product:					3472MH0002270001203019S00	

target named *Tama_Tama*

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3471MH0001900011202993C00	2993	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3471MH0001680011202995C00	2995	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3472MH0002270001203016R00				range map product:					3472MH0002270001203017S00	
mhli00168	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3471MH0001680011203005C00	3005	14016	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3472MH0002270001203014R00				range map product:					3472MH0002270001203015S00	

last update: 16_May_2022

Sol 3473 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **San_Pedro** - after DRT

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3473MH0001900011203025C00	3025	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3473MH0002990011203027C00	3027	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3474MH0002270001203086R00				range map product:					3474MH0002270001203087S00
mhli00299	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3473MH0002990011203037C00	3037	14015	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3474MH0002270001203084R00				range map product:					3474MH0002270001203085S00
mhli00337	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3473MH0003370011203047C00	3047	14715	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3474MH0002270001203082R00				range map product:					3474MH0002270001203083S00

target named **Pedra_Pintada**

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3473MH0001900011203057C00	3057	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3473MH0001820011203059C00	3059	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3474MH0002270001203080R00				range map product:					3474MH0002270001203081S00
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3473MH0001820011203069C00	3069	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3474MH0002270001203078R00				range map product:					3474MH0002270001203079S00

last update: 18_May_2022

Sol 3476 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Aratana													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3476MH0001900011203089C00	3089	13028	25.9	24.0	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	1608	1198	15.8	11.7
mhli00841	intermediate-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 15 cm										
	3476MH0008410011203091C00	3091	13289	16.0	14.1	-0.7	0.7	63.1	2.4	1608	1198	10.1	7.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3476MH0002650001203112R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3476MH0002650001203113S00				
mhli00841	intermediate-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 15 cm										
	3476MH0008410011203101C00	3101	13290	15.9	14.0	-0.7	0.7	63.0	2.4	1608	1198	10.1	7.5
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3476MH0002650001203110R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3476MH0002650001203111S00				

Sol 3478 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Las_Claritas - a 3 x 2 mosaic													
mhli00291	position 1 of 6	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3478MH0002910011203115C00	3115	13531	11.4	9.5	-0.4	0.4	47.0	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.6
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203222R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203223S00					
mhli00291	position 2 of 6	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3478MH0002910011203125C00	3125	13605	10.4	8.5	-0.3	0.3	43.5	1.1	1608	1198	7.0	5.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203220R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203221S00					
mhli00291	position 3 of 6	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3478MH0002910011203135C00	3135	13597	10.5	8.6	-0.3	0.3	43.9	1.1	1608	1198	7.1	5.3
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203218R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203219S00					
mhli00291	position 4 of 6	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3478MH0002910011203145C00	3145	13529	11.4	9.5	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.6
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203216R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203217S00					
mhli00291	position 5 of 6	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3478MH0002910011203155C00	3155	13530	11.4	9.5	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	1608	1198	7.6	5.6
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203214R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203215S00					
mhli00291	position 6 of 6	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3478MH0002910011203165C00	3165	13601	10.5	8.6	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	1608	1198	7.0	5.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203212R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203213S00					

target named Las_Claritas - after DRT													
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3478MH0001900011203175C00	3175	13025	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.6	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3478MH0001820011203177C00	3177	14077	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203210R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203211S00					
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3478MH0001820011203187C00	3187	14078	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203208R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203209S00					
mhli00302	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3478MH0003020011203197C00	3197	14866	3.3	1.4	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	1608	1198	3.0	2.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3478MH0005360001203206R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3478MH0005360001203207S00					

Sol 3480 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Maple_Creek**

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3480MH0001900011203225C00	3225	13013	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1		
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3480MH0001730011203227C00	3227	13973	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3481MH0001710001203312R00				range map product:					3481MH0001710001203313S00	
mhl00173	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3480MH0001730011203237C00	3237	13972	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3481MH0001710001203310R00				range map product:					3481MH0001710001203311S00	

target named **Apoteri**

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3480MH0001900011203247C00	3247	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
mhl00152	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3480MH0001520011203249C00	3249	14224	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3481MH0001710001203308R00				range map product:					3481MH0001710001203309S00	
mhl00152	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3480MH0001520011203259C00	3259	14228	5.6	3.7	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3481MH0001710001203306R00				range map product:					3481MH0001710001203307S00	

target named **Bamboo_Creek - after DRT**

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3480MH0001900011203269C00	3269	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3480MH0001820011203271C00	3271	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3481MH0001710001203304R00				range map product:					3481MH0001710001203305S00	
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	3480MH0001820011203281C00	3281	13985	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3481MH0001710001203302R00				range map product:					3481MH0001710001203303S00	
mhl00743	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	3480MH0007430011203291C00	3291	15037	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:			3481MH0001710001203300R00				range map product:					3481MH0001710001203301S00	

last update: 25_May_2022

Sol 3483 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Imataca - after DRT													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3483MH0001900011203315C00	3315	13021	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.4	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00173	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3483MH0001730011203317C00	3317	14023	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3483MH0001930001203350R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3483MH0001930001203351S00				
mhli00173	medium-r resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3483MH0001730011203327C00	3327	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3483MH0001930001203348R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3483MH0001930001203349S00				
mhli00337	high resolution view		intended standoff - 2 cm										
	3483MH0003370011203337C00	3338	14742	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3483MH0001930001203346R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3483MH0001930001203347S00				

last update: 27_May_2022

Sol 3485 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Cabo_Sobral - a 3 x 1 mosaic from 25 cm standoff

mhl00359	position 1 of 3	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3485MH0003590011203353C00	3353	13031	25.7	23.8	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	1608	1198	15.7	11.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3485MH0002270001203410R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3485MH0002270001203411S00					
mhl00359	position 2 of 3	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3485MH0003590011203363C00	3363	13051	24.6	22.7	-1.5	1.7	93.5	5.7	1608	1198	15.0	11.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3485MH0002270001203408R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3485MH0002270001203409S00					
mhl00359	position 3 of 3	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3485MH0003590011203373C00	3373	13071	23.6	21.7	-1.4	1.6	89.9	5.2	1608	1198	14.5	10.8
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3485MH0002270001203406R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3485MH0002270001203407S00					
mhl00847	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 7 cm											
	3485MH0008470011203383C00	3383	13725	9.1	7.2	-0.3	0.2	38.8	0.9	1608	1198	6.2	4.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3485MH0002270001203404R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3485MH0002270001203405S00					
mhl00847	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 7 cm											
	3485MH0008470011203393C00	3393	13759	8.7	6.8	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	1608	1198	6.1	4.5
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3485MH0002270001203402R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3485MH0002270001203403S00					

last update: 14_June_2022

Sol 3488 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Pitinga - no DRT - APXS raster spot 1													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3488MH0001900011203413C00	3413	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00168	medium-resolution view		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3488MH0001680011203415C00	3415	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3488MH0001530001203468R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3488MH0001530001203469S00					

target named Pitinga - after DRT - APXS raster spot 2 - quantitative relief model (QRM) data													
mhli00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3488MH0001900011203425C00	3425	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00168	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3488MH0001680011203427C00	3427	14011	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3488MH0001530001203466R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3488MH0001530001203467S00					
mhli00168	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3488MH0001680011203437C00	3437	14005	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3488MH0001530001203464R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3488MH0001530001203465S00					
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 3		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3488MH0007050011203447C00	3447	14008	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 4		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3488MH0007050011203449C00	3449	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00705	med res - relief model position 5		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3488MH0007050011203451C00	3451	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhli00848	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3488MH0008480011203453C00	3453	15109	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3488MH0001530001203462R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3488MH0001530001203463S00					

Sol 3491 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

*Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Parepona - after DRT													
mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3491MH0001900011203471C00	3471	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3491MH0001820011203473C00	3473	14021	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3491MH0001630001203544R00					range map product:	3491MH0001630001203545S00				
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3491MH0001820011203483C00	3483	14024	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3491MH0001630001203542R00					range map product:	3491MH0001630001203543S00				
mhl00302	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3491MH0003020011203493C00	3493	14729	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	1608	1198	3.2	2.4
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3491MH0001630001203540R00					range map product:	3491MH0001630001203541S00				

target named Cabadiscana													
mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3491MH0001900011203503C00	3503	13012	26.8	24.9	-1.8	2.0	101.3	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.1
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3491MH0002990011203505C00	3505	13948	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3491MH0001630001203538R00					range map product:	3491MH0001630001203539S00				
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3491MH0002990011203515C00	3515	13950	7.2	5.3	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3491MH0001630001203536R00					range map product:	3491MH0001630001203537S00				
mhl00311	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm											
	3491MH0003110011203525C00	3525	14553	4.2	2.3	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.5	2.6
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3491MH0001630001203534R00					range map product:	3491MH0001630001203535S00				

Sol 3492 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 1 of 5 (performed on sol 3492)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3492MH0007690011203546E01	3546	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3492MH0007700011203547E01	3547	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3492MH0007710011203548E01	3548	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3492MH0007720011203549E01	3549	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 2 of 5 (performed on sol 3492)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3492MH0007690011203550E01	3550	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3492MH0007700011203551E01	3551	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3492MH0007710011203552E01	3552	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3492MH0007720011203553E01	3553	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 3 of 5 (performed on sol 3492)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3492MH0007690011203554E01	3554	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3492MH0007700011203555E01	3555	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3492MH0007710011203556E01	3556	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3492MH0007720011203557E01	3557	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 4 of 5 (performed on sol 3492)

mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3492MH0007690011203558E01	3558	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3492MH0007700011203559E01	3559	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3492MH0007710011203560E01	3560	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3492MH0007720011203561E01	3561	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

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rover wheel inspection - top view, looking down on wheels - full wheel inspection, position 5 of 5 (performed on sol 3492)													
mhl00769	left (port) rear wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~170 cm											
	3492MH0007690011203562E01	3562	12618	~172	~170	~-0.6 m	~-1.6 m	~612	n/a	1608	1198	~98	~73
mhl00770	left (port) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~112 cm											
	3492MH0007700011203563E01	3563	12660	~114	~112	~-28	~-50	~408	~137	1608	1198	~65	~49
mhl00771	left (port) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~135 cm											
	3492MH0007710011203564E01	3564	12642	~137	~135	~-38	~-82	~489	~210	1608	1198	~78	~59
mhl00772	right (starboard) front wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to top of wheel: ~124 cm											
	3492MH0007720011203565E01	3565	12648	~126	~124	~-32	~-67	~450	~175	1608	1198	~72	~54

Sol 3493 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Tabaco - a 4 x 1 mosaic

mhl00849	position 1 of 4	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3493MH0008490011203567C00	3567	13203	18.4	16.5	-0.9	0.9	71.5	3.2	1608	1198	11.5	8.6
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3493MH0001710001203656R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3493MH0001710001203657S00					
mhl00849	position 2 of 4	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3493MH0008490011203577C00	3577	13218	17.9	16.0	-0.8	0.9	69.9	3.0	1608	1198	11.2	8.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3493MH0001710001203654R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3493MH0001710001203655S00					
mhl00849	position 3 of 4	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3493MH0008490011203587C00	3587	13229	17.6	15.7	-0.8	0.9	68.8	2.9	1608	1198	11.1	8.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3493MH0001710001203652R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3493MH0001710001203653S00					
mhl00849	position 4 of 4	intended standoff - 15 cm											
	3493MH0008490011203597C00	3597	13228	17.6	15.7	-0.8	0.9	68.9	2.9	1608	1198	11.1	8.2
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3493MH0001710001203650R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3493MH0001710001203651S00					

target named Issano - after DRT - quantitative relief model (QRM) data

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3493MH0001900011203607C00	3607	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00168	med res - stereo-1 & relief model position 1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3493MH0001680011203609C00	3609	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3493MH0001710001203648R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3493MH0001710001203649S00					
mhl00168	med res - stereo-2 & relief model position 2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3493MH0001680011203619C00	3619	14003	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3493MH0001710001203646R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3493MH0001710001203647S00					
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 3	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3493MH0007050011203629C00	3629	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 4	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3493MH0007050011203631C00	3631	14000	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl00705	med res - relief model position 5	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3493MH0007050011203633C00	3633	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
mhl00743	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm											
	3493MH0007430011203635C00	3635	15112	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3493MH0001710001203644R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3493MH0001710001203645S00					

Sol 3503 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

ChemCam mirror/window and RWEB

ChemCam mirror/window and RWEB														
mhli00520	RWEB full frame													
	3503MH0005200011203659C00	3659	13100	22.2	20.3	-1.3	1.4	85.1	4.7	1608	1198	13.7	10.2	
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3503MH0008500001203772R00				range map product:				3503MH0008500001203773S00	
	manual focus on interior hardware													
3503MH0005200041203677C00	3677	12990	28.3	26.4	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	1024	1200	10.9	12.8		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3503MH0008500001203770R00				range map product:				3503MH0008500001203771S00		

target named Wandapa - a 3 x 1 mosaic from 5 cm standoff

target named Wandapa - a 3 x 1 mosaic from 5 cm standoff													
mhli00706	context view												
	3503MH0007060011203687C00	3687	13023	26.2	24.3	-1.7	1.9	99.0	6.5	1608	1198	15.9	11.9
mhli00740	position 1 of 3												
	3503MH0007400011203690C00	3690	14066	6.4	4.5	-0.1	0.1	29.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.7	3.5
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3503MH0008500001203768R00				range map product:				3503MH0008500001203769S00
mhli00740	position 2 of 3												
	3503MH0007400011203701C00	3701	14155	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3503MH0008500001203766R00				range map product:				3503MH0008500001203767S00
mhli00740	position 3 of 3												
	3503MH0007400011203712C00	3712	14107	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3503MH0008500001203764R00				range map product:				3503MH0008500001203765S00

target named Omai - after DRT

target named Omai - after DRT													
mhli00706	context view												
	3503MH0007060011203723C00	3723	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-1												
	3503MH0007230011203726C00	3726	13995	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3503MH0008500001203762R00				range map product:				3503MH0008500001203763S00
mhli00723	medium-resolution stereo-2												
	3503MH0007230011203737C00	3737	13997	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3503MH0008500001203760R00				range map product:				3503MH0008500001203761S00
mhli00656	high resolution view												
	3503MH0006560011203748C00	3748	14668	3.9	2.0	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5
	corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3503MH0008500001203758R00				range map product:				3503MH0008500001203759S00

Sol 3505 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID *	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named **Tipuru**

mhl00359	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3505MH0003590011203775C00	3775	13046	24.9	23.0	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	1608	1198	15.2	11.3	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3505MH0002580001203808R00				range map product:						3505MH0002580001203809S00

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - first set

mhl00712	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0007120001203784C00	3784	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm standoff equivalent - ~3.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0007120011203785C00	3785	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm standoff equivalent - ~6.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0007120021203786C00	3786	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm standoff equivalent - ~26.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
3505MH0007120031203787C00	3787	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
infinity focus - manual focus													
3505MH0007120041203788C00	3788	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - first set

mhl00453	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0004530001203789C00	3789	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm standoff equivalent - ~3.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0004530011203790C00	3790	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm standoff equivalent - ~6.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0004530021203791C00	3791	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm standoff equivalent - ~26.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
3505MH0004530031203792C00	3792	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
pre-launch flat field equivalent - ~63.3 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
3505MH0004530041203793C00	3793	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
infinity focus - manual focus													
3505MH0004530051203794C00	3794	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover open - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl00453	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0004530001203795C00	3795	15996	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm standoff equivalent - ~3.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0004530011203796C00	3796	14664	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm standoff equivalent - ~6.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0004530021203797C00	3797	13998	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm standoff equivalent - ~26.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
3505MH0004530031203798C00	3798	13014	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
pre-launch flat field equivalent - ~63.3 cm working distance focus position - manual focus													
3505MH0004530041203799C00	3799	12750	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
infinity focus - manual focus													
3505MH0004530051203800C00	3800	12552	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

MAHLI sky flat field images - dust cover closed - second set (camera rotated approximately 180° relative to first set)

mhl00712	close focus - ~2.04 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0007120001203801C00	3801	0	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	2 cm standoff equivalent - ~3.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0007120011203802C00	3802	2412	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	5 cm standoff equivalent - ~6.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
	3505MH0007120021203803C00	3803	3078	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a
	25 cm standoff equivalent - ~26.9 cm working distance focus position - manual focus												
3505MH0007120031203804C00	3804	4062	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	
infinity focus - manual focus													
3505MH0007120041203805C00	3805	4488	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	n/a	1608	1198	n/a	n/a	

REMS UV sensor

mhl00095	standard viewing position	intended standoff: ~15 cm											
	3505MH0000950011203807C00	3807	13259	16.7	14.8	-0.7	0.8	65.8	2.7	1608	1198	10.6	7.9

Sol 3508 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)			
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)				
target named Kukui															
mhl00781	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3508MH0007810011203811C00	3811	13011	26.9	25.0	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	1608	1198	16.3	12.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3508MH0001710001203905R00				range map product:						3508MH0001710001203906S00	
mhl00798	intermediate-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3508MH0007980011203822C00	3822	13579	10.7	8.8	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.4		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3508MH0001710001203903R00				range map product:						3508MH0001710001203904S00	
mhl00798	intermediate-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3508MH0007980011203833C00	3833	13583	10.7	8.8	-0.3	0.3	44.5	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.3		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3508MH0001710001203901R00				range map product:						3508MH0001710001203902S00	
target named Salto_Angel															
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3508MH0007060011203844C00	3844	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
mhl00852	intermediate-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3508MH0008520011203847C00	3847	13596	10.5	8.6	-0.3	0.3	43.9	1.1	1608	1198	7.1	5.3		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3508MH0001710001203899R00				range map product:						3508MH0001710001203900S00	
mhl00852	intermediate-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3508MH0008520011203858C00	3858	13601	10.5	8.6	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	1608	1198	7.0	5.2		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3508MH0001710001203897R00				range map product:						3508MH0001710001203898S00	
target named Opadai															
mhl00706	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3508MH0007060011203869C00	3869	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6		
mhl00851	intermediate-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3508MH0008510011203872C00	3872	13572	10.8	8.9	-0.3	0.3	45.0	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.4		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3508MH0001710001203895R00				range map product:						3508MH0001710001203896S00	
mhl00851	intermediate-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 10 cm												
	3508MH0008510011203883C00	3883	13571	10.8	8.9	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.4		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3508MH0001710001203893R00				range map product:						3508MH0001710001203894S00	

Sol 3511 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)		

intended drill target named Avanavero - before DRT													
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3511MH0001900011203908C00	3908	13022	26.2	24.3	-1.7	2.0	99.2	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9
mhli00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3511MH0001220011203910C00	3910	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7

intended drill target named Avanavero - after DRT															
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm													
	3511MH0001900011203912C00	3912	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9		
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3511MH0001820011203914C00	3914	14013	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3511MH0001530001203961R00				range map product:						3511MH0001530001203962S00	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3511MH0001820011203924C00	3924	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3511MH0001530001203959R00				range map product:						3511MH0001530001203960S00	
mhli00796	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm													
	APXS raster spot 2														
	3511MH0007960011203934C00	3934	15137	2.8	0.9	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	1608	1198	2.7	2.0		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3511MH0001530001203957R00				range map product:						3511MH0001530001203958S00	
mhli00182	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm													
	APXS raster spot 1														
	3511MH0001820011203944C00	3944	14004	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7		
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3511MH0001530001203955R00				range map product:						3511MH0001530001203956S00	

intended drill target named Avanavero - after drill bit pre-load test													
mhli00465	context view	intended standoff - 35 cm											
	3511MH0004650011203954C00	3954	12898	36.2	34.3	-3.2	3.9	134.2	12.4	1608	1198	21.6	16.1

last update: 24_June_2022

Sol 3512 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information*

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

intended sample discard site for planned *Avanavero* drill sample

context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
mhi00190	3512MH0001900011203964C00	3964	13017	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0

last update: 11_July_2022

Sol 3528 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Avanavero drill hole

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3528MH0001970011203966C00	3966	13035	25.5	23.6	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	1608	1198	15.5	11.6
mhli00774	intermediate-resolution view	intended standoff - 10 cm											
	3528MH0007740011203968C00	3968	13583	10.7	8.8	-0.3	0.3	44.5	1.2	1608	1198	7.2	5.3

Avanavero drill hole cuttings

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	near (cm)	far (cm)	Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)
mhli00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3528MH0001220011203970C00	3970	14164	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.3

last update: 12_July_2022

Sol 3530 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

Avanavero drill hole cuttings

mhli00122	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3530MH0001220011203972C00	3972	13937	7.3	5.4	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.2	3.9

target named La_Laja

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3530MH0001900011203974C00	3974	13026	26.0	24.1	-1.7	1.9	98.4	6.4	1608	1198	15.8	11.8
mhli00306	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3530MH0003060011203976C00	3976	14113	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3530MH0002650001203997R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3530MH0002650001203998S00					
mhli00306	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	3530MH0003060011203986C00	3986	14109	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3530MH0002650001203995R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3530MH0002650001203996S00					

last update: 13_July_2022

Sol 3531 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Uai_Uai													
mhl00190	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm										
	3531MH0001900011204000C00	4000	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3531MH0001680011204002C00	4002	14020	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.5	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3531MH0001930001204035R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3531MH0001930001204036S00				
mhl00168	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm										
	3531MH0001680011204012C00	4012	14018	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3531MH0001930001204033R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3531MH0001930001204034S00				
mhl00743	high resolution view		intended standoff - 1 cm										
	3531MH0007430011204022C00	4022	15190	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0
	<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3531MH0001930001204031R00				<i>range map product:</i> 3531MH0001930001204032S00				

Sol 3532 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named *Seringa* - after DRT

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm														
	3532MH0007060011204038C00	4038	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0			
mhl00834	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm														
	3532MH0008340011204041C00	4041	13999	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3533MH0001700001204148R00				range map product:					3533MH0001700001204149S00		
mhl00834	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm														
	3532MH0008340011204052C00	4052	14002	6.8	4.9	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7			
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3533MH0001700001204146R00				range map product:					3533MH0001700001204147S00		
mhl00813	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm														
	3532MH0008130011204063C00	4063	14688	3.8	1.9	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.4			
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3533MH0001700001204144R00				range map product:					3533MH0001700001204145S00		

target named *La_Manare*

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm														
	3532MH0007060011204074C00	4074	13006	27.2	25.3	-1.9	2.1	102.7	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3			
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm														
	3532MH0007230011204077C00	4077	13896	7.6	5.7	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	1608	1198	5.4	4.0			
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3533MH0001700001204142R00				range map product:					3533MH0001700001204143S00		
mhl00723	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm														
	3532MH0007230011204088C00	4088	13912	7.5	5.6	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.3	4.0			
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3533MH0001700001204140R00				range map product:					3533MH0001700001204141S00		
mhl00800	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm														
	3532MH0008000011204099C00	4099	14459	4.6	2.7	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	1608	1198	3.7	2.8			
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3533MH0001700001204138R00				range map product:					3533MH0001700001204139S00		

target named *Caruai*

mhl00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm														
	3532MH0007060011204110C00	4110	13041	25.1	23.2	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	1608	1198	15.3	11.4			
mhl00709	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm														
	3532MH0007090011204113C00	4113	14255	5.4	3.5	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1			
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3533MH0001700001204136R00				range map product:					3533MH0001700001204137S00		
mhl00709	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm														
	3532MH0007090011204124C00	4124	14244	5.5	3.6	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	1608	1198	4.2	3.1			
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3533MH0001700001204134R00				range map product:					3533MH0001700001204135S00		

last update: 19_July_2022

Sol 3534 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horizontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Monte_Caburai

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3534MH0001900011204151C00	4151	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3534MH0002990011204153C00	4153	13982	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204275R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204276S00	
mhl00299	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3534MH0002990011204163C00	4163	13978	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204273R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204274S00	
mhl00419	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm											
	APXS raster spot 2												
	3534MH0004190011204173C00	4173	15026	3.0	1.1	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	1608	1198	2.8	2.1
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204271R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204272S00	
mhl00299	medium-resolution view	intended standoff - 5 cm											
	APXS raster spot 1												
	3534MH0002990011204183C00	4183	13992	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204269R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204270S00	

target named Ilha_Novo_Destino - a 2 x 3 mosaic

mhl00853	position 1 of 6	intended standoff - 30 cm											
	3534MH0008530011204193C00	4193	12927	33.3	31.4	-2.7	3.2	124.0	10.5	1608	1198	19.9	14.9
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204267R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204268S00	
mhl00853	position 2 of 6	intended standoff - 30 cm											
	3534MH0008530011204203C00	4203	13087	22.8	20.9	-1.3	1.5	87.2	4.9	1608	1198	14.0	10.4
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204265R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204266S00	
mhl00853	position 3 of 6	intended standoff - 30 cm											
	3534MH0008530011204213C00	4213	13151	20.1	18.2	-1.1	1.1	77.8	3.8	1608	1198	12.5	9.3
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204263R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204264S00	
mhl00853	position 4 of 6	intended standoff - 30 cm											
	3534MH0008530011204223C00	4223	13171	19.4	17.5	-1.0	1.0	75.3	3.6	1608	1198	12.1	9.0
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204261R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204262S00	
mhl00853	position 5 of 6	intended standoff - 30 cm											
	3534MH0008530011204233C00	4233	13039	25.2	23.3	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	1608	1198	15.4	11.5
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204259R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204260S00	
mhl00853	position 6 of 6	intended standoff - 30 cm											
	3534MH0008530011204243C00	4243	13005	27.3	25.4	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	1608	1198	16.5	12.3
corresponding focus merge products:		best focus product:		3536MH0003690001204257R00				range map product:				3536MH0003690001204258S00	

last update: 18_July_2022

Sol 3535 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - deep imaging to check cleanliness state of mesh, funnel, funnel throat

intended working distance to mesh is 12.4 cm; to funnel throat is 16.3 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm

mhl00312	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 1 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus	intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm											
	3535MH0003120001204252C00	4252	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at mesh												
	manual focus	intended distance to mesh: 12.4 cm											
	3535MH0003120011204253C00	4253	13458	12.5	10.6	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.5	1024	1024	5.2	5.2
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 2 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus	intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm											
	3535MH0003260001204254C00	4254	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6
mhl00326	image focused at funnel throat (~4 cm below mesh) - position 3 of 3 to inspect funnel throat												
	manual focus	intended distance to funnel throat: 16.3 cm											
	3535MH0003260001204255C00	4255	13272	16.4	14.5	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	1024	1024	6.6	6.6

CheMin sample inlet - at night with its cover open - overview of entire inlet

intended working distance to inlet is ~19 cm - for scale, note that mesh diameter is 3.5 cm

mhl00228	manual focus												
	intended distance: ~19 cm												
	3535MH0002280001204256C00	4256	13182	19.1	17.2	-0.9	1.0	74.0	3.4	1608	1198	11.9	8.9

last update: 19_July_2022

Sol 3537 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Cerro_Raya														
mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3537MH0001900011204278C00	4278	13033	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6	
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3537MH0001820011204280C00	4280	14192	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	1608	1198	4.4	3.2	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3537MH0002650001204301R00				range map product:							3537MH0002650001204302S00
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3537MH0001820011204290C00	4290	14194	5.7	3.8	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	1608	1198	4.3	3.2	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:	3537MH0002650001204299R00				range map product:							3537MH0002650001204300S00

last update: 25_July_2022

Sol 3539 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Surama

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3539MH0001900011204304C00	4304	13009	27.0	25.1	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	1608	1198	16.4	12.2	
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3539MH0003060011204306C00	4306	13980	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3540MH0001530001204354R00				range map product:						3540MH0001530001204355S00
mhl00306	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3539MH0003060011204316C00	4316	13982	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.1	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3540MH0001530001204352R00				range map product:						3540MH0001530001204353S00

target named Amajari

mhl00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3539MH0001900011204326C00	4326	13024	26.1	24.2	-1.7	1.9	98.8	6.4	1608	1198	15.9	11.8	
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3539MH0001820011204328C00	4328	14106	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3540MH0001530001204350R00				range map product:						3540MH0001530001204351S00
mhl00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3539MH0001820011204338C00	4338	14114	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:		3540MH0001530001204348R00				range map product:						3540MH0001530001204349S00

inspect right middle rover wheel/surface interface

mhl00261	right (starboard) middle wheel												
	manual focus	intended distance to wheel-surface interface: ~274 cm											
	3539MH0002610011204347E01	4347	12582	~334	~332	~-1.6 m	~-4.9 m	~1200	n/a	1608	1198	~193	~144

last update: 26_July_2022

Sol 3541 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Benhori_Bumoko

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3541MH0001900011204357C00	4357	13014	26.7	24.8	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	1608	1198	16.2	12.1	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3541MH0001820011204359C00	4359	13984	7.0	5.1	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.8	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3543MH0001630001204432R00				range map product:					3543MH0001630001204433S00
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3541MH0001820011204369C00	4369	13987	6.9	5.0	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	1608	1198	5.0	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3543MH0001630001204430R00				range map product:					3543MH0001630001204431S00
mhli00302	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3541MH0003020011204379C00	4379	14642	4.0	2.1	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	1608	1198	3.3	2.5	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3543MH0001630001204428R00				range map product:					3543MH0001630001204429S00

target named Serra_da_Mocidade

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm											
	3541MH0001900011204389C00	4389	13032	25.6	23.7	-1.7	1.9	97.1	6.2	1608	1198	15.6	11.6

target named Motocuruna- after DRT

mhli00190	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3541MH0001900011204391C00	4391	13019	26.4	24.5	-1.8	2.0	99.8	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3541MH0001820011204393C00	4393	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3543MH0001630001204426R00				range map product:					3543MH0001630001204427S00
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3541MH0001820011204403C00	4403	14017	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.7	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3543MH0001630001204424R00				range map product:					3543MH0001630001204425S00
mhli00302	high resolution view	intended standoff - 2 cm												
	3541MH0003020011204413C00	4413	14733	3.7	1.8	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.2	1608	1198	3.2	2.4	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3543MH0001630001204422R00				range map product:					3543MH0001630001204423S00

last update: 26_July_2022

Sol 3544 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Tumereng															
mhli00628	context view		intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3544MH0006280011204435C00	4435	13018	26.5	24.6	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	1608	1198	16.1	12.0		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3544MH0001930001204468R00				<i>range map product:</i>						3544MH0001930001204469S00	
mhli00673	medium-resolution stereo-1		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3544MH0006730011204445C00	4445	14104	6.2	4.3	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.6	3.4		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3544MH0001930001204466R00				<i>range map product:</i>						3544MH0001930001204467S00	
mhli00673	medium-resolution stereo-2		intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3544MH0006730011204455C00	4455	14301	5.2	3.3	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	1608	1198	4.1	3.0		
<i>corresponding focus merge products:</i>		<i>best focus product:</i>		3544MH0001930001204464R00				<i>range map product:</i>						3544MH0001930001204465S00	

Sol 3546 - MAHLI Image Range & Scale Information *

***Note that other images might have been acquired; this table does not describe all images; it describes each camera positioning.**
 Working distance is a photography term; it is the range from the MAHLI front lens element (sapphire window) to the target.
 Standoff distance is measured from the plane defined by the tips of the MAHLI contact sensor probes to the target.
 Range, Scale, and DOF are computed from Motor Count using the equations from version 2 of Edgett et al. (2015, <https://doi.org/10.13140/RG.2.1.3798.5447>).

Sequence	Image ID*	MSL:CAMERA_PRODUC_T_ID (CDPID)	Motor Count	Range or Working Distance from motor mount (cm)	Standoff (MAHLI Toolframe +X) from motor count (cm)	Depth of Field estimate		Pixel Scale (µm/pixel)	Pixel Scale uncertainty (± µm/pixel)	Illuminated Pixels on CCD (approximate)		Image Dimensions (cm) (approximate)	
						near (cm)	far (cm)			horiz-ontal	vertical	horizontal (CCD columns)	vertical (CCD rows)

target named Simoni

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3546MH0007060011204471C00	4471	13030	25.8	23.9	-1.7	1.9	97.6	6.3	1608	1198	15.7	11.7	
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3546MH0002240011204474C00	4474	14153	5.9	4.0	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3547MH0002270001204534R00				range map product:					3547MH0002270001204535S00
mhli00224	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3546MH0002240011204484C00	4484	14148	6.0	4.1	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	1608	1198	4.5	3.3	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3547MH0002270001204532R00				range map product:					3547MH0002270001204533S00

target named Lilas - after DRT

mhli00706	context view	intended standoff - 25 cm												
	3546MH0007060011204494C00	4494	13020	26.3	24.4	-1.7	2.0	99.6	6.5	1608	1198	16.0	11.9	
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-1	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3546MH0001820011204497C00	4497	14025	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.4	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3547MH0002270001204530R00				range map product:					3547MH0002270001204531S00
mhli00182	medium-resolution stereo-2	intended standoff - 5 cm												
	3546MH0001820011204507C00	4507	14030	6.7	4.8	-0.2	0.1	30.3	0.5	1608	1198	4.9	3.6	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3547MH0002270001204528R00				range map product:					3547MH0002270001204529S00
mhli00426	high resolution view	intended standoff - 1 cm												
	3546MH0004260011204517C00	4517	15184	2.7	0.8	0.0	0.1	16.3	0.2	1608	1198	2.6	2.0	
	corresponding focus merge products:	best focus product:			3547MH0002270001204526R00				range map product:					3547MH0002270001204527S00

5 Focus merge product information

5.1 Purpose and description

The MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* provide information about the best focus and range map products created by focus merges performed onboard the MAHLI instrument.

The information includes:

1. thumbnail images representing the appearance of each best focus and range map product;
2. a brief title or description of the image target and purpose;
3. the Sol and date (UTC) that the merged parent images were acquired;
4. the Sol on which the focus merge took place,
5. image IDs for the focus merge products and a corresponding full-frame image;
6. the MAHLI command sequence that acquired the parent images and the command sequence that created the focus merge products;
7. the commanded stack depth; that is, the number of parent images acquired in a given focus stack;
8. the type of focus stack (relative or absolute; see definitions in **Section 7**);
9. a list of the thumbnail image IDs for the parent images acquired in the focus stack (because, in some cases, these are the only versions of the focus stack images that are received on Earth);
10. the focus position (stepper motor count) for each parent image in the focus stack;
11. the range and range uncertainty determined from the focus position (motor count) of each parent image; and
12. the grayscale DN value corresponding to each parent image motor count and range in the focus merge range map product.

Further, for each parent image, the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* state whether any of the full-size images (Individual Focus Stack Images) were received on Earth, listing:

13. the image ID of the full-size parent or child image, if received on Earth;
14. the date on which the full-size image was received (applicable only to *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* for the period between Sol 0 and 946 after that, with the exception of Sol 930, this practice was abandoned as unnecessary);

15. the compression quality of the best version of the image, if received on Earth (this practice was later abandoned as unnecessary); and
16. a statement regarding the fate of parent images not received on Earth; that is, the Sol on which the parent was deleted from the data storage inside the instrument’s digital electronics assembly (DEA).

Each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is identified by the Sol on which the parent images were acquired. The onboard merge, in some cases, might have been performed on a later sol.

The parent images identified in rows that are colored orange, if they have a corresponding DN value in a yellow-colored column, are those that participated in the creation of the focus merge product. In other words, those that are in white rows (for which there is a corresponding DN in the yellow column) had no in-focus elements and thus were not incorporated into the merged product, even if they had been commanded to be merged. Which images were commanded to be merged can be determined by the yellow-colored column that indicates the corresponding DN values in the range map image product; for cases in which the commanded focus stack depth is > 8 , the corresponding DN values (yellow-colored column) will indicate the 8 commanded to be merged (the instrument cannot merge > 8 but it can acquire > 8 images in a focus stack).

In cases in which the focus stack parent images were returned to Earth, the data user has the option to perform a new focus merge using software approaches available on Earth, now or in the future, which might outperform the MAHLI onboard algorithm. The user also has the opportunity, in these cases, to improve each parent image before performing the merge (e.g., remove blemishes, perform flat field correction, etc.).

When a > 8 image focus stack has been acquired, the orange-colored rows can *also* indicate recommendations for images that would contain in-focus elements and could be added to a future focus merge product, whether performed onboard MAHLI or on Earth after receipt of the full-size images. Those images that are recommended, but were not merged onboard, have no “Corresponding DN in Range Map” in the yellow, rightmost columns of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*.

For the Sol 3424–3547 period, focus stacks that were merged onboard the instrument were acquired on **Sols 3425, 3428, 3432, 3436, 3439, 3442, 3444, 3447, 3449, 3451, 3453, 3456, 3458, 3459, 3462, 3465, 3466, 3469, 3471, 3473, 3476, 3478, 3480, 3483, 3485, 3488, 3491, 3493, 3503, 3505, 3508, 3511, 3530, 3531, 3532, 3534, 3537, 3539, 3541, 3544, 3546**. Unless otherwise stated, the onboard focus merges performed during this period were all of the “basic” type (see Edgett *et al.* 2012; Edgett *et al.* 2015).

5.2 Formulae

5.2.1 Range

When acquiring a focus stack, the MAHLI camera head is held in a fixed position. This means that the working distance (d_w) — and corresponding standoff distance (d_s) — is constant (see **Section 5.2.5**). However, each image acquired in a focus stack is done so at a different focus

position; that is, a different stepper motor count position (m_{open} or m_{closed} ; usually m_{open}). That motor count is related to the range (r_{fm}) between the front lens element of the camera and the in-focus elements of the image by the same empirical formula (**Equation 1**) as applied to determine working distance from motor count. In centimeters,

$$r_{fm} = (am_{open}^{-1} + b + cm_{open} + dm_{open}^2 + em_{open}^3)^{-1}, \quad (12)$$

in which $a = 0.576786$, $b = -11.8479$, $c = 2.80153 \times 10^{-3}$, $d = -2.266488 \times 10^{-7}$, and $e = 6.26666 \times 10^{-12}$.

For each parent image in a given focus stack, this range is given in the green-colored column on the right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

5.2.2 Range uncertainty estimate

The uncertainty ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) in the computed range (r_{fm}) is estimated using depth of field as related to the corresponding range (via motor count; **Equation 12**) for each merged parent image. The range uncertainty estimate is noted in the light green column on the lower right side of each MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*.

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Estimated Range Uncertainty”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created before Sol 942, our estimate of range uncertainty was based on the older (Edgett *et al.* 2013) depth of field equations described in **Section 4.2.3, Equations 4, 5, and 6**, in which we substituted r_{fm} for d_w .

Focus Merge Product Information Sheets in which the relevant column is labeled “Depth of Field”

For MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* created starting with Sol 942, we used the refined knowledge of MAHLI depth of field, described by Edgett *et al.* (2015) and in **Equation 7** of **Section 4.2.3** to determine d_{far} and d_{near} for each focus stack parent image motor count. The resulting range uncertainty estimate ($\pm r_{uncertainty}$, in centimeters) reported in the light green column on the lower right side of the corresponding *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet* is estimated by the average of the absolute values of d_{far} and d_{near} :

$$\pm r_{uncertainty} = ((-d_{near}) + d_{far})/2. \quad (13)$$

Alternatively, particularly after Sol 1000, the depth of field is reported in the form of both the near and far (d_{far} and d_{near}) depths of field, per **Equation 7**.

5.2.3 Corresponding DN in range map product

Focus merge range map products created onboard MAHLI are returned as grayscale JPEG compressed images. The pixel values (DN) range from 0 to 255. These are assigned by the onboard software on the basis of commanded focus stack depth. The table below, from Edgett *et al.* (2015), shows the relationship between each image commanded to be focus merged and its corresponding grayscale DN value in a MAHLI range map product. In other words, if the instrument is commanded to merge eight images, DN values are assigned according to the

second column in the table; if commanded to merge only four images, the corresponding DN values are those in the sixth column. Thus, each DN in a range map product can be related to a motor count position and a corresponding range via linear interpolation between these values.

Relation between commanded image participant in an onboard MAHLI focus merge and range map grayscale data value (DN)							
image commanded to be merged	DN for 8-image merge	DN for 7-image merge	DN for 6-image merge	DN for 5-image merge	DN for 4-image merge	DN for 3-image merge	DN for 2-image merge
1st	255	255	255	255	255	255	255
2nd	223	218	212	204	191	170	127
3rd	191	182	170	153	127	84	—
4th	159	145	127	102	63	—	—
5th	127	109	84	51	—	—	—
6th	95	72	42	—	—	—	—
7th	63	36	—	—	—	—	—
8th	31	—	—	—	—	—	—

5.2.4 Determination of which parent images participated in a given focus merge product (orange rows)

Focus merge parent images in the orange-colored rows on each of the *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* are an indicator of the images that were actually merged. A merge of up to 8 images might be commanded, but perhaps only 3, 4, or 5 of them actually exhibit in-focus elements the get incorporated into the best focus image product.

As discussed by Edgett *et al.* (2015), the parent images that were actually merged, relative to the number commanded to be merged (indicated by the number of yellow-colored rows regarding the corresponding DN in the range map products on the right side of each *Focus Merge Product Information Sheet*), are determined by the range of grayscale DN, between 0 and 255, in the focus merge range map product. For example, if the DN range of this product is 71 to 138, then only four of 8 images commanded to be merged participated in that merge, per the DN values corresponding to an 8-image focus merge, per the table above.

5.2.5 Camera working distance and standoff distance

For a given focus stack, the distance between the MAHLI camera head and an imaged target can be determined from a corresponding image acquired via autofocus (assuming the autofocus effort found focus). In other words, while the range between the camera and the in-focus elements of a parent image are captured by the individual parent images in the focus stack (**Section 5.2.1**), the camera acquired the stack from a fixed working distance. On the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the corresponding autofocused image, and its stepper motor count focus position, are stated on the left side of the sheet, beneath the thumbnail images, in rows and columns colored light blue.

For some *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets*, the working distance (d_w) and standoff distance (d_s) are provided in these blue rows and columns. These were computed from the

motor count position using the same formulae for d_w and d_s described in **Section 4.2 (Equations 1 and 3, respectively)**. Where these values are not given, the data user can apply **Equations 1 and 3** to the motor count, or use the corresponding full-frame image ID to identify the working distance and standoff distance using the *Range and Scale Information Sheets* for that Sol. We began to regularly provide a result for d_w and d_s starting with Sol 694; before that, the cases in which these values are not given are a reflection of the evolution of the production and content of the MAHLI *Focus Merge Product Information Sheets* over time.

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Sol 3425 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3425MH0001730011201635C00				
best focus image:	3427MH0001630001201712R00	1712	motor count:		14008	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3427MH0001630001201713S00	1713	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3425	focus merged on sol:		3427	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3425MH0001730021201636C00	1636	13888	7.64	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3425MH0001730021201637C00	1637	13918	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3425MH0001730021201638C00	1638	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3425MH0001730021201639C00	1639	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3425MH0001730021201640C00	1640	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3425MH0001730021201641C00	1641	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3425MH0001730021201642C00	1642	14068	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3425MH0001730021201643C00	1643	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3425 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3425MH0001730011201645C00				
best focus image:	3427MH0001630001201710R00	1710	motor count:		14009	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3427MH0001630001201711S00	1711	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3425	focus merged on sol:		3427	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3425MH0001730021201646C00	1646	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3425MH0001730021201647C00	1647	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3425MH0001730021201648C00	1648	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3425MH0001730021201649C00	1649	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3425MH0001730021201650C00	1650	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	127	5
3425MH0001730021201651C00	1651	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3425MH0001730021201652C00	1652	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3425MH0001730021201653C00	1653	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3425 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Burn_Mouth - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3425MH0008380011201661C00			
best focus image:	3427MH0001630001201708R00		1708	motor count:		15132	range (cm):	2.8	
range map product:	3427MH0001630001201709S00		1709	acquired sequence:		mhli00838	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3425	focus merged on sol:		3427	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3425MH0008380021201662C00	1662	14868	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	255	1
3425MH0008380021201663C00	1663	14934	3.18	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	223	2
3425MH0008380021201664C00	1664	15000	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	191	3
3425MH0008380021201665C00	1665	15066	2.90	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	159	4
3425MH0008380021201666C00	1666	15132	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	127	5
3425MH0008380021201667C00	1667	15198	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	95	6
3425MH0008380021201668C00	1668	15264	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7
3425MH0008380021201669C00	1669	15330	2.43	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3425 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Donkey_Trail - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3425MH0001680011201673C00			
best focus image:	3427MH0001630001201706R00		1706	motor count:		14047	range (cm):	6.5	
range map product:	3427MH0001630001201707S00		1707	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3425	focus merged on sol:		3427	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3425MH0001680021201674C00	1674	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
3425MH0001680021201675C00	1675	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3425MH0001680021201676C00	1676	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
3425MH0001680021201677C00	1677	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
3425MH0001680021201678C00	1678	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
3425MH0001680021201679C00	1679	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3425MH0001680021201680C00	1680	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3425MH0001680021201681C00	1681	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3425 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Donkey_Trail - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3425MH0001680011201683C00				
best focus image:	3427MH0001630001201704R00	1704	motor count:		14047	range (cm):		6.5	
range map product:	3427MH0001630001201705S00	1705	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3425	focus merged on sol:		3427	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3425MH0001680021201684C00	1684	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	255	1
3425MH0001680021201685C00	1685	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3425MH0001680021201686C00	1686	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
3425MH0001680021201687C00	1687	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	159	4
3425MH0001680021201688C00	1688	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	127	5
3425MH0001680021201689C00	1689	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3425MH0001680021201690C00	1690	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3425MH0001680021201691C00	1691	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3425 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Donkey_Trail - after DRT - ~7 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3425MH0007430011201693C00				
best focus image:	3427MH0001630001201702R00	1702	motor count:		15236	range (cm):		2.6	
range map product:	3427MH0001630001201703S00	1703	acquired sequence:		mhli00743	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3425	focus merged on sol:		3427	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3425MH0007430021201694C00	1694	15092	2.85	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	255	1
3425MH0007430021201695C00	1695	15128	2.78	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	223	2
3425MH0007430021201696C00	1696	15164	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	191	3
3425MH0007430021201697C00	1697	15200	2.65	-0.1	0.1	16.2	0.2	159	4
3425MH0007430021201698C00	1698	15236	2.58	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	127	5
3425MH0007430021201699C00	1699	15272	2.52	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	95	6
3425MH0007430021201700C00	1700	15308	2.46	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	63	7
3425MH0007430021201701C00	1701	15344	2.41	0.0	0.1	15.4	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Venlaw - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0002990011201717C00			
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201860R00		1860	motor count:		13988	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201861S00		1861	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0002990021201718C00	1718	13844	7.99	-0.2	0.2	35.0	0.7	255	1
3428MH0002990021201719C00	1719	13880	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3428MH0002990021201720C00	1720	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	191	3
3428MH0002990021201721C00	1721	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	159	4
3428MH0002990021201722C00	1722	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3428MH0002990021201723C00	1723	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3428MH0002990021201724C00	1724	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3428MH0002990021201725C00	1725	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Venlaw - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0002990011201727C00			
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201858R00		1858	motor count:		13993	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201859S00		1859	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0002990021201728C00	1728	13849	7.95	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3428MH0002990021201729C00	1729	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3428MH0002990021201730C00	1730	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3428MH0002990021201731C00	1731	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3428MH0002990021201732C00	1732	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3428MH0002990021201733C00	1733	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3428MH0002990021201734C00	1734	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3428MH0002990021201735C00	1735	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Venlaw - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003020011201737C00				
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201856R00	1856	motor count:		14651	range (cm):		3.9	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201857S00	1857	acquired sequence:		mhli00302		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22	merge sequence:		mhli00458		merge type: Basic			
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003020021201738C00	1738	14531	4.31	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	255	1
3428MH0003020021201739C00	1739	14561	4.21	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	223	2
3428MH0003020021201740C00	1740	14591	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3
3428MH0003020021201741C00	1741	14621	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	159	4
3428MH0003020021201742C00	1742	14651	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	127	5
3428MH0003020021201743C00	1743	14681	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	95	6
3428MH0003020021201744C00	1744	14711	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	63	7
3428MH0003020021201745C00	1745	14741	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Venlaw - after DRT - mosaic position 1 of 6 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003420011201747C00				
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201854R00	1854	motor count:		13555	range (cm):		11.1	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201855S00	1855	acquired sequence:		mhli00342		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22	merge sequence:		mhli00458		merge type: Basic			
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003420021201748C00	1748	13459	12.50	-0.4	0.4	50.9	1.5	255	1
3428MH0003420021201749C00	1749	13483	12.11	-0.4	0.4	49.5	1.5	223	2
3428MH0003420021201750C00	1750	13507	11.74	-0.4	0.4	48.2	1.4	191	3
3428MH0003420021201751C00	1751	13531	11.39	-0.4	0.4	47.0	1.3	159	4
3428MH0003420021201752C00	1752	13555	11.06	-0.4	0.4	45.8	1.2	127	5
3428MH0003420021201753C00	1753	13579	10.74	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	95	6
3428MH0003420021201754C00	1754	13603	10.43	-0.3	0.3	43.6	1.1	63	7
3428MH0003420021201755C00	1755	13627	10.14	-0.3	0.3	42.6	1.1	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Venlaw - after DRT - mosaic position 2 of 6 - ~9 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003420011201757C00				
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201852R00	1852	motor count:		13560	range (cm):		11.0	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201853S00	1853	acquired sequence:		mhli00342	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22	merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003420021201758C00	1758	13464	12.42	-0.4	0.4	50.6	1.5	255	1
3428MH0003420021201759C00	1759	13488	12.03	-0.4	0.4	49.3	1.4	223	2
3428MH0003420021201760C00	1760	13512	11.67	-0.4	0.4	48.0	1.4	191	3
3428MH0003420021201761C00	1761	13536	11.32	-0.4	0.4	46.8	1.3	159	4
3428MH0003420021201762C00	1762	13560	10.99	-0.4	0.3	45.6	1.2	127	5
3428MH0003420021201763C00	1763	13584	10.67	-0.3	0.3	44.5	1.1	95	6
3428MH0003420021201764C00	1764	13608	10.37	-0.3	0.3	43.4	1.1	63	7
3428MH0003420021201765C00	1765	13632	10.08	-0.3	0.3	42.4	1.0	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Venlaw - mosaic position 3 of 6 - ~9 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003420011201767C00				
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201850R00	1850	motor count:		13580	range (cm):		10.7	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201851S00	1851	acquired sequence:		mhli00342	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22	merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003420021201768C00	1768	13484	12.10	-0.4	0.4	49.5	1.4	255	1
3428MH0003420021201769C00	1769	13508	11.73	-0.4	0.4	48.2	1.4	223	2
3428MH0003420021201770C00	1770	13532	11.38	-0.4	0.4	47.0	1.3	191	3
3428MH0003420021201771C00	1771	13556	11.04	-0.4	0.3	45.8	1.2	159	4
3428MH0003420021201772C00	1772	13580	10.73	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	127	5
3428MH0003420021201773C00	1773	13604	10.42	-0.3	0.3	43.6	1.1	95	6
3428MH0003420021201774C00	1774	13628	10.13	-0.3	0.3	42.6	1.1	63	7
3428MH0003420021201775C00	1775	13652	9.85	-0.3	0.3	41.6	1.0	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Venlaw - mosaic position 4 of 6 - ~85 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003420011201777C00				
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201848R00	1848	motor count:		13602	range (cm):		10.4	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201849S00	1849	acquired sequence:		mhli00342	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003420021201778C00	1778	13506	11.76	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	255	1
3428MH0003420021201779C00	1779	13530	11.41	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	223	2
3428MH0003420021201780C00	1780	13554	11.07	-0.4	0.4	45.9	1.2	191	3
3428MH0003420021201781C00	1781	13578	10.75	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	159	4
3428MH0003420021201782C00	1782	13602	10.45	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	127	5
3428MH0003420021201783C00	1783	13626	10.15	-0.3	0.3	42.6	1.1	95	6
3428MH0003420021201784C00	1784	13650	9.88	-0.3	0.3	41.7	1.0	63	7
3428MH0003420021201785C00	1785	13674	9.61	-0.3	0.3	40.7	1.0	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Venlaw - mosaic position 5 of 6 - ~7 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003420011201787C00				
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201846R00	1846	motor count:		13730	range (cm):		9.0	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201847S00	1847	acquired sequence:		mhli00342	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003420021201788C00	1788	13634	10.06	-0.3	0.3	42.3	1.0	255	1
3428MH0003420021201789C00	1789	13658	9.78	-0.3	0.3	41.3	1.0	223	2
3428MH0003420021201790C00	1790	13682	9.52	-0.3	0.3	40.4	0.9	191	3
3428MH0003420021201791C00	1791	13706	9.27	-0.3	0.3	39.5	0.9	159	4
3428MH0003420021201792C00	1792	13730	9.02	-0.3	0.2	38.7	0.9	127	5
3428MH0003420021201793C00	1793	13754	8.79	-0.2	0.2	37.8	0.8	95	6
3428MH0003420021201794C00	1794	13778	8.57	-0.2	0.2	37.1	0.8	63	7
3428MH0003420021201795C00	1795	13802	8.35	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Venlaw - mosaic position 6 of 6 - ~55 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003420011201797C00				
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201844R00	1844	motor count:		13878	range (cm):		7.7	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201845S00	1845	acquired sequence:		mhli00342	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003420021201798C00	1798	13782	8.53	-0.2	0.2	36.9	0.8	255	1
3428MH0003420021201799C00	1799	13806	8.32	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2
3428MH0003420021201800C00	1800	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	191	3
3428MH0003420021201801C00	1801	13854	7.91	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	159	4
3428MH0003420021201802C00	1802	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	127	5
3428MH0003420021201803C00	1803	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	95	6
3428MH0003420021201804C00	1804	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	63	7
3428MH0003420021201805C00	1805	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Broadfell - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003080011201809C00				
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201842R00	1842	motor count:		13943	range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201843S00	1843	acquired sequence:		mhli00308	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003080021201810C00	1810	13679	9.55	-0.3	0.3	40.5	1.0	255	1
3428MH0003080021201811C00	1811	13745	8.88	-0.3	0.2	38.1	0.8	223	2
3428MH0003080021201812C00	1812	13811	8.27	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	191	3
3428MH0003080021201813C00	1813	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	159	4
3428MH0003080021201814C00	1814	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	127	5
3428MH0003080021201815C00	1815	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3428MH0003080021201816C00	1816	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3428MH0003080021201817C00	1817	14141	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Broadfell - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0003080011201819C00			
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201840R00		1840	motor count:		13962	range (cm):	7.1	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201841S00		1841	acquired sequence:		mhli00308	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0003080021201820C00	1820	13698	9.35	-0.3	0.3	39.8	0.9	255	1
3428MH0003080021201821C00	1821	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	223	2
3428MH0003080021201822C00	1822	13830	8.11	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	191	3
3428MH0003080021201823C00	1823	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	159	4
3428MH0003080021201824C00	1824	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3428MH0003080021201825C00	1825	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3428MH0003080021201826C00	1826	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3428MH0003080021201827C00	1827	14160	5.90	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3428 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Broadfell - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3428MH0007160011201829C00			
best focus image:	3429MH0004580001201838R00		1838	motor count:		14955	range (cm):	3.1	
range map product:	3429MH0004580001201839S00		1839	acquired sequence:		mhli00716	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Mar-22			merge sequence:		mhli00458	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3428	focus merged on sol:		3429	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3428MH0007160021201830C00	1830	14715	3.74	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	255	1
3428MH0007160021201831C00	1831	14775	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	223	2
3428MH0007160021201832C00	1832	14835	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	191	3
3428MH0007160021201833C00	1833	14895	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	159	4
3428MH0007160021201834C00	1834	14955	3.14	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	127	5
3428MH0007160021201835C00	1835	15015	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	95	6
3428MH0007160021201836C00	1836	15075	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	63	7
3428MH0007160021201837C00	1837	15135	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	31	8

updated: 07_February_2023

Sol 3432 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3432MH0007080011201866C00				
best focus image:	3433MH0002270001201943R00	1943	motor count:		13963	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3433MH0002270001201944S00	1944	acquired sequence:		mhli00708	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3432	focus merged on sol:		3433	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3432MH0007080031201868C00	1868	13723	9.09	-0.3	0.2	38.9	0.9	255	1
3432MH0007080031201869C00	1869	13783	8.52	-0.2	0.2	36.9	0.8	223	2
3432MH0007080031201870C00	1870	13843	8.00	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	191	3
3432MH0007080031201871C00	1871	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	159	4
3432MH0007080031201872C00	1872	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3432MH0007080031201873C00	1873	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3432MH0007080031201874C00	1874	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3432MH0007080031201875C00	1875	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 07_February_2023

Sol 3432 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3432MH0007080011201877C00				
best focus image:	3433MH0002270001201941R00	1941	motor count:		13921	range (cm):		7.4	
range map product:	3433MH0002270001201942S00	1942	acquired sequence:		mhli00708	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3432	focus merged on sol:		3433	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3432MH0007080031201879C00	1879	13681	9.53	-0.3	0.3	40.5	1.0	255	1
3432MH0007080031201880C00	1880	13741	8.92	-0.3	0.2	38.3	0.9	223	2
3432MH0007080031201881C00	1881	13801	8.36	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	191	3
3432MH0007080031201882C00	1882	13861	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	159	4
3432MH0007080031201883C00	1883	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	127	5
3432MH0007080031201884C00	1884	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6
3432MH0007080031201885C00	1885	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3432MH0007080031201886C00	1886	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3432 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Blue_Anchor - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3432MH0007950011201894C00				
best focus image:	3433MH0002270001201939R00	1939	motor count:		14616	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3433MH0002270001201940S00	1940	acquired sequence:		mhli00795	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3432	focus merged on sol:		3433	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3432MH0007950031201896C00	1896	14280	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	255	1
3432MH0007950031201897C00	1897	14364	4.94	-0.1	0.1	24.3	0.4	223	2
3432MH0007950031201898C00	1898	14448	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	191	3
3432MH0007950031201899C00	1899	14532	4.31	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	159	4
3432MH0007950031201900C00	1900	14616	4.04	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	127	5
3432MH0007950031201901C00	1901	14700	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	95	6
3432MH0007950031201902C00	1902	14784	3.55	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3432MH0007950031201903C00	1903	14868	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3432 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3432MH0008030011201908C00				
best focus image:	3433MH0002270001201937R00	1937	motor count:		14185	range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:	3433MH0002270001201938S00	1938	acquired sequence:		mhli00803	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3432	focus merged on sol:		3433	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3432MH0008030031201910C00	1910	13849	7.95	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3432MH0008030031201911C00	1911	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3432MH0008030031201912C00	1912	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
3432MH0008030031201913C00	1913	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	159	4
3432MH0008030031201914C00	1914	14185	5.77	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	127	5
3432MH0008030031201915C00	1915	14269	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	95	6
3432MH0008030031201916C00	1916	14353	4.99	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	63	7
3432MH0008030031201917C00	1917	14437	4.65	-0.1	0.1	23.3	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3432 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3432MH0008030011201919C00				
best focus image:	3433MH0002270001201935R00	1935	motor count:		14173	range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:	3433MH0002270001201936S00	1936	acquired sequence:		mhli00803	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3432	focus merged on sol:		3433	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3432MH0008030031201921C00	1921	13837	8.05	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
3432MH0008030031201922C00	1922	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3432MH0008030031201923C00	1923	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3432MH0008030031201924C00	1924	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	159	4
3432MH0008030031201925C00	1925	14173	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	127	5
3432MH0008030031201926C00	1926	14257	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	95	6
3432MH0008030031201927C00	1927	14341	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	63	7
3432MH0008030031201928C00	1928	14425	4.70	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3436 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Broo - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3436MH0001680011201948C00				
best focus image:	3436MH0001930001201981R00	1981	motor count:		14039	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3436MH0001930001201982S00	1982	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3436	focus merged on sol:		3436	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3436MH0001680021201949C00	1949	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
3436MH0001680021201950C00	1950	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
3436MH0001680021201951C00	1951	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3436MH0001680021201952C00	1952	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
3436MH0001680021201953C00	1953	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3436MH0001680021201954C00	1954	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3436MH0001680021201955C00	1955	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3436MH0001680021201956C00	1956	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3436 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Broo - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3436MH0001680011201958C00				
best focus image:	3436MH0001930001201979R00	1979	motor count:		14042	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3436MH0001930001201980S00	1980	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3436	focus merged on sol:		3436	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3436MH0001680021201959C00	1959	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3436MH0001680021201960C00	1960	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	223	2
3436MH0001680021201961C00	1961	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3436MH0001680021201962C00	1962	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3436MH0001680021201963C00	1963	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	127	5
3436MH0001680021201964C00	1964	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3436MH0001680021201965C00	1965	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3436MH0001680021201966C00	1966	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3436 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Broo - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3436MH0003020011201968C00			
best focus image:	3436MH0001930001201977R00		1977	motor count:		14764	range (cm):	3.6	
range map product:	3436MH0001930001201978S00		1978	acquired sequence:		mhli00302	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	6-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3436	focus merged on sol:		3436	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3436MH0003020021201969C00	1969	14644	3.95	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	255	1
3436MH0003020021201970C00	1970	14674	3.86	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	223	2
3436MH0003020021201971C00	1971	14704	3.77	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	191	3
3436MH0003020021201972C00	1972	14734	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	159	4
3436MH0003020021201973C00	1973	14764	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	127	5
3436MH0003020021201974C00	1974	14794	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	95	6
3436MH0003020021201975C00	1975	14824	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	63	7
3436MH0003020021201976C00	1976	14854	3.37	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0007230011201987C00				
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202099R00	2099	motor count:		13994	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202100S00	2100	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0007230031201989C00	1989	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3439MH0007230031201990C00	1990	13886	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3439MH0007230031201991C00	1991	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3439MH0007230031201992C00	1992	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3439MH0007230031201993C00	1993	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3439MH0007230031201994C00	1994	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3439MH0007230031201995C00	1995	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3439MH0007230031201996C00	1996	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0007230011201998C00				
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202097R00	2097	motor count:		14003	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202098S00	2098	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0007230031202000C00	2000	13859	7.87	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1
3439MH0007230031202001C00	2001	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	223	2
3439MH0007230031202002C00	2002	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3439MH0007230031202003C00	2003	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3439MH0007230031202004C00	2004	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3439MH0007230031202005C00	2005	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3439MH0007230031202006C00	2006	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3439MH0007230031202007C00	2007	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Lodberrie - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0007460011202009C00			
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202095R00		2095	motor count:		14687	range (cm):	3.8	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202096S00		2096	acquired sequence:		mhli00746	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0007460031202011C00	2011	14495	4.44	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	255	1
3439MH0007460031202012C00	2012	14543	4.27	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	223	2
3439MH0007460031202013C00	2013	14591	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3
3439MH0007460031202014C00	2014	14639	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	159	4
3439MH0007460031202015C00	2015	14687	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	127	5
3439MH0007460031202016C00	2016	14735	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	95	6
3439MH0007460031202017C00	2017	14783	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3439MH0007460031202018C00	2018	14831	3.43	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0001520011202022C00			
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202093R00		2093	motor count:		13977	range (cm):	7.0	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202094S00		2094	acquired sequence:		mhli00152	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0001520021202023C00	2023	13785	8.50	-0.2	0.2	36.8	0.8	255	1
3439MH0001520021202024C00	2024	13833	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	223	2
3439MH0001520021202025C00	2025	13881	7.70	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	191	3
3439MH0001520021202026C00	2026	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	159	4
3439MH0001520021202027C00	2027	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3439MH0001520021202028C00	2028	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3439MH0001520021202029C00	2029	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3439MH0001520021202030C00	2030	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sneuga - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0001520011202032C00				
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202091R00	2091	motor count:		13983	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202092S00	2092	acquired sequence:		mhli00152		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0001520021202033C00	2033	13791	8.45	-0.2	0.2	36.6	0.8	255	1
3439MH0001520021202034C00	2034	13839	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
3439MH0001520021202035C00	2035	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	191	3
3439MH0001520021202036C00	2036	13935	7.29	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	159	4
3439MH0001520021202037C00	2037	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
3439MH0001520021202038C00	2038	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3439MH0001520021202039C00	2039	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3439MH0001520021202040C00	2040	14127	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Sneuga - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0001760011202042C00				
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202089R00	2089	motor count:		14623	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202090S00	2090	acquired sequence:		mhli00176		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0001760021202043C00	2043	14431	4.68	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	255	1
3439MH0001760021202044C00	2044	14479	4.50	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	223	2
3439MH0001760021202045C00	2045	14527	4.33	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	191	3
3439MH0001760021202046C00	2046	14575	4.17	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	159	4
3439MH0001760021202047C00	2047	14623	4.01	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	127	5
3439MH0001760021202048C00	2048	14671	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	95	6
3439MH0001760021202049C00	2049	14719	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	63	7
3439MH0001760021202050C00	2050	14767	3.60	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0002990011202054C00				
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202087R00	2087	motor count:		14181	range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202088S00	2088	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0002990021202055C00	2055	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	255	1
3439MH0002990021202056C00	2056	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	223	2
3439MH0002990021202057C00	2057	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	191	3
3439MH0002990021202058C00	2058	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
3439MH0002990021202059C00	2059	14181	5.79	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
3439MH0002990021202060C00	2060	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
3439MH0002990021202061C00	2061	14253	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7
3439MH0002990021202062C00	2062	14289	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0002990011202064C00				
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202085R00	2085	motor count:		14063	range (cm):		6.4	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202086S00	2086	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0002990021202065C00	2065	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3439MH0002990021202066C00	2066	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3439MH0002990021202067C00	2067	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3439MH0002990021202068C00	2068	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	159	4
3439MH0002990021202069C00	2069	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	127	5
3439MH0002990021202070C00	2070	14099	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	95	6
3439MH0002990021202071C00	2071	14135	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	63	7
3439MH0002990021202072C00	2072	14171	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3439 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Inchnobny- mosaic position 3 of 3 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3439MH0002990011202074C00				
best focus image:	3440MH0005360001202083R00	2083	motor count:		14012	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3440MH0005360001202084S00	2084	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	9-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3439	focus merged on sol:		3440	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3439MH0002990021202075C00	2075	13868	7.80	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	255	1
3439MH0002990021202076C00	2076	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3439MH0002990021202077C00	2077	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3439MH0002990021202078C00	2078	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3439MH0002990021202079C00	2079	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3439MH0002990021202080C00	2080	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3439MH0002990021202081C00	2081	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3439MH0002990021202082C00	2082	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Brackenberry - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0001680011202108C00				
best focus image:	3442MH0005360001202219R00	2219	motor count:		13967	range (cm):	7.1		
range map product:	3442MH0005360001202220S00	2220	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	12-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3442	focus merged on sol:		3442	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0001680021202109C00	2109	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3442MH0001680021202110C00	2110	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
3442MH0001680021202111C00	2111	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3442MH0001680021202112C00	2112	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	159	4
3442MH0001680021202113C00	2113	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	127	5
3442MH0001680021202114C00	2114	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3442MH0001680021202115C00	2115	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	63	7
3442MH0001680021202116C00	2116	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Brackenberry - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0001680011202118C00				
best focus image:	3442MH0005360001202217R00	2217	motor count:		13974	range (cm):	7.0		
range map product:	3442MH0005360001202218S00	2218	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	12-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3442	focus merged on sol:		3442	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0001680021202119C00	2119	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3442MH0001680021202120C00	2120	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3442MH0001680021202121C00	2121	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3442MH0001680021202122C00	2122	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3442MH0001680021202123C00	2123	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
3442MH0001680021202124C00	2124	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
3442MH0001680021202125C00	2125	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	63	7
3442MH0001680021202126C00	2126	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Brackenberry - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0003020011202128C00			
best focus image:	3442MH0005360001202215R00		2215	motor count:		14600	range (cm):	4.1	
range map product:	3442MH0005360001202216S00		2216	acquired sequence:		mhli00302	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3442	focus merged on sol:		3442	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0003020021202129C00	2129	14480	4.49	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	255	1
3442MH0003020021202130C00	2130	14510	4.39	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	223	2
3442MH0003020021202131C00	2131	14540	4.28	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	191	3
3442MH0003020021202132C00	2132	14570	4.18	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	159	4
3442MH0003020021202133C00	2133	14600	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	127	5
3442MH0003020021202134C00	2134	14630	3.99	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	95	6
3442MH0003020021202135C00	2135	14660	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	63	7
3442MH0003020021202136C00	2136	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Skidbladner - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0001730011202142C00			
best focus image:	3442MH0005360001202213R00		2213	motor count:		13961	range (cm):	7.1	
range map product:	3442MH0005360001202214S00		2214	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3442	focus merged on sol:		3442	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0001730021202143C00	2143	13841	8.02	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	255	1
3442MH0001730021202144C00	2144	13871	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
3442MH0001730021202145C00	2145	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
3442MH0001730021202146C00	2146	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	159	4
3442MH0001730021202147C00	2147	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	127	5
3442MH0001730021202148C00	2148	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	95	6
3442MH0001730021202149C00	2149	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
3442MH0001730021202150C00	2150	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Skidbladner - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0001730011202152C00				
best focus image:	3442MH0005360001202211R00	2211	motor count:		13956	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3442MH0005360001202212S00	2212	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3442	focus merged on sol:		3442	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0001730021202153C00	2153	13836	8.06	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	255	1
3442MH0001730021202154C00	2154	13866	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	223	2
3442MH0001730021202155C00	2155	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	191	3
3442MH0001730021202156C00	2156	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4
3442MH0001730021202157C00	2157	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	127	5
3442MH0001730021202158C00	2158	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3442MH0001730021202159C00	2159	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	63	7
3442MH0001730021202160C00	2160	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Skidbladner - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0001840011202162C00				
best focus image:	3442MH0005360001202209R00	2209	motor count:		14607	range (cm):		4.1	
range map product:	3442MH0005360001202210S00	2210	acquired sequence:		mhli00184	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3442	focus merged on sol:		3442	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0001840021202163C00	2163	14463	4.56	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	255	1
3442MH0001840021202164C00	2164	14499	4.43	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	223	2
3442MH0001840021202165C00	2165	14535	4.30	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	191	3
3442MH0001840021202166C00	2166	14571	4.18	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	159	4
3442MH0001840021202167C00	2167	14607	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	127	5
3442MH0001840021202168C00	2168	14643	3.95	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	95	6
3442MH0001840021202169C00	2169	14679	3.84	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	63	7
3442MH0001840021202170C00	2170	14715	3.74	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Up_Helly_Aa - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0002240011202174C00				
best focus image:	3442MH0005360001202207R00	2207	motor count:		13988	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3442MH0005360001202208S00	2208	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3442	focus merged on sol:		3442	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0002240021202175C00	2175	13820	8.19	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	255	1
3442MH0002240021202176C00	2176	13862	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3442MH0002240021202177C00	2177	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
3442MH0002240021202178C00	2178	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3442MH0002240021202179C00	2179	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3442MH0002240021202180C00	2180	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3442MH0002240021202181C00	2181	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3442MH0002240021202182C00	2182	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Up_Helly_Aa - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0002240011202184C00				
best focus image:	3442MH0005360001202205R00	2205	motor count:		13988	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3442MH0005360001202206S00	2206	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3442	focus merged on sol:		3442	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0002240021202185C00	2185	13820	8.19	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	255	1
3442MH0002240021202186C00	2186	13862	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	223	2
3442MH0002240021202187C00	2187	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	191	3
3442MH0002240021202188C00	2188	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3442MH0002240021202189C00	2189	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3442MH0002240021202190C00	2190	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3442MH0002240021202191C00	2191	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3442MH0002240021202192C00	2192	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Up_Helly_Aa - ~2 cm standoff							
best focus image:		3442MH0005360001202203R00		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3442MH0001760011202194C00		
range map product:		3442MH0005360001202204S00		2203	motor count:		14652	range (cm):	3.9
acquired on date:		12-Apr-22		2204	acquired sequence:		mhli00176	stack type:	Relative
motor count interval:		48		merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
acquired on sol:		3442		focus merged on sol:		3442			
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3442MH0001760021202195C00	2195	14460	4.57	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	255	1
3442MH0001760021202196C00	2196	14508	4.39	-0.1	0.1	22.4	0.3	223	2
3442MH0001760021202197C00	2197	14556	4.23	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	191	3
3442MH0001760021202198C00	2198	14604	4.07	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4
3442MH0001760021202199C00	2199	14652	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	127	5
3442MH0001760021202200C00	2200	14700	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	95	6
3442MH0001760021202201C00	2201	14748	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	63	7
3442MH0001760021202202C00	2202	14796	3.52	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3444 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dun - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3444MH0003060011202224C00				
best focus image:	3444MH0001930001202257R00	2257	motor count:		13968	range (cm):		7.1	
range map product:	3444MH0001930001202258S00	2258	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3444	focus merged on sol:		3444	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3444MH0003060021202225C00	2225	13752	8.81	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	255	1
3444MH0003060021202226C00	2226	13806	8.32	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2
3444MH0003060021202227C00	2227	13860	7.86	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	191	3
3444MH0003060021202228C00	2228	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	159	4
3444MH0003060021202229C00	2229	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3444MH0003060021202230C00	2230	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3444MH0003060021202231C00	2231	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3444MH0003060021202232C00	2232	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3444 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Dun - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3444MH0003060011202234C00				
best focus image:	3444MH0001930001202255R00	2255	motor count:		13977	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3444MH0001930001202256S00	2256	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3444	focus merged on sol:		3444	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3444MH0003060021202235C00	2235	13761	8.72	-0.2	0.2	37.6	0.8	255	1
3444MH0003060021202236C00	2236	13815	8.24	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	223	2
3444MH0003060021202237C00	2237	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	191	3
3444MH0003060021202238C00	2238	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	159	4
3444MH0003060021202239C00	2239	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3444MH0003060021202240C00	2240	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3444MH0003060021202241C00	2241	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3444MH0003060021202242C00	2242	14139	6.01	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3444 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Dun - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3444MH0003110011202244C00				
best focus image:	3444MH0001930001202253R00	2253	motor count:		14610	range (cm):		4.1	
range map product:	3444MH0001930001202254S00	2254	acquired sequence:		mhli00311	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3444	focus merged on sol:		3444	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3444MH0003110021202245C00	2245	14346	5.02	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	255	1
3444MH0003110021202246C00	2246	14412	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	223	2
3444MH0003110021202247C00	2247	14478	4.50	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	191	3
3444MH0003110021202248C00	2248	14544	4.27	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	159	4
3444MH0003110021202249C00	2249	14610	4.05	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	127	5
3444MH0003110021202250C00	2250	14676	3.85	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	95	6
3444MH0003110021202251C00	2251	14742	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	63	7
3444MH0003110021202252C00	2252	14808	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	31	8

updated: 07_February_2023

Sol 3447 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3447MH0002970011202262C00				
best focus image:	3447MH0008170001202314R00	2314	motor count:		14151	range (cm):		5.9	
range map product:	3447MH0008170001202315S00	2315	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00817	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3447	focus merged on sol:		3447	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3447MH0002970021202263C00	2263	13911	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3447MH0002970021202264C00	2264	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	223	2
3447MH0002970021202265C00	2265	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3
3447MH0002970021202266C00	2266	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	159	4
3447MH0002970021202267C00	2267	14151	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	127	5
3447MH0002970021202268C00	2268	14211	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	95	6
3447MH0002970021202269C00	2269	14271	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
3447MH0002970021202270C00	2270	14331	5.08	-0.1	0.1	24.8	0.4	31	8

updated: 07_February_2023

Sol 3447 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3447MH0002970011202272C00				
best focus image:	3447MH0008170001202312R00	2312	motor count:		14117	range (cm):		6.1	
range map product:	3447MH0008170001202313S00	2313	acquired sequence:		mhli00297	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00817	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3447	focus merged on sol:		3447	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3447MH0002970021202273C00	2273	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	255	1
3447MH0002970021202274C00	2274	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3447MH0002970021202275C00	2275	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
3447MH0002970021202276C00	2276	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	159	4
3447MH0002970021202277C00	2277	14117	6.13	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	127	5
3447MH0002970021202278C00	2278	14177	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	95	6
3447MH0002970021202279C00	2279	14237	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	63	7
3447MH0002970021202280C00	2280	14297	5.23	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	31	8

updated: 07_February_2023

Sol 3447 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3447MH0007400011202285C00				
best focus image:	3447MH0008170001202310R00	2310	motor count:		14281	range (cm):		5.3	
range map product:	3447MH0008170001202311S00	2311	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00817	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3447	focus merged on sol:		3447	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3447MH0007400031202287C00	2287	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	255	1
3447MH0007400031202288C00	2288	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	223	2
3447MH0007400031202289C00	2289	14173	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	191	3
3447MH0007400031202290C00	2290	14227	5.56	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	159	4
3447MH0007400031202291C00	2291	14281	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	127	5
3447MH0007400031202292C00	2292	14335	5.07	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	95	6
3447MH0007400031202293C00	2293	14389	4.84	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	63	7
3447MH0007400031202294C00	2294	14443	4.63	-0.1	0.1	23.2	0.3	31	8

updated: 07_February_2023

Sol 3447 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3447MH0007400011202296C00				
best focus image:	3447MH0008170001202308R00	2308	motor count:		14287	range (cm):		5.3	
range map product:	3447MH0008170001202309S00	2309	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00817	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3447	focus merged on sol:		3447	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3447MH0007400031202298C00	2298	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	255	1
3447MH0007400031202299C00	2299	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	223	2
3447MH0007400031202300C00	2300	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	191	3
3447MH0007400031202301C00	2301	14233	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	159	4
3447MH0007400031202302C00	2302	14287	5.28	-0.1	0.1	25.5	0.4	127	5
3447MH0007400031202303C00	2303	14341	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	95	6
3447MH0007400031202304C00	2304	14395	4.82	-0.1	0.1	23.9	0.4	63	7
3447MH0007400031202305C00	2305	14449	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3449 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Runn - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3449MH0002240011202319C00			
best focus image:	3449MH0002650001202342R00			2342	motor count:		14027	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3449MH0002650001202343S00			2343	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Apr-22					merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic
motor count interval:		42		acquired on sol:		3449		focus merged on sol:		3449
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3449MH0002240021202320C00	2320	13859	7.87	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	255	1	
3449MH0002240021202321C00	2321	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2	
3449MH0002240021202322C00	2322	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3	
3449MH0002240021202323C00	2323	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4	
3449MH0002240021202324C00	2324	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5	
3449MH0002240021202325C00	2325	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	95	6	
3449MH0002240021202326C00	2326	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7	
3449MH0002240021202327C00	2327	14153	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8	

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3449 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Runn - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3449MH0002240011202329C00			
best focus image:	3449MH0002650001202340R00			2340	motor count:		14030	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3449MH0002650001202341S00			2341	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Apr-22					merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic
motor count interval:		42		acquired on sol:		3449		focus merged on sol:		3449
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3449MH0002240021202330C00	2330	13862	7.85	-0.2	0.2	34.5	0.7	255	1	
3449MH0002240021202331C00	2331	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2	
3449MH0002240021202332C00	2332	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3	
3449MH0002240021202333C00	2333	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4	
3449MH0002240021202334C00	2334	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5	
3449MH0002240021202335C00	2335	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6	
3449MH0002240021202336C00	2336	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7	
3449MH0002240021202337C00	2337	14156	5.92	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.5	31	8	

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff									
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3451MH0008430011202348C00					
best focus image:	3451MH0001700001202455R00	2455	motor count:		14221	range (cm):		5.6		
range map product:	3451MH0001700001202456S00	2456	acquired sequence:		mhli00843		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170		merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3451	focus merged on sol:		3451		
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3451MH0008430031202350C00	2350	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	255	1	
3451MH0008430031202351C00	2351	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	223	2	
3451MH0008430031202352C00	2352	14137	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	191	3	
3451MH0008430031202353C00	2353	14179	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	159	4	
3451MH0008430031202354C00	2354	14221	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	127	5	
3451MH0008430031202355C00	2355	14263	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	95	6	
3451MH0008430031202356C00	2356	14305	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	63	7	
3451MH0008430031202357C00	2357	14347	5.01	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	31	8	

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff									
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3451MH0008430011202359C00					
best focus image:	3451MH0001700001202453R00	2453	motor count:		14212	range (cm):		5.6		
range map product:	3451MH0001700001202454S00	2454	acquired sequence:		mhli00843		stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170		merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3451	focus merged on sol:		3451		
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3451MH0008430031202361C00	2361	14044	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	255	1	
3451MH0008430031202362C00	2362	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	223	2	
3451MH0008430031202363C00	2363	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	191	3	
3451MH0008430031202364C00	2364	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	159	4	
3451MH0008430031202365C00	2365	14212	5.63	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	127	5	
3451MH0008430031202366C00	2366	14254	5.43	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	95	6	
3451MH0008430031202367C00	2367	14296	5.24	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	63	7	
3451MH0008430031202368C00	2368	14338	5.05	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	31	8	

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Shandon - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3451MH0007630011202373C00				
best focus image:	3451MH0001700001202451R00	2451	motor count:		13989	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3451MH0001700001202452S00	2452	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3451	focus merged on sol:		3451	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3451MH0007630031202375C00	2375	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3451MH0007630031202376C00	2376	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3451MH0007630031202377C00	2377	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3451MH0007630031202378C00	2378	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3451MH0007630031202379C00	2379	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3451MH0007630031202380C00	2380	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3451MH0007630031202381C00	2381	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3451MH0007630031202382C00	2382	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Shandon - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3451MH0007630011202384C00				
best focus image:	3451MH0001700001202449R00	2449	motor count:		13988	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3451MH0001700001202450S00	2450	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3451	focus merged on sol:		3451	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3451MH0007630031202386C00	2386	13892	7.61	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3451MH0007630031202387C00	2387	13916	7.43	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3451MH0007630031202388C00	2388	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3451MH0007630031202389C00	2389	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3451MH0007630031202390C00	2390	13988	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3451MH0007630031202391C00	2391	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3451MH0007630031202392C00	2392	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3451MH0007630031202393C00	2393	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Shandon - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3451MH0008240011202395C00				
best focus image:	3451MH0001700001202447R00	2447	motor count:		14648	range (cm):		3.9	
range map product:	3451MH0001700001202448S00	2448	acquired sequence:		mhli00824	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3451	focus merged on sol:		3451	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3451MH0008240031202397C00	2397	14480	4.49	-0.1	0.1	22.7	0.3	255	1
3451MH0008240031202398C00	2398	14522	4.35	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	223	2
3451MH0008240031202399C00	2399	14564	4.20	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	191	3
3451MH0008240031202400C00	2400	14606	4.07	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4
3451MH0008240031202401C00	2401	14648	3.94	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
3451MH0008240031202402C00	2402	14690	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	95	6
3451MH0008240031202403C00	2403	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	63	7
3451MH0008240031202404C00	2404	14774	3.58	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nesting - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3451MH0006990011202409C00				
best focus image:	3451MH0001700001202445R00	2445	motor count:		14013	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3451MH0001700001202446S00	2446	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3451	focus merged on sol:		3451	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3451MH0006990031202411C00	2411	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3451MH0006990031202412C00	2412	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3451MH0006990031202413C00	2413	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3451MH0006990031202414C00	2414	13983	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3451MH0006990031202415C00	2415	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3451MH0006990031202416C00	2416	14043	6.57	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6
3451MH0006990031202417C00	2417	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3451MH0006990031202418C00	2418	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nesting - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3451MH0006990011202420C00				
best focus image:	3451MH0001700001202443R00	2443	motor count:		14004	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3451MH0001700001202444S00	2444	acquired sequence:		mhli00699	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3451	focus merged on sol:		3451	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3451MH0006990031202422C00	2422	13884	7.67	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
3451MH0006990031202423C00	2423	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
3451MH0006990031202424C00	2424	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3451MH0006990031202425C00	2425	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3451MH0006990031202426C00	2426	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3451MH0006990031202427C00	2427	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6
3451MH0006990031202428C00	2428	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3451MH0006990031202429C00	2429	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3451 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Nesting - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3451MH0008240011202431C00				
best focus image:	3451MH0001700001202441R00	2441	motor count:		14718	range (cm):		3.7	
range map product:	3451MH0001700001202442S00	2442	acquired sequence:		mhli00824	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3451	focus merged on sol:		3451	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3451MH0008240031202433C00	2433	14550	4.25	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1
3451MH0008240031202434C00	2434	14592	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	223	2
3451MH0008240031202435C00	2435	14634	3.98	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	191	3
3451MH0008240031202436C00	2436	14676	3.85	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	159	4
3451MH0008240031202437C00	2437	14718	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	127	5
3451MH0008240031202438C00	2438	14760	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	95	6
3451MH0008240031202439C00	2439	14802	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	63	7
3451MH0008240031202440C00	2440	14844	3.40	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3453 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Delting - after DRT - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3453MH0007630011202461C00				
best focus image:	3454MH0001630001202546R00	2546	motor count:		13998	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3454MH0001630001202547S00	2547	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3453	focus merged on sol:		3454	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3453MH0007630031202463C00	2463	13902	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3453MH0007630031202464C00	2464	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3453MH0007630031202465C00	2465	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3453MH0007630031202466C00	2466	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3453MH0007630031202467C00	2467	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3453MH0007630031202468C00	2468	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3453MH0007630031202469C00	2469	14046	6.55	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	63	7
3453MH0007630031202470C00	2470	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3453 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Delting - after DRT - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3453MH0007630011202472C00				
best focus image:	3454MH0001630001202544R00	2544	motor count:		13999	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3454MH0001630001202545S00	2545	acquired sequence:		mhli00763	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3453	focus merged on sol:		3454	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3453MH0007630031202474C00	2474	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3453MH0007630031202475C00	2475	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3453MH0007630031202476C00	2476	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3453MH0007630031202477C00	2477	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3453MH0007630031202478C00	2478	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3453MH0007630031202479C00	2479	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3453MH0007630031202480C00	2480	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3453MH0007630031202481C00	2481	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3453 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Delting - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3453MH0008130011202489C00			
best focus image:	3454MH0001630001202542R00	2542	motor count:		14691	range (cm):		3.8	
range map product:	3454MH0001630001202543S00	2543	acquired sequence:		mhli00813		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	24-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3453	focus merged on sol:		3454	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3453MH0008130031202491C00	2491	14571	4.18	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	255	1
3453MH0008130031202492C00	2492	14601	4.08	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	223	2
3453MH0008130031202493C00	2493	14631	3.99	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	191	3
3453MH0008130031202494C00	2494	14661	3.90	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	159	4
3453MH0008130031202495C00	2495	14691	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
3453MH0008130031202496C00	2496	14721	3.72	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
3453MH0008130031202497C00	2497	14751	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	63	7
3453MH0008130031202498C00	2498	14781	3.56	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3453 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3453MH0007090011202503C00			
best focus image:	3454MH0001630001202540R00	2540	motor count:		14026	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3454MH0001630001202541S00	2541	acquired sequence:		mhli00709		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	24-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3453	focus merged on sol:		3454	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3453MH0007090031202505C00	2505	13834	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	255	1
3453MH0007090031202506C00	2506	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3453MH0007090031202507C00	2507	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3453MH0007090031202508C00	2508	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3453MH0007090031202509C00	2509	14026	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3453MH0007090031202510C00	2510	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	95	6
3453MH0007090031202511C00	2511	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	63	7
3453MH0007090031202512C00	2512	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3453 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Rumbings - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3453MH0007090011202514C00				
best focus image:	3454MH0001630001202538R00	2538	motor count:		13994	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3454MH0001630001202539S00	2539	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3453	focus merged on sol:		3454	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3453MH0007090031202516C00	2516	13802	8.35	-0.2	0.2	36.3	0.8	255	1
3453MH0007090031202517C00	2517	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	223	2
3453MH0007090031202518C00	2518	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	191	3
3453MH0007090031202519C00	2519	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3453MH0007090031202520C00	2520	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3453MH0007090031202521C00	2521	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
3453MH0007090031202522C00	2522	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3453MH0007090031202523C00	2523	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3453 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Rumbings - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3453MH0007110011202525C00				
best focus image:	3454MH0001630001202536R00	2536	motor count:		14737	range (cm):		3.7	
range map product:	3454MH0001630001202537S00	2537	acquired sequence:		mhli00711	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	24-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3453	focus merged on sol:		3454	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3453MH0007110031202527C00	2527	14449	4.61	-0.1	0.1	23.1	0.3	255	1
3453MH0007110031202528C00	2528	14521	4.35	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	223	2
3453MH0007110031202529C00	2529	14593	4.11	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	191	3
3453MH0007110031202530C00	2530	14665	3.89	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	159	4
3453MH0007110031202531C00	2531	14737	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	127	5
3453MH0007110031202532C00	2532	14809	3.49	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	95	6
3453MH0007110031202533C00	2533	14881	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	63	7
3453MH0007110031202534C00	2534	14953	3.14	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3456 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3456MH0001820011202552C00			
best focus image:	3456MH0002650001202573R00		2573	motor count:		14062	range (cm):	6.5	
range map product:	3456MH0002650001202574S00		2574	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3456	focus merged on sol:		3456	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3456MH0001820021202553C00	2553	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1
3456MH0001820021202554C00	2554	13990	6.91	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3456MH0001820021202555C00	2555	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	191	3
3456MH0001820021202556C00	2556	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	159	4
3456MH0001820021202557C00	2557	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	127	5
3456MH0001820021202558C00	2558	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	95	6
3456MH0001820021202559C00	2559	14110	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3456MH0001820021202560C00	2560	14134	6.04	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3456 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3456MH0001820011202562C00			
best focus image:	3456MH0002650001202571R00		2571	motor count:		14064	range (cm):	6.4	
range map product:	3456MH0002650001202572S00		2572	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	27-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3456	focus merged on sol:		3456	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3456MH0001820021202563C00	2563	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	255	1
3456MH0001820021202564C00	2564	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3456MH0001820021202565C00	2565	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	191	3
3456MH0001820021202566C00	2566	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	159	4
3456MH0001820021202567C00	2567	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	127	5
3456MH0001820021202568C00	2568	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	95	6
3456MH0001820021202569C00	2569	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	63	7
3456MH0001820021202570C00	2570	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3458 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3458MH0001730011202579C00				
best focus image:	3458MH0002270001202639R00	2639	motor count:		14172	range (cm):	5.8		
range map product:	3458MH0002270001202640S00	2640	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	29-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3458	focus merged on sol:		3458	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3458MH0001730021202580C00	2580	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	255	1
3458MH0001730021202581C00	2581	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	223	2
3458MH0001730021202582C00	2582	14112	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	191	3
3458MH0001730021202583C00	2583	14142	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	159	4
3458MH0001730021202584C00	2584	14172	5.84	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	127	5
3458MH0001730021202585C00	2585	14202	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	95	6
3458MH0001730021202586C00	2586	14232	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	63	7
3458MH0001730021202587C00	2587	14262	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3458 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3458MH0001730011202589C00				
best focus image:	3458MH0002270001202637R00	2637	motor count:		14192	range (cm):	5.7		
range map product:	3458MH0002270001202638S00	2638	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	29-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3458	focus merged on sol:		3458	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3458MH0001730021202590C00	2590	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	255	1
3458MH0001730021202591C00	2591	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	223	2
3458MH0001730021202592C00	2592	14132	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	191	3
3458MH0001730021202593C00	2593	14162	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	159	4
3458MH0001730021202594C00	2594	14192	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	127	5
3458MH0001730021202595C00	2595	14222	5.58	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
3458MH0001730021202596C00	2596	14252	5.44	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	63	7
3458MH0001730021202597C00	2597	14282	5.30	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3458 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3458MH0001820011202602C00				
best focus image:	3458MH0002270001202635R00	2635	motor count:		13999	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3458MH0002270001202636S00	2636	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3458	focus merged on sol:		3458	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3458MH0001820021202603C00	2603	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3458MH0001820021202604C00	2604	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	223	2
3458MH0001820021202605C00	2605	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	191	3
3458MH0001820021202606C00	2606	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	159	4
3458MH0001820021202607C00	2607	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3458MH0001820021202608C00	2608	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3458MH0001820021202609C00	2609	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3458MH0001820021202610C00	2610	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3458 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3458MH0001820011202612C00				
best focus image:	3458MH0002270001202633R00	2633	motor count:		13994	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3458MH0002270001202634S00	2634	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Apr-22	merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3458	focus merged on sol:		3458	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3458MH0001820021202613C00	2613	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1
3458MH0001820021202614C00	2614	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3458MH0001820021202615C00	2615	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3458MH0001820021202616C00	2616	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3458MH0001820021202617C00	2617	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3458MH0001820021202618C00	2618	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3458MH0001820021202619C00	2619	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	63	7
3458MH0001820021202620C00	2620	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3458 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cow_Head - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3458MH0001760011202622C00				
best focus image:	3458MH0002270001202631R00	2631	motor count:		14692	range (cm):		3.8	
range map product:	3458MH0002270001202632S00	2632	acquired sequence:		mhli00176	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	29-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3458	focus merged on sol:		3458	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3458MH0001760021202623C00	2623	14500	4.42	-0.1	0.1	22.5	0.3	255	1
3458MH0001760021202624C00	2624	14548	4.26	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	223	2
3458MH0001760021202625C00	2625	14596	4.10	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	191	3
3458MH0001760021202626C00	2626	14644	3.95	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	159	4
3458MH0001760021202627C00	2627	14692	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
3458MH0001760021202628C00	2628	14740	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	95	6
3458MH0001760021202629C00	2629	14788	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3458MH0001760021202630C00	2630	14836	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3459 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Castle Craig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3459MH0007400011202645C00				
best focus image:	3461MH0002270001202714R00	2714	motor count:		13931	range (cm):		7.3	
range map product:	3461MH0002270001202715S00	2715	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3459	focus merged on sol:		3461	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3459MH0007400031202647C00	2647	13715	9.18	-0.3	0.3	39.2	0.9	255	1
3459MH0007400031202648C00	2648	13769	8.65	-0.2	0.2	37.3	0.8	223	2
3459MH0007400031202649C00	2649	13823	8.17	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	191	3
3459MH0007400031202650C00	2650	13877	7.73	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	159	4
3459MH0007400031202651C00	2651	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	127	5
3459MH0007400031202652C00	2652	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3459MH0007400031202653C00	2653	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3459MH0007400031202654C00	2654	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3459 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Castle Craig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3459MH0007400011202656C00				
best focus image:	3461MH0002270001202712R00	2712	motor count:		13924	range (cm):		7.4	
range map product:	3461MH0002270001202713S00	2713	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3459	focus merged on sol:		3461	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3459MH0007400031202658C00	2658	13708	9.25	-0.3	0.3	39.4	0.9	255	1
3459MH0007400031202659C00	2659	13762	8.72	-0.2	0.2	37.6	0.8	223	2
3459MH0007400031202660C00	2660	13816	8.23	-0.2	0.2	35.9	0.8	191	3
3459MH0007400031202661C00	2661	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	159	4
3459MH0007400031202662C00	2662	13924	7.37	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	127	5
3459MH0007400031202663C00	2663	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	95	6
3459MH0007400031202664C00	2664	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3459MH0007400031202665C00	2665	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3459 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target CastleCraig - ~35 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3459MH0008440011202673C00			
best focus image:	3461MH0002270001202710R00	2710	motor count:		14277	range (cm):		5.3	
range map product:	3461MH0002270001202711S00	2711	acquired sequence:		mhli00844	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3459	focus merged on sol:		3461	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3459MH0008440031202675C00	2675	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	255	1
3459MH0008440031202676C00	2676	14079	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	223	2
3459MH0008440031202677C00	2677	14145	5.98	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	191	3
3459MH0008440031202678C00	2678	14211	5.64	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	159	4
3459MH0008440031202679C00	2679	14277	5.32	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	127	5
3459MH0008440031202680C00	2680	14343	5.03	-0.1	0.1	24.6	0.4	95	6
3459MH0008440031202681C00	2681	14409	4.76	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	63	7
3459MH0008440031202682C00	2682	14475	4.51	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3459 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cat_Firth - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3459MH0001820011202687C00			
best focus image:	3461MH0002270001202708R00	2708	motor count:		13992	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3461MH0002270001202709S00	2709	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	30-Apr-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3459	focus merged on sol:		3461	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3459MH0001820021202688C00	2688	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3459MH0001820021202689C00	2689	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3459MH0001820021202690C00	2690	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3459MH0001820021202691C00	2691	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3459MH0001820021202692C00	2692	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3459MH0001820021202693C00	2693	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3459MH0001820021202694C00	2694	14040	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3459MH0001820021202695C00	2695	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3459 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cat_Firth - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff												
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3459MH0001820011202697C00								
best focus image:		3461MH0002270001202706R00		2706		motor count:		13994		range (cm):		6.9		
range map product:		3461MH0002270001202707S00		2707		acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type:		Relative		
acquired on date:		30-Apr-22				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:			24		acquired on sol:		3459		focus merged on sol:		3461			
Individual Focus Stack Images		CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8				
					near	far								
3459MH0001820021202698C00		2698	13898	7.56	-0.2	0.2	33.5	0.7	255	1				
3459MH0001820021202699C00		2699	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2				
3459MH0001820021202700C00		2700	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3				
3459MH0001820021202701C00		2701	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4				
3459MH0001820021202702C00		2702	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5				
3459MH0001820021202703C00		2703	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6				
3459MH0001820021202704C00		2704	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	63	7				
3459MH0001820021202705C00		2705	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	31	8				

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Sol 3462 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3462MH0002990011202719C00				
best focus image:	3462MH0002270001202778R00	2778	motor count:		14015	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3462MH0002270001202779S00	2779	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	3-May-22		merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3462	focus merged on sol:		3462	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3462MH0002990021202720C00	2720	13871	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
3462MH0002990021202721C00	2721	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3462MH0002990021202722C00	2722	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3462MH0002990021202723C00	2723	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3462MH0002990021202724C00	2724	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3462MH0002990021202725C00	2725	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3462MH0002990021202726C00	2726	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3462MH0002990021202727C00	2727	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3462 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3462MH0002990011202729C00				
best focus image:	3462MH0002270001202776R00	2776	motor count:		14029	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3462MH0002270001202777S00	2777	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	3-May-22		merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3462	focus merged on sol:		3462	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3462MH0002990021202730C00	2730	13885	7.66	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	255	1
3462MH0002990021202731C00	2731	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3462MH0002990021202732C00	2732	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3462MH0002990021202733C00	2733	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3462MH0002990021202734C00	2734	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3462MH0002990021202735C00	2735	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3462MH0002990021202736C00	2736	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	63	7
3462MH0002990021202737C00	2737	14137	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3462 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Gran_Sabana - ~2 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3462MH0003110011202739C00		
best focus image:	3462MH0002270001202774R00	2774		motor count:		14733	range (cm):	3.7	
range map product:	3462MH0002270001202775S00	2775		acquired sequence:		mhli00311	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	3-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3462	focus merged on sol:		3462	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3462MH0003110021202740C00	2740	14469	4.53	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	255	1
3462MH0003110021202741C00	2741	14535	4.30	-0.1	0.1	22.0	0.3	223	2
3462MH0003110021202742C00	2742	14601	4.08	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	191	3
3462MH0003110021202743C00	2743	14667	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.6	0.3	159	4
3462MH0003110021202744C00	2744	14733	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	127	5
3462MH0003110021202745C00	2745	14799	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	95	6
3462MH0003110021202746C00	2746	14865	3.35	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	63	7
3462MH0003110021202747C00	2747	14931	3.19	-0.1	0.1	18.1	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3462 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Berbice - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3462MH0003630011202751C00		
best focus image:	3462MH0002270001202772R00	2772		motor count:		13938	range (cm):	7.3	
range map product:	3462MH0002270001202773S00	2773		acquired sequence:		mhli00363	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	3-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3462	focus merged on sol:		3462	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3462MH0003630021202752C00	2752	13650	9.88	-0.3	0.3	41.7	1.0	255	1
3462MH0003630021202753C00	2753	13722	9.10	-0.3	0.2	38.9	0.9	223	2
3462MH0003630021202754C00	2754	13794	8.42	-0.2	0.2	36.5	0.8	191	3
3462MH0003630021202755C00	2755	13866	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	159	4
3462MH0003630021202756C00	2756	13938	7.27	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	127	5
3462MH0003630021202757C00	2757	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3462MH0003630021202758C00	2758	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3462MH0003630021202759C00	2759	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3462 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Berbice - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3462MH0003630011202761C00					
best focus image:		3462MH0002270001202770R00		2770		motor count:		13927		range (cm): 7.3	
range map product:		3462MH0002270001202771S00		2771		acquired sequence:		mhli00363		stack type: Relative	
acquired on date:		3-May-22				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		72		acquired on sol:		3462		focus merged on sol:		3462	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3462MH0003630021202762C00	2762	13639	10.00	-0.3	0.3	42.1	1.0	255	1		
3462MH0003630021202763C00	2763	13711	9.22	-0.3	0.3	39.3	0.9	223	2		
3462MH0003630021202764C00	2764	13783	8.52	-0.2	0.2	36.9	0.8	191	3		
3462MH0003630021202765C00	2765	13855	7.90	-0.2	0.2	34.7	0.7	159	4		
3462MH0003630021202766C00	2766	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	127	5		
3462MH0003630021202767C00	2767	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	95	6		
3462MH0003630021202768C00	2768	14071	6.40	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7		
3462MH0003630021202769C00	2769	14143	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	31	8		

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Sol 3465 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - ~20 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3465MH0008460011202781C00				
best focus image:	3465MH0001930001202816R00	2816	motor count:		13103	range (cm):		22.1	
range map product:	3465MH0001930001202817S00	2817	acquired sequence:		mhli00846	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3465	focus merged on sol:		3465	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3465MH0008460021202782C00	2782	12887	37.38	-3.4	4.2	138.5	13.3	255	1
3465MH0008460021202783C00	2783	12941	32.02	-2.5	3.0	119.6	9.7	223	2
3465MH0008460021202784C00	2784	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	191	3
3465MH0008460021202785C00	2785	13049	24.70	-1.6	1.7	93.8	5.8	159	4
3465MH0008460021202786C00	2786	13103	22.09	-1.3	1.4	84.6	4.6	127	5
3465MH0008460021202787C00	2787	13157	19.93	-1.0	1.1	77.0	3.8	95	6
3465MH0008460021202788C00	2788	13211	18.11	-0.9	0.9	70.7	3.1	63	7
3465MH0008460021202789C00	2789	13265	16.57	-0.7	0.8	65.2	2.6	31	8

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Sol 3465 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - ~24 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3465MH0008460011202791C00				
best focus image:	3465MH0001930001202814R00	2814	motor count:		13031	range (cm):		25.7	
range map product:	3465MH0001930001202815S00	2815	acquired sequence:		mhli00846	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	6-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3465	focus merged on sol:		3465	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3465MH0008460021202792C00	2792	12815	47.79	-5.4	7.1	175.1	22.0	255	1
3465MH0008460021202793C00	2793	12869	39.55	-3.8	4.7	146.1	14.9	223	2
3465MH0008460021202794C00	2794	12923	33.64	-2.8	3.3	125.3	10.7	191	3
3465MH0008460021202795C00	2795	12977	29.18	-2.1	2.4	109.6	8.0	159	4
3465MH0008460021202796C00	2796	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
3465MH0008460021202797C00	2797	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	95	6
3465MH0008460021202798C00	2798	13139	20.60	-1.1	1.2	79.4	4.0	63	7
3465MH0008460021202799C00	2799	13193	18.69	-0.9	1.0	72.7	3.3	31	8

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Sol 3465 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Bartica - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3465MH0002240011202803C00				
best focus image:	3465MH0001930001202812R00	2812	motor count:		14178	range (cm):		5.8	
range map product:	3465MH0001930001202813S00	2813	acquired sequence:		mhli00224		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	6-May-22		merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3465		focus merged on sol:		3465
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3465MH0002240021202804C00	2804	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	255	1
3465MH0002240021202805C00	2805	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	223	2
3465MH0002240021202806C00	2806	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	191	3
3465MH0002240021202807C00	2807	14136	6.03	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	159	4
3465MH0002240021202808C00	2808	14178	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	127	5
3465MH0002240021202809C00	2809	14220	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
3465MH0002240021202810C00	2810	14262	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
3465MH0002240021202811C00	2811	14304	5.20	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3466 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Bonfim - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3466MH0001730011202821C00				
best focus image:	3466MH0001630001202900R00	2900	motor count:		14029	range (cm):	6.7		
range map product:	3466MH0001630001202901S00	2901	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	7-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3466	focus merged on sol:		3466	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3466MH0001730021202822C00	2822	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3466MH0001730021202823C00	2823	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	223	2
3466MH0001730021202824C00	2824	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3466MH0001730021202825C00	2825	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3466MH0001730021202826C00	2826	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3466MH0001730021202827C00	2827	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3466MH0001730021202828C00	2828	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3466MH0001730021202829C00	2829	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3466 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Bonfim - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3466MH0001730011202831C00				
best focus image:	3466MH0001630001202898R00	2898	motor count:		14031	range (cm):	6.6		
range map product:	3466MH0001630001202899S00	2899	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	7-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3466	focus merged on sol:		3466	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3466MH0001730021202832C00	2832	13911	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3466MH0001730021202833C00	2833	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3466MH0001730021202834C00	2834	13971	7.04	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3466MH0001730021202835C00	2835	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3466MH0001730021202836C00	2836	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3466MH0001730021202837C00	2837	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3466MH0001730021202838C00	2838	14091	6.28	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3466MH0001730021202839C00	2839	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3466 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bonfim - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3466MH0001760011202841C00				
best focus image:	3466MH0001630001202896R00	2896	motor count:		14739	range (cm):		3.7	
range map product:	3466MH0001630001202897S00	2897	acquired sequence:		mhli00176	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-May-22	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3466	focus merged on sol:		3466	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3466MH0001760021202842C00	2842	14547	4.26	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1
3466MH0001760021202843C00	2843	14595	4.10	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	223	2
3466MH0001760021202844C00	2844	14643	3.95	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	191	3
3466MH0001760021202845C00	2845	14691	3.81	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	159	4
3466MH0001760021202846C00	2846	14739	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	127	5
3466MH0001760021202847C00	2847	14787	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	95	6
3466MH0001760021202848C00	2848	14835	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	63	7
3466MH0001760021202849C00	2849	14883	3.30	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3466 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Oshi - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3466MH0001820011202861C00				
best focus image:	3466MH0001630001202894R00	2894	motor count:		13993	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3466MH0001630001202895S00	2895	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-May-22	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3466	focus merged on sol:		3466	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3466MH0001820021202862C00	2862	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3466MH0001820021202863C00	2863	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	223	2
3466MH0001820021202864C00	2864	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	191	3
3466MH0001820021202865C00	2865	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	159	4
3466MH0001820021202866C00	2866	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3466MH0001820021202867C00	2867	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3466MH0001820021202868C00	2868	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3466MH0001820021202869C00	2869	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3466 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Oshi - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3466MH0001820011202871C00				
best focus image:	3466MH0001630001202892R00	2892	motor count:		13991	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3466MH0001630001202893S00	2893	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-May-22	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3466	focus merged on sol:		3466	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3466MH0001820021202872C00	2872	13895	7.59	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3466MH0001820021202873C00	2873	13919	7.41	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	223	2
3466MH0001820021202874C00	2874	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3466MH0001820021202875C00	2875	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3466MH0001820021202876C00	2876	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3466MH0001820021202877C00	2877	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3466MH0001820021202878C00	2878	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3466MH0001820021202879C00	2879	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3466 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Oshi - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3466MH0004260011202881C00				
best focus image:	3466MH0001630001202890R00	2890	motor count:		15070	range (cm):		2.9	
range map product:	3466MH0001630001202891S00	2891	acquired sequence:		mhli00426	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	7-May-22	merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3466	focus merged on sol:		3466	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3466MH0004260021202882C00	2882	14878	3.32	-0.1	0.1	18.6	0.2	255	1
3466MH0004260021202883C00	2883	14926	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2
3466MH0004260021202884C00	2884	14974	3.10	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	191	3
3466MH0004260021202885C00	2885	15022	2.99	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	159	4
3466MH0004260021202886C00	2886	15070	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	127	5
3466MH0004260021202887C00	2887	15118	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	95	6
3466MH0004260021202888C00	2888	15166	2.71	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
3466MH0004260021202889C00	2889	15214	2.62	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3469 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3469MH0002240011202905C00				
best focus image:	3469MH0001530001202952R00	2952	motor count:		14041	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3469MH0001530001202953S00	2953	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3469	focus merged on sol:		3469	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3469MH0002240021202906C00	2906	13873	7.76	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3469MH0002240021202907C00	2907	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3469MH0002240021202908C00	2908	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3469MH0002240021202909C00	2909	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3469MH0002240021202910C00	2910	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	127	5
3469MH0002240021202911C00	2911	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	95	6
3469MH0002240021202912C00	2912	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
3469MH0002240021202913C00	2913	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3469 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3469MH0002240011202915C00				
best focus image:	3469MH0001530001202950R00	2950	motor count:		14077	range (cm):		6.4	
range map product:	3469MH0001530001202951S00	2951	acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3469	focus merged on sol:		3469	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3469MH0002240021202916C00	2916	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3469MH0002240021202917C00	2917	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3469MH0002240021202918C00	2918	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	191	3
3469MH0002240021202919C00	2919	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	159	4
3469MH0002240021202920C00	2920	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	127	5
3469MH0002240021202921C00	2921	14119	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.5	0.5	95	6
3469MH0002240021202922C00	2922	14161	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
3469MH0002240021202923C00	2923	14203	5.68	-0.1	0.1	26.9	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3469 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Parima - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3469MH0001730011202927C00				
best focus image:	3469MH0001530001202948R00	2948	motor count:		14035	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3469MH0001530001202949S00	2949	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3469	focus merged on sol:		3469	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3469MH0001730021202928C00	2928	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	255	1
3469MH0001730021202929C00	2929	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3469MH0001730021202930C00	2930	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3469MH0001730021202931C00	2931	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3469MH0001730021202932C00	2932	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3469MH0001730021202933C00	2933	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3469MH0001730021202934C00	2934	14095	6.26	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	63	7
3469MH0001730021202935C00	2935	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3469 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Parima - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3469MH0001730011202937C00				
best focus image:	3469MH0001530001202946R00	2946	motor count:		14034	range (cm):		6.6	
range map product:	3469MH0001530001202947S00	2947	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	10-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3469	focus merged on sol:		3469	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3469MH0001730021202938C00	2938	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	255	1
3469MH0001730021202939C00	2939	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3469MH0001730021202940C00	2940	13974	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3469MH0001730021202941C00	2941	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3469MH0001730021202942C00	2942	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	127	5
3469MH0001730021202943C00	2943	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	95	6
3469MH0001730021202944C00	2944	14094	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3469MH0001730021202945C00	2945	14124	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3471 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pastora - after DRT - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3471MH0001730011202957C00				
best focus image:	3472MH0002270001203022R00	3022	motor count:		13991	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3472MH0002270001203023S00	3023	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	12-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3471	focus merged on sol:		3472	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3471MH0001730021202958C00	2958	13871	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
3471MH0001730021202959C00	2959	13901	7.54	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3471MH0001730021202960C00	2960	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	191	3
3471MH0001730021202961C00	2961	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3471MH0001730021202962C00	2962	13991	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3471MH0001730021202963C00	2963	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3471MH0001730021202964C00	2964	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3471MH0001730021202965C00	2965	14081	6.34	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3471 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pastora - after DRT - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3471MH0001730011202967C00				
best focus image:	3472MH0002270001203020R00	3020	motor count:		13994	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3472MH0002270001203021S00	3021	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	12-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3471	focus merged on sol:		3472	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3471MH0001730021202968C00	2968	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	255	1
3471MH0001730021202969C00	2969	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3471MH0001730021202970C00	2970	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	191	3
3471MH0001730021202971C00	2971	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	159	4
3471MH0001730021202972C00	2972	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5
3471MH0001730021202973C00	2973	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3471MH0001730021202974C00	2974	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3471MH0001730021202975C00	2975	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3471 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pastora - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3471MH0001740011202983C00			
best focus image:	3472MH0002270001203018R00		3018	motor count:		14651	range (cm):	3.9	
range map product:	3472MH0002270001203019S00		3019	acquired sequence:		mhli00174	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	12-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3471	focus merged on sol:		3472	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3471MH0001740021202984C00	2984	14411	4.75	-0.1	0.1	23.6	0.3	255	1
3471MH0001740021202985C00	2985	14471	4.53	-0.1	0.1	22.8	0.3	223	2
3471MH0001740021202986C00	2986	14531	4.31	-0.1	0.1	22.1	0.3	191	3
3471MH0001740021202987C00	2987	14591	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	159	4
3471MH0001740021202988C00	2988	14651	3.93	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	127	5
3471MH0001740021202989C00	2989	14711	3.75	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	95	6
3471MH0001740021202990C00	2990	14771	3.59	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	63	7
3471MH0001740021202991C00	2991	14831	3.43	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3471 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3471MH0001680011202995C00			
best focus image:	3472MH0002270001203016R00		3016	motor count:		14030	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3472MH0002270001203017S00		3017	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	12-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3471	focus merged on sol:		3472	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3471MH0001680021202996C00	2996	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	255	1
3471MH0001680021202997C00	2997	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	223	2
3471MH0001680021202998C00	2998	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	191	3
3471MH0001680021202999C00	2999	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3471MH0001680021203000C00	3000	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3471MH0001680021203001C00	3001	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3471MH0001680021203002C00	3002	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3471MH0001680021203003C00	3003	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3471 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3471MH0001680011203005C00					
best focus image:		3472MH0002270001203014R00		3014		motor count:		14016		range (cm): 6.7	
range map product:		3472MH0002270001203015S00		3015		acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative	
acquired on date:		12-May-22				merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18		acquired on sol:		3471		focus merged on sol:		3472	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3471MH0001680021203006C00	3006	13944	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1		
3471MH0001680021203007C00	3007	13962	7.10	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	223	2		
3471MH0001680021203008C00	3008	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3		
3471MH0001680021203009C00	3009	13998	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4		
3471MH0001680021203010C00	3010	14016	6.74	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5		
3471MH0001680021203011C00	3011	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6		
3471MH0001680021203012C00	3012	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7		
3471MH0001680021203013C00	3013	14070	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8		

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3473 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target San_Pedro - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3473MH0002990011203027C00		
best focus image:	3474MH0002270001203086R00			3086	motor count:		14013	range (cm):	6.8
range map product:	3474MH0002270001203087S00			3087	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative
acquired on date:	14-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36		acquired on sol:		3473	focus merged on sol:		3474
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3473MH0002990021203028C00	3028	13869	7.79	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
3473MH0002990021203029C00	3029	13905	7.51	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3473MH0002990021203030C00	3030	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3473MH0002990021203031C00	3031	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3473MH0002990021203032C00	3032	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3473MH0002990021203033C00	3033	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3473MH0002990021203034C00	3034	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3473MH0002990021203035C00	3035	14121	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3473 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target San_Pedro - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3473MH0002990011203037C00		
best focus image:	3474MH0002270001203084R00			3084	motor count:		14015	range (cm):	6.7
range map product:	3474MH0002270001203085S00			3085	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative
acquired on date:	14-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36		acquired on sol:		3473	focus merged on sol:		3474
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3473MH0002990021203038C00	3038	13871	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	255	1
3473MH0002990021203039C00	3039	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	223	2
3473MH0002990021203040C00	3040	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	191	3
3473MH0002990021203041C00	3041	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3473MH0002990021203042C00	3042	14015	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3473MH0002990021203043C00	3043	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3473MH0002990021203044C00	3044	14087	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7
3473MH0002990021203045C00	3045	14123	6.10	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3473 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target San_Pedro - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3473MH0003370011203047C00			
best focus image:	3474MH0002270001203082R00		3082	motor count:		14715	range (cm):	3.7	
range map product:	3474MH0002270001203083S00		3083	acquired sequence:		mhli00337	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	14-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3473	focus merged on sol:		3474	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3473MH0003370021203048C00	3048	14547	4.26	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	255	1
3473MH0003370021203049C00	3049	14589	4.12	-0.1	0.1	21.4	0.3	223	2
3473MH0003370021203050C00	3050	14631	3.99	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	191	3
3473MH0003370021203051C00	3051	14673	3.86	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	159	4
3473MH0003370021203052C00	3052	14715	3.74	-0.1	0.1	20.1	0.3	127	5
3473MH0003370021203053C00	3053	14757	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	95	6
3473MH0003370021203054C00	3054	14799	3.51	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	63	7
3473MH0003370021203055C00	3055	14841	3.41	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3473 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pedra_Pintada - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3473MH0001820011203059C00			
best focus image:	3474MH0002270001203080R00		3080	motor count:		14003	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3474MH0002270001203081S00		3081	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	14-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3473	focus merged on sol:		3474	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3473MH0001820021203060C00	3060	13907	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3473MH0001820021203061C00	3061	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	223	2
3473MH0001820021203062C00	3062	13955	7.15	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	191	3
3473MH0001820021203063C00	3063	13979	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3473MH0001820021203064C00	3064	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3473MH0001820021203065C00	3065	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3473MH0001820021203066C00	3066	14051	6.52	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3473MH0001820021203067C00	3067	14075	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3473 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pedra_Pintada- stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3473MH0001820011203069C00				
best focus image:	3474MH0002270001203078R00	3078	motor count:		14005	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3474MH0002270001203079S00	3079	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3473	focus merged on sol:		3474	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3473MH0001820021203070C00	3070	13909	7.48	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3473MH0001820021203071C00	3071	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3473MH0001820021203072C00	3072	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3473MH0001820021203073C00	3073	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3473MH0001820021203074C00	3074	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3473MH0001820021203075C00	3075	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3473MH0001820021203076C00	3076	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3473MH0001820021203077C00	3077	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3476 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Aratana - stereo-1 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3476MH0008410011203091C00				
best focus image:	3476MH0002650001203112R00	3112	motor count:		13289	range (cm):		16.0	
range map product:	3476MH0002650001203113S00	3113	acquired sequence:		mhli00841	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3476	focus merged on sol:		3476	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3476MH0008410021203092C00	3092	13217	17.93	-0.9	0.9	70.0	3.1	255	1
3476MH0008410021203093C00	3093	13235	17.40	-0.8	0.8	68.1	2.9	223	2
3476MH0008410021203094C00	3094	13253	16.89	-0.8	0.8	66.4	2.7	191	3
3476MH0008410021203095C00	3095	13271	16.41	-0.7	0.7	64.7	2.6	159	4
3476MH0008410021203096C00	3096	13289	15.95	-0.7	0.7	63.1	2.4	127	5
3476MH0008410021203097C00	3097	13307	15.52	-0.7	0.7	61.5	2.3	95	6
3476MH0008410021203098C00	3098	13325	15.10	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	63	7
3476MH0008410021203099C00	3099	13343	14.70	-0.6	0.6	58.6	2.1	31	8

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Sol 3476 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Aratana - stereo-2 - ~14 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3476MH0008410011203101C00				
best focus image:	3476MH0002650001203110R00	3110	motor count:		13290	range (cm):		15.9	
range map product:	3476MH0002650001203111S00	3111	acquired sequence:		mhli00841	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	17-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3476	focus merged on sol:		3476	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3476MH0008410021203102C00	3102	13218	17.90	-0.8	0.9	69.9	3.0	255	1
3476MH0008410021203103C00	3103	13236	17.37	-0.8	0.8	68.0	2.9	223	2
3476MH0008410021203104C00	3104	13254	16.87	-0.8	0.8	66.3	2.7	191	3
3476MH0008410021203105C00	3105	13272	16.39	-0.7	0.7	64.6	2.6	159	4
3476MH0008410021203106C00	3106	13290	15.93	-0.7	0.7	63.0	2.4	127	5
3476MH0008410021203107C00	3107	13308	15.49	-0.7	0.7	61.4	2.3	95	6
3476MH0008410021203108C00	3108	13326	15.08	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	63	7
3476MH0008410021203109C00	3109	13344	14.68	-0.6	0.6	58.6	2.1	31	8

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Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Las_Claritas - mosaic position 1 of 6 - ~95 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0002910011203115C00				
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203222R00	3222	motor count:		13531	range (cm):		11.4	
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203223S00	3223	acquired sequence:		mhli00291	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-May-22	merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0002910021203116C00	3116	13387	13.80	-0.5	0.5	55.5	1.9	255	1
3478MH0002910021203117C00	3117	13423	13.12	-0.5	0.5	53.1	1.7	223	2
3478MH0002910021203118C00	3118	13459	12.50	-0.4	0.4	50.9	1.5	191	3
3478MH0002910021203119C00	3119	13495	11.93	-0.4	0.4	48.9	1.4	159	4
3478MH0002910021203120C00	3120	13531	11.39	-0.4	0.4	47.0	1.3	127	5
3478MH0002910021203121C00	3121	13567	10.90	-0.4	0.3	45.3	1.2	95	6
3478MH0002910021203122C00	3122	13603	10.43	-0.3	0.3	43.6	1.1	63	7
3478MH0002910021203123C00	3123	13639	10.00	-0.3	0.3	42.1	1.0	31	8

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Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Las_Claritas - mosaic position 2 of 6 - ~85 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0002910011203125C00				
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203220R00	3220	motor count:		13605	range (cm):		10.4	
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203221S00	3221	acquired sequence:		mhli00291	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-May-22	merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0002910021203126C00	3126	13461	12.47	-0.4	0.4	50.8	1.5	255	1
3478MH0002910021203127C00	3127	13497	11.90	-0.4	0.4	48.8	1.4	223	2
3478MH0002910021203128C00	3128	13533	11.36	-0.4	0.4	46.9	1.3	191	3
3478MH0002910021203129C00	3129	13569	10.87	-0.3	0.3	45.2	1.2	159	4
3478MH0002910021203130C00	3130	13605	10.41	-0.3	0.3	43.5	1.1	127	5
3478MH0002910021203131C00	3131	13641	9.98	-0.3	0.3	42.0	1.0	95	6
3478MH0002910021203132C00	3132	13677	9.57	-0.3	0.3	40.6	1.0	63	7
3478MH0002910021203133C00	3133	13713	9.20	-0.3	0.3	39.3	0.9	31	8

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Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Las_Claritas - mosaic position 3 of 6 - ~85 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0002910011203135C00			
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203218R00		3218	motor count:		13597	range (cm):	10.5	
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203219S00		3219	acquired sequence:		mhli00291	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	19-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0002910021203136C00	3136	13453	12.60	-0.5	0.4	51.3	1.6	255	1
3478MH0002910021203137C00	3137	13489	12.02	-0.4	0.4	49.2	1.4	223	2
3478MH0002910021203138C00	3138	13525	11.48	-0.4	0.4	47.3	1.3	191	3
3478MH0002910021203139C00	3139	13561	10.98	-0.4	0.3	45.5	1.2	159	4
3478MH0002910021203140C00	3140	13597	10.51	-0.3	0.3	43.9	1.1	127	5
3478MH0002910021203141C00	3141	13633	10.07	-0.3	0.3	42.4	1.0	95	6
3478MH0002910021203142C00	3142	13669	9.66	-0.3	0.3	40.9	1.0	63	7
3478MH0002910021203143C00	3143	13705	9.28	-0.3	0.3	39.6	0.9	31	8

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Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Las_Claritas - mosaic position 4 of 6 - ~95 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0002910011203145C00			
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203216R00		3216	motor count:		13529	range (cm):	11.4	
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203217S00		3217	acquired sequence:		mhli00291	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	19-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0002910021203146C00	3146	13385	13.83	-0.5	0.5	55.6	1.9	255	1
3478MH0002910021203147C00	3147	13421	13.16	-0.5	0.5	53.2	1.7	223	2
3478MH0002910021203148C00	3148	13457	12.53	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.6	191	3
3478MH0002910021203149C00	3149	13493	11.96	-0.4	0.4	49.0	1.4	159	4
3478MH0002910021203150C00	3150	13529	11.42	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	127	5
3478MH0002910021203151C00	3151	13565	10.92	-0.4	0.3	45.4	1.2	95	6
3478MH0002910021203152C00	3152	13601	10.46	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	63	7
3478MH0002910021203153C00	3153	13637	10.02	-0.3	0.3	42.2	1.0	31	8

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Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Las_Claritas - mosaic position 5 of 6 - ~95 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0002910011203155C00			
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203214R00		3214	motor count:		13530	range (cm):	11.4	
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203215S00		3215	acquired sequence:		mhli00291	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	19-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0002910021203156C00	3156	13386	13.82	-0.5	0.5	55.5	1.9	255	1
3478MH0002910021203157C00	3157	13422	13.14	-0.5	0.5	53.2	1.7	223	2
3478MH0002910021203158C00	3158	13458	12.52	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.6	191	3
3478MH0002910021203159C00	3159	13494	11.94	-0.4	0.4	48.9	1.4	159	4
3478MH0002910021203160C00	3160	13530	11.41	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	127	5
3478MH0002910021203161C00	3161	13566	10.91	-0.4	0.3	45.3	1.2	95	6
3478MH0002910021203162C00	3162	13602	10.45	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	63	7
3478MH0002910021203163C00	3163	13638	10.01	-0.3	0.3	42.1	1.0	31	8

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Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Las_Claritas - mosaic position 6 of 6 - ~85 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0002910011203165C00			
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203212R00		3212	motor count:		13601	range (cm):	10.5	
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203213S00		3213	acquired sequence:		mhli00291	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	19-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0002910021203166C00	3166	13457	12.53	-0.4	0.4	51.0	1.6	255	1
3478MH0002910021203167C00	3167	13493	11.96	-0.4	0.4	49.0	1.4	223	2
3478MH0002910021203168C00	3168	13529	11.42	-0.4	0.4	47.1	1.3	191	3
3478MH0002910021203169C00	3169	13565	10.92	-0.4	0.3	45.4	1.2	159	4
3478MH0002910021203170C00	3170	13601	10.46	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	127	5
3478MH0002910021203171C00	3171	13637	10.02	-0.3	0.3	42.2	1.0	95	6
3478MH0002910021203172C00	3172	13673	9.62	-0.3	0.3	40.8	1.0	63	7
3478MH0002910021203173C00	3173	13709	9.24	-0.3	0.3	39.4	0.9	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Las_Claritas - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0001820011203177C00				
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203210R00	3210	motor count:		14077	range (cm):	6.4		
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203211S00	3211	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	19-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0001820021203178C00	3178	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
3478MH0001820021203179C00	3179	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
3478MH0001820021203180C00	3180	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3
3478MH0001820021203181C00	3181	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	159	4
3478MH0001820021203182C00	3182	14077	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	127	5
3478MH0001820021203183C00	3183	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	95	6
3478MH0001820021203184C00	3184	14125	6.09	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
3478MH0001820021203185C00	3185	14149	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Las_Claritas - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0001820011203187C00				
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203208R00	3208	motor count:		14078	range (cm):	6.4		
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203209S00	3209	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	19-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0001820021203188C00	3188	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	255	1
3478MH0001820021203189C00	3189	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	223	2
3478MH0001820021203190C00	3190	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	191	3
3478MH0001820021203191C00	3191	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	159	4
3478MH0001820021203192C00	3192	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	127	5
3478MH0001820021203193C00	3193	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	95	6
3478MH0001820021203194C00	3194	14126	6.08	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	63	7
3478MH0001820021203195C00	3195	14150	5.95	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3478 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Las_Claritas - after DRT - ~15 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3478MH0003020011203197C00				
best focus image:	3478MH0005360001203206R00	3206	motor count:		14866	range (cm):		3.3	
range map product:	3478MH0005360001203207S00	3207	acquired sequence:		mhli00302	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00536	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3478	focus merged on sol:		3478	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3478MH0003020021203198C00	3198	14746	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	255	1
3478MH0003020021203199C00	3199	14776	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	223	2
3478MH0003020021203200C00	3200	14806	3.50	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	191	3
3478MH0003020021203201C00	3201	14836	3.42	-0.1	0.1	18.9	0.2	159	4
3478MH0003020021203202C00	3202	14866	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	127	5
3478MH0003020021203203C00	3203	14896	3.27	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	95	6
3478MH0003020021203204C00	3204	14926	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	63	7
3478MH0003020021203205C00	3205	14956	3.13	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3480 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3480MH0001730011203227C00				
best focus image:	3481MH0001710001203312R00	3312	motor count:		13973	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3481MH0001710001203313S00	3313	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	21-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3480	focus merged on sol:		3481	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3480MH0001730021203228C00	3328	13853	7.92	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	255	1
3480MH0001730021203229C00	3329	13883	7.68	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3480MH0001730021203230C00	3330	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	191	3
3480MH0001730021203231C00	3331	13943	7.23	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3480MH0001730021203232C00	3332	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	127	5
3480MH0001730021203233C00	3333	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3480MH0001730021203234C00	3334	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3480MH0001730021203235C00	3335	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3480 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3480MH0001730011203237C00				
best focus image:	3481MH0001710001203310R00	3310	motor count:		13972	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3481MH0001710001203311S00	3311	acquired sequence:		mhli00173	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	21-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3480	focus merged on sol:		3481	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3480MH0001730021203238C00	3238	13852	7.93	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	255	1
3480MH0001730021203239C00	3239	13882	7.69	-0.2	0.2	34.0	0.7	223	2
3480MH0001730021203240C00	3240	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3480MH0001730021203241C00	3241	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3480MH0001730021203242C00	3242	13972	7.03	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	127	5
3480MH0001730021203243C00	3243	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	95	6
3480MH0001730021203244C00	3244	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3480MH0001730021203245C00	3245	14062	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3480 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Apoteri- stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3480MH0001520011203249C00				
best focus image:	3481MH0001710001203308R00	3308	motor count:		14224	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3481MH0001710001203309S00	3309	acquired sequence:		mhli00152		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-May-22		merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3480	focus merged on sol:		3481	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3480MH0001520021203250C00	3250	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	255	1
3480MH0001520021203251C00	3251	14080	6.35	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	223	2
3480MH0001520021203252C00	3252	14128	6.07	-0.1	0.1	28.3	0.5	191	3
3480MH0001520021203253C00	3253	14176	5.82	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	159	4
3480MH0001520021203254C00	3254	14224	5.57	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3480MH0001520021203255C00	3255	14272	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	95	6
3480MH0001520021203256C00	3256	14320	5.13	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	63	7
3480MH0001520021203257C00	3257	14368	4.93	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3480 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Apoteri- stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3480MH0001520011203259C00				
best focus image:	3481MH0001710001203306R00	3306	motor count:		14228	range (cm):		5.6	
range map product:	3481MH0001710001203307S00	3307	acquired sequence:		mhli00152		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-May-22		merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3480	focus merged on sol:		3481	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3480MH0001520021203260C00	3260	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	255	1
3480MH0001520021203261C00	3261	14084	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.2	0.5	223	2
3480MH0001520021203262C00	3262	14132	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	191	3
3480MH0001520021203263C00	3263	14180	5.80	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	159	4
3480MH0001520021203264C00	3264	14228	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	127	5
3480MH0001520021203265C00	3265	14276	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	95	6
3480MH0001520021203266C00	3266	14324	5.11	-0.1	0.1	24.9	0.4	63	7
3480MH0001520021203267C00	3267	14372	4.91	-0.1	0.1	24.2	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3480 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bamboo_Creek - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3480MH0001820011203271C00			
best focus image:	3481MH0001710001203304R00	3304	motor count:		13987	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3481MH0001710001203305S00	3305	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	21-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3480	focus merged on sol:		3481	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3480MH0001820021203272C00	3472	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3480MH0001820021203273C00	3473	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3480MH0001820021203274C00	3474	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3480MH0001820021203275C00	3475	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3480MH0001820021203276C00	3476	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3480MH0001820021203277C00	3477	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3480MH0001820021203278C00	3478	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3480MH0001820021203279C00	3479	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3480 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Bamboo_Creek - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3480MH0001820011203281C00			
best focus image:	3481MH0001710001203302R00	3302	motor count:		13985	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3481MH0001710001203303S00	3303	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	21-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3480	focus merged on sol:		3481	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3480MH0001820021203282C00	3482	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3480MH0001820021203283C00	3483	13913	7.45	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	223	2
3480MH0001820021203284C00	3484	13937	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3480MH0001820021203285C00	3485	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3480MH0001820021203286C00	3486	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3480MH0001820021203287C00	3487	14009	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3480MH0001820021203288C00	3488	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3480MH0001820021203289C00	3489	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3480 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Bamboo_Creek - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3480MH0007430011203291C00				
best focus image:	3481MH0001710001203300R00	3300	motor count:		15037	range (cm):		3.0	
range map product:	3481MH0001710001203301S00	3301	acquired sequence:		mhli00743	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	21-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3480	focus merged on sol:		3481	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3480MH0007430021203292C00	3492	14893	3.28	-0.1	0.1	18.4	0.2	255	1
3480MH0007430021203293C00	3493	14929	3.20	-0.1	0.1	18.2	0.2	223	2
3480MH0007430021203294C00	3494	14965	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.9	0.2	191	3
3480MH0007430021203295C00	3495	15001	3.04	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	159	4
3480MH0007430021203296C00	3496	15037	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	127	5
3480MH0007430021203297C00	3497	15073	2.89	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	95	6
3480MH0007430021203298C00	3498	15109	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	63	7
3480MH0007430021203299C00	3499	15145	2.75	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3483 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Imatoca - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3483MH0001730011203317C00				
best focus image:	3483MH0001930001203350R00	3350	motor count:		14023	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3483MH0001930001203351S00	3351	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	24-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3483	focus merged on sol:		3483	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3483MH0001730021203318C00	3318	13903	7.53	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	255	1
3483MH0001730021203319C00	3319	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3483MH0001730021203320C00	3320	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3483MH0001730021203321C00	3321	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3483MH0001730021203322C00	3322	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3483MH0001730021203323C00	3323	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
3483MH0001730021203324C00	3324	14083	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	63	7
3483MH0001730021203325C00	3325	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3483 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Imatoca - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3483MH0001730011203327C00				
best focus image:	3483MH0001930001203348R00	3348	motor count:		14030	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3483MH0001930001203349S00	3349	acquired sequence:		mhli00173		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	24-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3483	focus merged on sol:		3483	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3483MH0001730021203328C00	3328	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	255	1
3483MH0001730021203329C00	3329	13940	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3483MH0001730021203330C00	3330	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3483MH0001730021203331C00	3331	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3483MH0001730021203332C00	3332	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3483MH0001730021203333C00	3333	14060	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	95	6
3483MH0001730021203334C00	3334	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7
3483MH0001730021203335C00	3335	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3483 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Imatoca - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3483MH0003370011203337C00				
best focus image:	3483MH0001930001203346R00	3346	motor count:		14742	range (cm):		3.7	
range map product:	3483MH0001930001203347S00	3347	acquired sequence:		mhli00337		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	24-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3483	focus merged on sol:		3483	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3483MH0003370021203338C00	3338	14574	4.17	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	255	1
3483MH0003370021203339C00	3339	14616	4.04	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	223	2
3483MH0003370021203340C00	3340	14658	3.91	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	191	3
3483MH0003370021203341C00	3341	14700	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	159	4
3483MH0003370021203342C00	3342	14742	3.67	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	127	5
3483MH0003370021203343C00	3343	14784	3.55	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	95	6
3483MH0003370021203344C00	3344	14826	3.44	-0.1	0.1	19.0	0.2	63	7
3483MH0003370021203345C00	3345	14868	3.34	-0.1	0.1	18.7	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3485 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - ~24 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3485MH0003590011203353C00				
best focus image:	3485MH0002270001203410R00	3410	motor count:		13031	range (cm):		25.7	
range map product:	3485MH0002270001203411S00	3411	acquired sequence:		mhli00359	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3485	focus merged on sol:		3485	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3485MH0003590021203354C00	3354	12959	30.54	-2.3	2.7	114.4	8.8	255	1
3485MH0003590021203355C00	3355	12977	29.18	-2.1	2.4	109.6	8.0	223	2
3485MH0003590021203356C00	3356	12995	27.92	-2.0	2.2	105.2	7.4	191	3
3485MH0003590021203357C00	3357	13013	26.77	-1.8	2.0	101.1	6.8	159	4
3485MH0003590021203358C00	3358	13031	25.70	-1.7	1.9	97.3	6.2	127	5
3485MH0003590021203359C00	3359	13049	24.70	-1.6	1.7	93.8	5.8	95	6
3485MH0003590021203360C00	3360	13067	23.77	-1.4	1.6	90.6	5.3	63	7
3485MH0003590021203361C00	3361	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3485 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - ~23 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3485MH0003590011203363C00				
best focus image:	3485MH0002270001203408R00	3408	motor count:		13051	range (cm):		24.6	
range map product:	3485MH0002270001203409S00	3409	acquired sequence:		mhli00359	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3485	focus merged on sol:		3485	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3485MH0003590021203364C00	3364	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	255	1
3485MH0003590021203365C00	3365	12997	27.79	-1.9	2.2	104.7	7.3	223	2
3485MH0003590021203366C00	3366	13015	26.64	-1.8	2.0	100.7	6.7	191	3
3485MH0003590021203367C00	3367	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	159	4
3485MH0003590021203368C00	3368	13051	24.59	-1.5	1.7	93.5	5.7	127	5
3485MH0003590021203369C00	3369	13069	23.67	-1.4	1.6	90.2	5.3	95	6
3485MH0003590021203370C00	3370	13087	22.81	-1.3	1.5	87.2	4.9	63	7
3485MH0003590021203371C00	3371	13105	22.00	-1.2	1.4	84.3	4.6	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3485 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - ~22 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3485MH0003590011203373C00			
best focus image:	3485MH0002270001203406R00	3406	motor count:		13071	range (cm):		23.6	
range map product:	3485MH0002270001203407S00	3407	acquired sequence:		mhli00359		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	26-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3485	focus merged on sol:		3485	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3485MH0003590021203374C00	3374	12999	27.66	-1.9	2.2	104.3	7.2	255	1
3485MH0003590021203375C00	3375	13017	26.52	-1.8	2.0	100.3	6.6	223	2
3485MH0003590021203376C00	3376	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	191	3
3485MH0003590021203377C00	3377	13053	24.49	-1.5	1.7	93.1	5.7	159	4
3485MH0003590021203378C00	3378	13071	23.57	-1.4	1.6	89.9	5.2	127	5
3485MH0003590021203379C00	3379	13089	22.71	-1.3	1.4	86.9	4.9	95	6
3485MH0003590021203380C00	3380	13107	21.91	-1.2	1.3	84.0	4.5	63	7
3485MH0003590021203381C00	3381	13125	21.16	-1.2	1.3	81.4	4.2	31	8

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Sol 3485 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - ~7 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3485MH0008470011203383C00			
best focus image:	3485MH0002270001203404R00	3404	motor count:		13725	range (cm):		9.1	
range map product:	3485MH0002270001203405S00	3405	acquired sequence:		mhli00847		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	26-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3485	focus merged on sol:		3485	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3485MH0008470021203384C00	3384	13509	11.71	-0.4	0.4	48.1	1.4	255	1
3485MH0008470021203385C00	3385	13563	10.95	-0.4	0.3	45.4	1.2	223	2
3485MH0008470021203386C00	3386	13617	10.26	-0.3	0.3	43.0	1.1	191	3
3485MH0008470021203387C00	3387	13671	9.64	-0.3	0.3	40.8	1.0	159	4
3485MH0008470021203388C00	3388	13725	9.07	-0.3	0.2	38.8	0.9	127	5
3485MH0008470021203389C00	3389	13779	8.56	-0.2	0.2	37.0	0.8	95	6
3485MH0008470021203390C00	3390	13833	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.4	0.7	63	7
3485MH0008470021203391C00	3391	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	31	8

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Sol 3485 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cabo_Sobral- stereo-2 - ~7 cm standoff								
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3485MH0008470011203393C00			
best focus image:	3485MH0002270001203402R00			3402	motor count:		13759	range (cm):	8.7	
range map product:	3485MH0002270001203403S00			3403	acquired sequence:		mhli00847	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	26-May-22				merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		54		acquired on sol:		3485		focus merged on sol:		3485
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3485MH0008470021203394C00	3394	13543	11.22	-0.4	0.4	46.4	1.3	255	1	
3485MH0008470021203395C00	3395	13597	10.51	-0.3	0.3	43.9	1.1	223	2	
3485MH0008470021203396C00	3396	13651	9.86	-0.3	0.3	41.6	1.0	191	3	
3485MH0008470021203397C00	3397	13705	9.28	-0.3	0.3	39.6	0.9	159	4	
3485MH0008470021203398C00	3398	13759	8.74	-0.2	0.2	37.7	0.8	127	5	
3485MH0008470021203399C00	3399	13813	8.25	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	95	6	
3485MH0008470021203400C00	3400	13867	7.81	-0.2	0.2	34.4	0.7	63	7	
3485MH0008470021203401C00	3401	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	31	8	

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3488 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pitinga - no DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3488MH0001680011203415C00			
best focus image:	3488MH0001530001203468R00	3468	motor count:		14000	range (cm):	6.8		
range map product:	3488MH0001530001203469S00	3469	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	30-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3488	focus merged on sol:		3488	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3488MH0001680021203416C00	3416	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3488MH0001680021203417C00	3417	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3488MH0001680021203418C00	3418	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3488MH0001680021203419C00	3419	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3488MH0001680021203420C00	3420	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3488MH0001680021203421C00	3421	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3488MH0001680021203422C00	3422	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	63	7
3488MH0001680021203423C00	3423	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3488 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pitinga - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 1 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3488MH0001680011203427C00			
best focus image:	3488MH0001530001203466R00	3466	motor count:		14011	range (cm):	6.8		
range map product:	3488MH0001530001203467S00	3467	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	30-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3488	focus merged on sol:		3488	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3488MH0001680021203428C00	3428	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3488MH0001680021203429C00	3429	13957	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3488MH0001680021203430C00	3430	13975	7.01	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3
3488MH0001680021203431C00	3431	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3488MH0001680021203432C00	3432	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3488MH0001680021203433C00	3433	14029	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6
3488MH0001680021203434C00	3434	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3488MH0001680021203435C00	3435	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3488 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pitinga - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3488MH0001680011203437C00			
best focus image:	3488MH0001530001203464R00	3464	motor count:		14005	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3488MH0001530001203465S00	3465	acquired sequence:		mhli00168		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	30-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3488	focus merged on sol:		3488	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3488MH0001680021203438C00	3438	13933	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3488MH0001680021203439C00	3439	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3488MH0001680021203440C00	3440	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3488MH0001680021203441C00	3441	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3488MH0001680021203442C00	3442	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3488MH0001680021203443C00	3443	14023	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3488MH0001680021203444C00	3444	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3488MH0001680021203445C00	3445	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3488 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Pitinga - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3488MH0008480011203453C00			
best focus image:	3488MH0001530001203462R00	3462	motor count:		15109	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3488MH0001530001203463S00	3463	acquired sequence:		mhli00848		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	30-May-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3488	focus merged on sol:		3488	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3488MH0008480021203454C00	3454	15013	3.01	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	255	1
3488MH0008480021203455C00	3455	15037	2.96	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3488MH0008480021203456C00	3456	15061	2.91	-0.1	0.1	17.1	0.2	191	3
3488MH0008480021203457C00	3457	15085	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
3488MH0008480021203458C00	3458	15109	2.82	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
3488MH0008480021203459C00	3459	15133	2.77	-0.1	0.1	16.7	0.2	95	6
3488MH0008480021203460C00	3460	15157	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	63	7
3488MH0008480021203461C00	3461	15181	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3491 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Parepona - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3491MH0001820011203473C00			
best focus image:	3491MH0001630001203544R00		3544		motor count:		14021	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3491MH0001630001203545S00		3545		acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Jun-22				merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24		acquired on sol:		3491		focus merged on sol:		3491
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3491MH0001820021203474C00	3474	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1	
3491MH0001820021203475C00	3475	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2	
3491MH0001820021203476C00	3476	13973	7.02	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3	
3491MH0001820021203477C00	3477	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4	
3491MH0001820021203478C00	3478	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5	
3491MH0001820021203479C00	3479	14045	6.56	-0.2	0.1	30.0	0.5	95	6	
3491MH0001820021203480C00	3480	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7	
3491MH0001820021203481C00	3481	14093	6.27	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8	

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Sol 3491 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Parepona - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3491MH0001820011203483C00			
best focus image:	3491MH0001630001203542R00		3542		motor count:		14024	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3491MH0001630001203543S00		3543		acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Jun-22				merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24		acquired on sol:		3491		focus merged on sol:		3491
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3491MH0001820021203484C00	3484	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1	
3491MH0001820021203485C00	3485	13952	7.17	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2	
3491MH0001820021203486C00	3486	13976	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.6	0.6	191	3	
3491MH0001820021203487C00	3487	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4	
3491MH0001820021203488C00	3488	14024	6.69	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5	
3491MH0001820021203489C00	3489	14048	6.54	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6	
3491MH0001820021203490C00	3490	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7	
3491MH0001820021203491C00	3491	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8	

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Sol 3491 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Parepona - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3491MH0003020011203493C00			
best focus image:	3491MH0001630001203540R00		3540	motor count:		14729	range (cm):	3.7	
range map product:	3491MH0001630001203541S00		3541	acquired sequence:		mhli00302	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3491	focus merged on sol:		3491	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3491MH0003020021203494C00	3494	14609	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	255	1
3491MH0003020021203495C00	3495	14639	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.9	0.3	223	2
3491MH0003020021203496C00	3496	14669	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	191	3
3491MH0003020021203497C00	3497	14699	3.79	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	159	4
3491MH0003020021203498C00	3498	14729	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	127	5
3491MH0003020021203499C00	3499	14759	3.62	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	95	6
3491MH0003020021203500C00	3500	14789	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3491MH0003020021203501C00	3501	14819	3.46	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3491 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3491MH0002990011203505C00			
best focus image:	3491MH0001630001203538R00		3538	motor count:		13948	range (cm):	7.2	
range map product:	3491MH0001630001203539S00		3539	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3491	focus merged on sol:		3491	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3491MH0002990021203506C00	3506	13804	8.33	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	255	1
3491MH0002990021203507C00	3507	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	223	2
3491MH0002990021203508C00	3508	13876	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	191	3
3491MH0002990021203509C00	3509	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	159	4
3491MH0002990021203510C00	3510	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	127	5
3491MH0002990021203511C00	3511	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	95	6
3491MH0002990021203512C00	3512	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
3491MH0002990021203513C00	3513	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3491 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3491MH0002990011203515C00				
best focus image:	3491MH0001630001203536R00	3536	motor count:		13950	range (cm):		7.2	
range map product:	3491MH0001630001203537S00	3537	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3491	focus merged on sol:		3491	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3491MH0002990021203516C00	3516	13806	8.32	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	255	1
3491MH0002990021203517C00	3517	13842	8.01	-0.2	0.2	35.1	0.7	223	2
3491MH0002990021203518C00	3518	13878	7.72	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	191	3
3491MH0002990021203519C00	3519	13914	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.7	159	4
3491MH0002990021203520C00	3520	13950	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	127	5
3491MH0002990021203521C00	3521	13986	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	95	6
3491MH0002990021203522C00	3522	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	63	7
3491MH0002990021203523C00	3523	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3491 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Cabadiscana - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3491MH0003110011203525C00				
best focus image:	3491MH0001630001203534R00	3534	motor count:		14553	range (cm):		4.2	
range map product:	3491MH0001630001203535S00	3535	acquired sequence:		mhli00311	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	2-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		66	acquired on sol:		3491	focus merged on sol:		3491	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3491MH0003110021203526C00	3526	14289	5.27	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	255	1
3491MH0003110021203527C00	3527	14355	4.98	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	223	2
3491MH0003110021203528C00	3528	14421	4.72	-0.1	0.1	23.5	0.3	191	3
3491MH0003110021203529C00	3529	14487	4.47	-0.1	0.1	22.6	0.3	159	4
3491MH0003110021203530C00	3530	14553	4.24	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	127	5
3491MH0003110021203531C00	3531	14619	4.03	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	95	6
3491MH0003110021203532C00	3532	14685	3.83	-0.1	0.1	20.4	0.3	63	7
3491MH0003110021203533C00	3533	14751	3.64	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3493 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tabacco - mosaic position 1 of 4 - ~16 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3493MH0008490011203567C00				
best focus image:	3493MH0001710001203656R00	3656	motor count:		13203	range (cm):		18.4	
range map product:	3493MH0001710001203657S00	3657	acquired sequence:		mhli00849	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3493	focus merged on sol:		3493	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3493MH0008490021203568C00	3568	13059	24.17	-1.5	1.6	92.0	5.5	255	1
3493MH0008490021203569C00	3569	13095	22.44	-1.3	1.4	85.9	4.8	223	2
3493MH0008490021203570C00	3570	13131	20.92	-1.1	1.2	80.5	4.1	191	3
3493MH0008490021203571C00	3571	13167	19.57	-1.0	1.1	75.8	3.6	159	4
3493MH0008490021203572C00	3572	13203	18.36	-0.9	0.9	71.5	3.2	127	5
3493MH0008490021203573C00	3573	13239	17.28	-0.8	0.8	67.7	2.8	95	6
3493MH0008490021203574C00	3574	13275	16.31	-0.7	0.7	64.3	2.5	63	7
3493MH0008490021203575C00	3575	13311	15.42	-0.6	0.7	61.2	2.3	31	8

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Sol 3493 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tabacco - mosaic position 2 of 4 - ~16 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3493MH0008490011203577C00				
best focus image:	3493MH0001710001203654R00	3654	motor count:		13218	range (cm):		17.9	
range map product:	3493MH0001710001203655S00	3655	acquired sequence:		mhli00849	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3493	focus merged on sol:		3493	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (μm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (μm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3493MH0008490021203578C00	3578	13074	23.42	-1.4	1.5	89.4	5.2	255	1
3493MH0008490021203579C00	3579	13110	21.78	-1.2	1.3	83.6	4.5	223	2
3493MH0008490021203580C00	3580	13146	20.34	-1.1	1.2	78.5	3.9	191	3
3493MH0008490021203581C00	3581	13182	19.05	-1.0	1.0	74.0	3.4	159	4
3493MH0008490021203582C00	3582	13218	17.90	-0.8	0.9	69.9	3.0	127	5
3493MH0008490021203583C00	3583	13254	16.87	-0.8	0.8	66.3	2.7	95	6
3493MH0008490021203584C00	3584	13290	15.93	-0.7	0.7	63.0	2.4	63	7
3493MH0008490021203585C00	3585	13326	15.08	-0.6	0.6	60.0	2.2	31	8

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Sol 3493 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tabaco - mosaic position 3 of 4 - ~16 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3493MH0008490011203587C00				
best focus image:	3493MH0001710001203652R00	3652	motor count:		13229	range (cm):		17.6	
range map product:	3493MH0001710001203653S00	3653	acquired sequence:		mhli00849		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3493	focus merged on sol:		3493	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3493MH0008490021203588C00	3588	13085	22.90	-1.3	1.5	87.5	5.0	255	1
3493MH0008490021203589C00	3589	13121	21.32	-1.2	1.3	82.0	4.3	223	2
3493MH0008490021203590C00	3590	13157	19.93	-1.0	1.1	77.0	3.8	191	3
3493MH0008490021203591C00	3591	13193	18.69	-0.9	1.0	72.7	3.3	159	4
3493MH0008490021203592C00	3592	13229	17.57	-0.8	0.9	68.8	2.9	127	5
3493MH0008490021203593C00	3593	13265	16.57	-0.7	0.8	65.2	2.6	95	6
3493MH0008490021203594C00	3594	13301	15.66	-0.7	0.7	62.0	2.3	63	7
3493MH0008490021203595C00	3595	13337	14.83	-0.6	0.6	59.1	2.1	31	8

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Sol 3493 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tabaco - mosaic position 4 of 4 - ~16 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3493MH0008490011203597C00				
best focus image:	3493MH0001710001203650R00	3650	motor count:		13228	range (cm):		17.6	
range map product:	3493MH0001710001203651S00	3651	acquired sequence:		mhli00849		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3493	focus merged on sol:		3493	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3493MH0008490021203598C00	3598	13084	22.95	-1.4	1.5	87.7	5.0	255	1
3493MH0008490021203599C00	3599	13120	21.36	-1.2	1.3	82.1	4.3	223	2
3493MH0008490021203600C00	3600	13156	19.96	-1.0	1.1	77.2	3.8	191	3
3493MH0008490021203601C00	3601	13192	18.72	-0.9	1.0	72.8	3.3	159	4
3493MH0008490021203602C00	3602	13228	17.60	-0.8	0.9	68.9	2.9	127	5
3493MH0008490021203603C00	3603	13264	16.60	-0.7	0.8	65.3	2.6	95	6
3493MH0008490021203604C00	3604	13300	15.68	-0.7	0.7	62.1	2.4	63	7
3493MH0008490021203605C00	3605	13336	14.85	-0.6	0.6	59.2	2.1	31	8

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Sol 3493 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Issano - after DRT - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3493MH0001680011203609C00			
best focus image:	3493MH0001710001203648R00	3648	motor count:		14002	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3493MH0001710001203649S00	3649	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3493	focus merged on sol:		3493	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3493MH0001680021203610C00	3610	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3493MH0001680021203611C00	3611	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3493MH0001680021203612C00	3612	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3493MH0001680021203613C00	3613	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3493MH0001680021203614C00	3614	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3493MH0001680021203615C00	3615	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3493MH0001680021203616C00	3616	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3493MH0001680021203617C00	3617	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3493 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Issano - after DRT - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3493MH0001680011203619C00			
best focus image:	3493MH0001710001203646R00	3646	motor count:		14003	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3493MH0001710001203647S00	3647	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	4-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3493	focus merged on sol:		3493	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3493MH0001680021203620C00	3620	13931	7.32	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3493MH0001680021203621C00	3621	13949	7.19	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3493MH0001680021203622C00	3622	13967	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3493MH0001680021203623C00	3623	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	159	4
3493MH0001680021203624C00	3624	14003	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3493MH0001680021203625C00	3625	14021	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3493MH0001680021203626C00	3626	14039	6.59	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3493MH0001680021203627C00	3627	14057	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3493 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Issano - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3493MH0007430011203635C00				
best focus image:	3493MH0001710001203644R00	3644	motor count:		15112	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3493MH0001710001203645S00	3645	acquired sequence:		mhli00743		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	4-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3493	focus merged on sol:		3493	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3493MH0007430021203636C00	3636	14968	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
3493MH0007430021203637C00	3637	15004	3.03	-0.1	0.1	17.6	0.2	223	2
3493MH0007430021203638C00	3638	15040	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	191	3
3493MH0007430021203639C00	3639	15076	2.88	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	159	4
3493MH0007430021203640C00	3640	15112	2.81	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	127	5
3493MH0007430021203641C00	3641	15148	2.74	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	95	6
3493MH0007430021203642C00	3642	15184	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	63	7
3493MH0007430021203643C00	3643	15220	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3503 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		ChemCam RWEB window - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3503MH0005200011203659C00				
best focus image:	3503MH0008500001203772R00	3772	motor count:		13100	range (cm):	22.2		
range map product:	3503MH0008500001203773S00	3773	acquired sequence:		mhli00520	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	14-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00850	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3503	focus merged on sol:		3503	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 16
				near	far				
3503MH0005200021203660C00	3660	12908	35.11	-3.0	3.6	130.5	11.7	n/a	1
3503MH0005200021203661C00	3661	12932	32.81	-2.7	3.1	122.4	10.2	n/a	2
3503MH0005200021203662C00	3662	12956	30.77	-2.4	2.7	115.2	9.0	255	3
3503MH0005200021203663C00	3663	12980	28.96	-2.1	2.4	108.8	7.9	223	4
3503MH0005200021203664C00	3664	13004	27.34	-1.9	2.1	103.1	7.1	191	5
3503MH0005200021203665C00	3665	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	159	6
3503MH0005200021203666C00	3666	13052	24.54	-1.5	1.7	93.3	5.7	127	7
3503MH0005200021203667C00	3667	13076	23.33	-1.4	1.5	89.0	5.1	95	8
3503MH0005200021203668C00	3668	13100	22.22	-1.3	1.4	85.1	4.7	63	9
3503MH0005200021203669C00	3669	13124	21.20	-1.2	1.3	81.5	4.2	31	10
3503MH0005200021203670C00	3670	13148	20.26	-1.1	1.1	78.2	3.9	n/a	11
3503MH0005200021203671C00	3671	13172	19.39	-1.0	1.0	75.2	3.6	n/a	12
3503MH0005200021203672C00	3672	13196	18.59	-0.9	1.0	72.3	3.3	n/a	13
3503MH0005200021203673C00	3673	13220	17.84	-0.8	0.9	69.7	3.0	n/a	14
3503MH0005200021203674C00	3674	13244	17.14	-0.8	0.8	67.2	2.8	n/a	15
3503MH0005200021203675C00	3675	13268	16.49	-0.7	0.8	64.9	2.6	n/a	16

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Sol 3503 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		ChemCam RWEB window - focused on internal hardware - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3503MH0005200041203677C00				
best focus image:	3503MH0008500001203770R00	3770	motor count:		12990	range (cm):		28.3	
range map product:	3503MH0008500001203771S00	3771	acquired sequence:		mhli00520	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jun-22	merge sequence:		mhli00850	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3503	focus merged on sol:		3503	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3503MH0005200051203678C00	3678	12894	36.59	-3.3	4.0	135.7	12.7	255	1
3503MH0005200051203679C00	3679	12918	34.11	-2.9	3.4	127.0	11.1	223	2
3503MH0005200051203680C00	3680	12942	31.93	-2.5	3.0	119.3	9.7	191	3
3503MH0005200051203681C00	3681	12966	29.99	-2.2	2.6	112.5	8.5	159	4
3503MH0005200051203682C00	3682	12990	28.26	-2.0	2.3	106.4	7.5	127	5
3503MH0005200051203683C00	3683	13014	26.71	-1.8	2.0	100.9	6.7	95	6
3503MH0005200051203684C00	3684	13038	25.30	-1.6	1.8	96.0	6.0	63	7
3503MH0005200051203685C00	3685	13062	24.02	-1.5	1.6	91.5	5.4	31	8

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Sol 3503 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3503MH0007400011203690C00				
best focus image:	3503MH0008500001203768R00	3768	motor count:		14066	range (cm):		6.4	
range map product:	3503MH0008500001203769S00	3769	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jun-22	merge sequence:		mhli00850	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3503	focus merged on sol:		3503	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3503MH0007400031203692C00	3692	13850	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3503MH0007400031203693C00	3693	13904	7.52	-0.2	0.2	33.4	0.7	223	2
3503MH0007400031203694C00	3694	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3503MH0007400031203695C00	3695	14012	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	159	4
3503MH0007400031203696C00	3696	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	127	5
3503MH0007400031203697C00	3697	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	95	6
3503MH0007400031203698C00	3698	14174	5.83	-0.1	0.1	27.4	0.4	63	7
3503MH0007400031203699C00	3699	14228	5.55	-0.1	0.1	26.5	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3503 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - ~4 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3503MH0007400011203701C00			
best focus image:	3503MH0008500001203766R00		3766	motor count:		14155	range (cm):	5.9	
range map product:	3503MH0008500001203767S00		3767	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00850	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3503	focus merged on sol:		3503	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3503MH0007400031203703C00	3703	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	255	1
3503MH0007400031203704C00	3704	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	223	2
3503MH0007400031203705C00	3705	14047	6.55	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	191	3
3503MH0007400031203706C00	3706	14101	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	159	4
3503MH0007400031203707C00	3707	14155	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	127	5
3503MH0007400031203708C00	3708	14209	5.65	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	95	6
3503MH0007400031203709C00	3709	14263	5.39	-0.1	0.1	25.9	0.4	63	7
3503MH0007400031203710C00	3710	14317	5.14	-0.1	0.1	25.0	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3503 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - ~45 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3503MH0007400011203712C00			
best focus image:	3503MH0008500001203764R00		3764	motor count:		14107	range (cm):	6.2	
range map product:	3503MH0008500001203765S00		3765	acquired sequence:		mhli00740	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00850	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3503	focus merged on sol:		3503	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3503MH0007400031203714C00	3714	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3503MH0007400031203715C00	3715	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3503MH0007400031203716C00	3716	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
3503MH0007400031203717C00	3717	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	159	4
3503MH0007400031203718C00	3718	14107	6.19	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
3503MH0007400031203719C00	3719	14161	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	95	6
3503MH0007400031203720C00	3720	14215	5.62	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	63	7
3503MH0007400031203721C00	3721	14269	5.36	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3503 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Omai - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3503MH0007230011203726C00			
best focus image:	3503MH0008500001203762R00			3762	motor count:		13995	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3503MH0008500001203763S00			3763	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jun-22				merge sequence:		mhli00850	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36		acquired on sol:		3503		focus merged on sol:		3503
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3503MH0007230031203728C00	3728	13851	7.94	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	255	1	
3503MH0007230031203729C00	3729	13887	7.65	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	223	2	
3503MH0007230031203730C00	3730	13923	7.38	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3	
3503MH0007230031203731C00	3731	13959	7.12	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4	
3503MH0007230031203732C00	3732	13995	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5	
3503MH0007230031203733C00	3733	14031	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	95	6	
3503MH0007230031203734C00	3734	14067	6.42	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7	
3503MH0007230031203735C00	3735	14103	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8	

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Sol 3503 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Omai - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3503MH0007230011203737C00			
best focus image:	3503MH0008500001203760R00			3760	motor count:		13997	range (cm):	6.9	
range map product:	3503MH0008500001203761S00			3761	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jun-22				merge sequence:		mhli00850	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36		acquired on sol:		3503		focus merged on sol:		3503
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3503MH0007230031203739C00	3739	13853	7.92	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	255	1	
3503MH0007230031203740C00	3740	13889	7.63	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	223	2	
3503MH0007230031203741C00	3741	13925	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	191	3	
3503MH0007230031203742C00	3742	13961	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4	
3503MH0007230031203743C00	3743	13997	6.86	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	127	5	
3503MH0007230031203744C00	3744	14033	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6	
3503MH0007230031203745C00	3745	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7	
3503MH0007230031203746C00	3746	14105	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	31	8	

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Sol 3503 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Omai - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3503MH0006560011203748C00			
best focus image:	3503MH0008500001203758R00	3758	motor count:		14668	range (cm):		3.9	
range map product:	3503MH0008500001203759S00	3759	acquired sequence:		mhli00656		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	14-Jun-22				merge sequence:		mhli00850		
motor count interval:		60	acquired on sol:		3503	focus merged on sol:		3503	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3503MH0006560031203750C00	3750	14428	4.69	-0.1	0.1	23.4	0.3	255	1
3503MH0006560031203751C00	3751	14488	4.47	-0.1	0.1	22.6	0.3	223	2
3503MH0006560031203752C00	3752	14548	4.26	-0.1	0.1	21.9	0.3	191	3
3503MH0006560031203753C00	3753	14608	4.06	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4
3503MH0006560031203754C00	3754	14668	3.88	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	127	5
3503MH0006560031203755C00	3755	14728	3.70	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	95	6
3503MH0006560031203756C00	3756	14788	3.54	-0.1	0.1	19.4	0.3	63	7
3503MH0006560031203757C00	3757	14848	3.39	-0.1	0.1	18.8	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3505 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tipuru - ~23 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3505MH0003590011203775C00					
best focus image:		3505MH0002580001203808R00		3808		motor count:		13046		range (cm): 24.9	
range map product:		3505MH0002580001203809S00		3809		acquired sequence:		mhli00359		stack type: Relative	
acquired on date:		16-Jun-22				merge sequence:		mhli00258		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		18		acquired on sol:		3505		focus merged on sol:		3505	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3505MH0003590021203776C00	3776	12974	29.40	-2.2	2.5	110.4	8.2	255	1		
3505MH0003590021203777C00	3777	12992	28.13	-2.0	2.3	105.9	7.5	223	2		
3505MH0003590021203778C00	3778	13010	26.95	-1.8	2.1	101.8	6.9	191	3		
3505MH0003590021203779C00	3779	13028	25.87	-1.7	1.9	98.0	6.3	159	4		
3505MH0003590021203780C00	3780	13046	24.86	-1.6	1.7	94.4	5.8	127	5		
3505MH0003590021203781C00	3781	13064	23.92	-1.5	1.6	91.1	5.4	95	6		
3505MH0003590021203782C00	3782	13082	23.04	-1.4	1.5	88.0	5.0	63	7		
3505MH0003590021203783C00	3783	13100	22.22	-1.3	1.4	85.1	4.7	31	8		

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Sol 3508 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Kukui - ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3508MH0007810011203811C00				
best focus image:	3508MH0001710001203905R00	3905	motor count:		13011	range (cm):		26.9	
range map product:	3508MH0001710001203906S00	3906	acquired sequence:		mhli00781	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3508	focus merged on sol:		3508	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3508MH0007810031203813C00	3813	12891	36.92	-3.3	4.0	136.9	13.0	255	1
3508MH0007810031203814C00	3814	12921	33.82	-2.8	3.4	126.0	10.9	223	2
3508MH0007810031203815C00	3815	12951	31.18	-2.4	2.8	116.6	9.2	191	3
3508MH0007810031203816C00	3816	12981	28.89	-2.1	2.4	108.6	7.9	159	4
3508MH0007810031203817C00	3817	13011	26.89	-1.8	2.1	101.6	6.8	127	5
3508MH0007810031203818C00	3818	13041	25.13	-1.6	1.8	95.4	6.0	95	6
3508MH0007810031203819C00	3819	13071	23.57	-1.4	1.6	89.9	5.2	63	7
3508MH0007810031203820C00	3820	13101	22.17	-1.3	1.4	85.0	4.6	31	8

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Sol 3508 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Kukui - stereo-1 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3508MH0007980011203822C00				
best focus image:	3508MH0001710001203903R00	3903	motor count:		13579	range (cm):		10.7	
range map product:	3508MH0001710001203904S00	3904	acquired sequence:		mhli00798	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		78	acquired on sol:		3508	focus merged on sol:		3508	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3508MH0007980031203824C00	3824	13267	16.52	-0.7	0.8	65.0	2.6	255	1
3508MH0007980031203825C00	3825	13345	14.66	-0.6	0.6	58.5	2.1	223	2
3508MH0007980031203826C00	3826	13423	13.12	-0.5	0.5	53.1	1.7	191	3
3508MH0007980031203827C00	3827	13501	11.83	-0.4	0.4	48.6	1.4	159	4
3508MH0007980031203828C00	3828	13579	10.74	-0.3	0.3	44.7	1.2	127	5
3508MH0007980031203829C00	3829	13657	9.80	-0.3	0.3	41.4	1.0	95	6
3508MH0007980031203830C00	3830	13735	8.98	-0.3	0.2	38.5	0.9	63	7
3508MH0007980031203831C00	3831	13813	8.25	-0.2	0.2	36.0	0.8	31	8

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Sol 3508 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Kukui - stereo-2 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3508MH0007980011203833C00				
best focus image:	3508MH0001710001203901R00	3901	motor count:		13583	range (cm):	10.7		
range map product:	3508MH0001710001203902S00	3902	acquired sequence:		mhli00798	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	19-Jun-22			merge sequence:	mhli00171	merge type:	Basic		
motor count interval:		78	acquired on sol:		3508	focus merged on sol:		3508	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3508MH0007980031203835C00	3835	13271	16.41	-0.7	0.7	64.7	2.6	255	1
3508MH0007980031203836C00	3836	13349	14.57	-0.6	0.6	58.2	2.0	223	2
3508MH0007980031203837C00	3837	13427	13.05	-0.5	0.5	52.8	1.7	191	3
3508MH0007980031203838C00	3838	13505	11.77	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	159	4
3508MH0007980031203839C00	3839	13583	10.69	-0.3	0.3	44.5	1.1	127	5
3508MH0007980031203840C00	3840	13661	9.75	-0.3	0.3	41.2	1.0	95	6
3508MH0007980031203841C00	3841	13739	8.94	-0.3	0.2	38.4	0.9	63	7
3508MH0007980031203842C00	3842	13817	8.22	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.8	31	8

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Sol 3508 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3508MH0008520011203847C00				
best focus image:	3508MH0001710001203899R00	3899	motor count:		13596	range (cm):	10.5		
range map product:	3508MH0001710001203900S00	3900	acquired sequence:		mhli00852	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	19-Jun-22			merge sequence:	mhli00171	merge type:	Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3508	focus merged on sol:		3508	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3508MH0008520031203849C00	3849	13476	12.22	-0.4	0.4	49.9	1.5	255	1
3508MH0008520031203850C00	3850	13506	11.76	-0.4	0.4	48.3	1.4	223	2
3508MH0008520031203851C00	3851	13536	11.32	-0.4	0.4	46.8	1.3	191	3
3508MH0008520031203852C00	3852	13566	10.91	-0.4	0.3	45.3	1.2	159	4
3508MH0008520031203853C00	3853	13596	10.52	-0.3	0.3	43.9	1.1	127	5
3508MH0008520031203854C00	3854	13626	10.15	-0.3	0.3	42.6	1.1	95	6
3508MH0008520031203855C00	3855	13656	9.81	-0.3	0.3	41.4	1.0	63	7
3508MH0008520031203856C00	3856	13686	9.48	-0.3	0.3	40.3	0.9	31	8

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Sol 3508 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3508MH0008520011203858C00				
best focus image:	3508MH0001710001203897R00	3897	motor count:		13601	range (cm):		10.5	
range map product:	3508MH0001710001203898S00	3898	acquired sequence:		mhli00852	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3508	focus merged on sol:		3508	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3508MH0008520031203860C00	3860	13481	12.14	-0.4	0.4	49.7	1.5	255	1
3508MH0008520031203861C00	3861	13511	11.68	-0.4	0.4	48.0	1.4	223	2
3508MH0008520031203862C00	3862	13541	11.25	-0.4	0.4	46.5	1.3	191	3
3508MH0008520031203863C00	3863	13571	10.84	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	159	4
3508MH0008520031203864C00	3864	13601	10.46	-0.3	0.3	43.7	1.1	127	5
3508MH0008520031203865C00	3865	13631	10.10	-0.3	0.3	42.4	1.0	95	6
3508MH0008520031203866C00	3866	13661	9.75	-0.3	0.3	41.2	1.0	63	7
3508MH0008520031203867C00	3867	13691	9.42	-0.3	0.3	40.1	0.9	31	8

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Sol 3508 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Opadai - stereo-1 - ~9 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3508MH0008510011203872C00				
best focus image:	3508MH0001710001203895R00	3895	motor count:		13572	range (cm):		10.8	
range map product:	3508MH0001710001203896S00	3896	acquired sequence:		mhli00851	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3508	focus merged on sol:		3508	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3508MH0008510031203874C00	3874	13500	11.85	-0.4	0.4	48.6	1.4	255	1
3508MH0008510031203875C00	3875	13518	11.58	-0.4	0.4	47.7	1.3	223	2
3508MH0008510031203876C00	3876	13536	11.32	-0.4	0.4	46.8	1.3	191	3
3508MH0008510031203877C00	3877	13554	11.07	-0.4	0.4	45.9	1.2	159	4
3508MH0008510031203878C00	3878	13572	10.83	-0.3	0.3	45.0	1.2	127	5
3508MH0008510031203879C00	3879	13590	10.60	-0.3	0.3	44.2	1.1	95	6
3508MH0008510031203880C00	3880	13608	10.37	-0.3	0.3	43.4	1.1	63	7
3508MH0008510031203881C00	3881	13626	10.15	-0.3	0.3	42.6	1.1	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3508 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Opadai - stereo-2 - ~9 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3508MH0008510011203883C00				
best focus image:	3508MH0001710001203893R00	3893	motor count:		13571	range (cm):		10.8	
range map product:	3508MH0001710001203894S00	3894	acquired sequence:		mhli00851	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	19-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00171	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3508	focus merged on sol:		3508	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3508MH0008510031203885C00	3885	13499	11.87	-0.4	0.4	48.7	1.4	255	1
3508MH0008510031203886C00	3886	13517	11.60	-0.4	0.4	47.7	1.3	223	2
3508MH0008510031203887C00	3887	13535	11.34	-0.4	0.4	46.8	1.3	191	3
3508MH0008510031203888C00	3888	13553	11.09	-0.4	0.4	45.9	1.3	159	4
3508MH0008510031203889C00	3889	13571	10.84	-0.3	0.3	45.1	1.2	127	5
3508MH0008510031203890C00	3890	13589	10.61	-0.3	0.3	44.3	1.1	95	6
3508MH0008510031203891C00	3891	13607	10.38	-0.3	0.3	43.5	1.1	63	7
3508MH0008510031203892C00	3892	13625	10.17	-0.3	0.3	42.7	1.1	31	8

updated: 13_September_2022

Sol 3511 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Avanvero - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3511MH0001820011203914C00		
best focus image:	3511MH0001530001203961R00	3961		motor count:		14013	range (cm):	6.8	
range map product:	3511MH0001530001203962S00	3962		acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3511	focus merged on sol:		3511	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3511MH0001820021203915C00	3915	13917	7.42	-0.2	0.2	33.0	0.6	255	1
3511MH0001820021203916C00	3916	13941	7.25	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	223	2
3511MH0001820021203917C00	3917	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3511MH0001820021203918C00	3918	13989	6.92	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3511MH0001820021203919C00	3919	14013	6.76	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	127	5
3511MH0001820021203920C00	3920	14037	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3511MH0001820021203921C00	3921	14061	6.46	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3511MH0001820021203922C00	3922	14085	6.32	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_September_2022

Sol 3511 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Avanvero - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3511MH0001820011203924C00		
best focus image:	3511MH0001530001203959R00	3959		motor count:		14018	range (cm):	6.7	
range map product:	3511MH0001530001203960S00	3960		acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	22-Jun-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3511	focus merged on sol:		3511	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3511MH0001820021203925C00	3925	13922	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3511MH0001820021203926C00	3926	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3511MH0001820021203927C00	3927	13970	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3511MH0001820021203928C00	3928	13994	6.88	-0.2	0.2	31.1	0.6	159	4
3511MH0001820021203929C00	3929	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3511MH0001820021203930C00	3930	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	95	6
3511MH0001820021203931C00	3931	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	63	7
3511MH0001820021203932C00	3932	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_September_2022

Sol 3511 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Avanvero - after DRT - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3511MH0007960011203934C00				
best focus image:	3511MH0001530001203957R00	3957	motor count:		15137	range (cm):		2.8	
range map product:	3511MH0001530001203958S00	3958	acquired sequence:		mhli00796		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	22-Jun-22	merge sequence:			mhli00153		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3511		focus merged on sol:		3511
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3511MH0007960021203935C00	3935	14969	3.11	-0.1	0.1	17.8	0.2	255	1
3511MH0007960021203936C00	3936	15011	3.02	-0.1	0.1	17.5	0.2	223	2
3511MH0007960021203937C00	3937	15053	2.93	-0.1	0.1	17.2	0.2	191	3
3511MH0007960021203938C00	3938	15095	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	159	4
3511MH0007960021203939C00	3939	15137	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	127	5
3511MH0007960021203940C00	3940	15179	2.69	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	95	6
3511MH0007960021203941C00	3941	15221	2.61	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	63	7
3511MH0007960021203942C00	3942	15263	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_September_2022

Sol 3511 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Avanvero - after DRT - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3511MH0001820011203944C00				
best focus image:	3511MH0001530001203955R00	3955	motor count:		14004	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3511MH0001530001203956S00	3956	acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	22-Jun-22	merge sequence:			mhli00153		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3511		focus merged on sol:		3511
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3511MH0001820021203945C00	3945	13908	7.49	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	255	1
3511MH0001820021203946C00	3946	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	223	2
3511MH0001820021203947C00	3947	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	191	3
3511MH0001820021203948C00	3948	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	159	4
3511MH0001820021203949C00	3949	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3511MH0001820021203950C00	3950	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3511MH0001820021203951C00	3951	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3511MH0001820021203952C00	3952	14076	6.37	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3530 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3530MH0003060011203976C00				
best focus image:	3530MH0002650001203997R00	3997	motor count:		14113	range (cm):		6.2	
range map product:	3530MH0002650001203998S00	3998	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3530	focus merged on sol:		3530	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3530MH0003060021203977C00	3977	13897	7.57	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	255	1
3530MH0003060021203978C00	3978	13951	7.18	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3530MH0003060021203979C00	3979	14005	6.81	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	191	3
3530MH0003060021203980C00	3980	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	159	4
3530MH0003060021203981C00	3981	14113	6.16	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
3530MH0003060021203982C00	3982	14167	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	95	6
3530MH0003060021203983C00	3983	14221	5.59	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
3530MH0003060021203984C00	3984	14275	5.33	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3530 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3530MH0003060011203986C00				
best focus image:	3530MH0002650001203995R00	3995	motor count:		14109	range (cm):		6.2	
range map product:	3530MH0002650001203996S00	3996	acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	12-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3530	focus merged on sol:		3530	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3530MH0003060021203987C00	3987	13893	7.60	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3530MH0003060021203988C00	3988	13947	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3530MH0003060021203989C00	3989	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	191	3
3530MH0003060021203990C00	3990	14055	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	159	4
3530MH0003060021203991C00	3991	14109	6.18	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
3530MH0003060021203992C00	3992	14163	5.88	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	95	6
3530MH0003060021203993C00	3993	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	63	7
3530MH0003060021203994C00	3994	14271	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3531 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3531MH0001680011204002C00				
best focus image:	3531MH0001930001204035R00	4035	motor count:		14020	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3531MH0001930001204036S00	4036	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	13-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3531	focus merged on sol:		3531	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3531MH0001680021204003C00	4003	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	255	1
3531MH0001680021204004C00	4004	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3531MH0001680021204005C00	4005	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3531MH0001680021204006C00	4006	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3531MH0001680021204007C00	4007	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	127	5
3531MH0001680021204008C00	4008	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3531MH0001680021204009C00	4009	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	63	7
3531MH0001680021204010C00	4010	14074	6.38	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3531 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3531MH0001680011204012C00				
best focus image:	3531MH0001930001204033R00	4033	motor count:		14018	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3531MH0001930001204034S00	4034	acquired sequence:		mhli00168	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	13-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3531	focus merged on sol:		3531	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3531MH0001680021204013C00	4013	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	255	1
3531MH0001680021204014C00	4014	13964	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	223	2
3531MH0001680021204015C00	4015	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3531MH0001680021204016C00	4016	14000	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3531MH0001680021204017C00	4017	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3531MH0001680021204018C00	4018	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6
3531MH0001680021204019C00	4019	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3531MH0001680021204020C00	4020	14072	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3531 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Uai_Uai - ~1 cm standoff								
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3531MH0007430011204022C00			
best focus image:	3531MH0001930001204031R00			4031	motor count:		15190	range (cm):	2.7	
range map product:	3531MH0001930001204032S00			4032	acquired sequence:		mhli00743	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	13-Jul-22				merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		36		acquired on sol:		3531		focus merged on sol:		3531
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8	
				near	far					
3531MH0007430021204023C00	4023	15046	2.94	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	255	1	
3531MH0007430021204024C00	4024	15082	2.87	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	223	2	
3531MH0007430021204025C00	4025	15118	2.80	-0.1	0.1	16.8	0.2	191	3	
3531MH0007430021204026C00	4026	15154	2.73	-0.1	0.1	16.5	0.2	159	4	
3531MH0007430021204027C00	4027	15190	2.67	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5	
3531MH0007430021204028C00	4028	15226	2.60	-0.1	0.1	16.1	0.2	95	6	
3531MH0007430021204029C00	4029	15262	2.54	-0.1	0.1	15.8	0.2	63	7	
3531MH0007430021204030C00	4030	15298	2.48	0.0	0.1	15.6	0.2	31	8	

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Sol 3532 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Seringa - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3532MH0008340011204041C00				
best focus image:	3533MH0001700001204148R00	4148	motor count:		13999	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3533MH0001700001204149S00	4149	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3532	focus merged on sol:		3533	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3532MH0008340031204043C00	4043	13927	7.35	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	255	1
3532MH0008340031204044C00	4044	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3532MH0008340031204045C00	4045	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	191	3
3532MH0008340031204046C00	4046	13981	6.97	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3532MH0008340031204047C00	4047	13999	6.85	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	127	5
3532MH0008340031204048C00	4048	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3532MH0008340031204049C00	4049	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3532MH0008340031204050C00	4050	14053	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3532 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Seringa - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3532MH0008340011204052C00				
best focus image:	3533MH0001700001204146R00	4146	motor count:		14002	range (cm):		6.8	
range map product:	3533MH0001700001204147S00	4147	acquired sequence:		mhli00834	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		18	acquired on sol:		3532	focus merged on sol:		3533	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3532MH0008340031204054C00	4054	13930	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3532MH0008340031204055C00	4055	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	223	2
3532MH0008340031204056C00	4056	13966	7.07	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	191	3
3532MH0008340031204057C00	4057	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	159	4
3532MH0008340031204058C00	4058	14002	6.83	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	127	5
3532MH0008340031204059C00	4059	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	95	6
3532MH0008340031204060C00	4060	14038	6.60	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	63	7
3532MH0008340031204061C00	4061	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3532 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Seringa - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3532MH0008130011204063C00				
best focus image:	3533MH0001700001204144R00	4144	motor count:		14688	range (cm):		3.8	
range map product:	3533MH0001700001204145S00	4145	acquired sequence:		mhli00813	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3532	focus merged on sol:		3533	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3532MH0008130031204065C00	4065	14568	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.6	0.3	255	1
3532MH0008130031204066C00	4066	14598	4.09	-0.1	0.1	21.3	0.3	223	2
3532MH0008130031204067C00	4067	14628	4.00	-0.1	0.1	21.0	0.3	191	3
3532MH0008130031204068C00	4068	14658	3.91	-0.1	0.1	20.7	0.3	159	4
3532MH0008130031204069C00	4069	14688	3.82	-0.1	0.1	20.3	0.3	127	5
3532MH0008130031204070C00	4070	14718	3.73	-0.1	0.1	20.0	0.3	95	6
3532MH0008130031204071C00	4071	14748	3.65	-0.1	0.1	19.7	0.3	63	7
3532MH0008130031204072C00	4072	14778	3.57	-0.1	0.1	19.5	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3532 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3532MH0007230011204077C00				
best focus image:	3533MH0001700001204142R00	4142	motor count:		13896	range (cm):		7.6	
range map product:	3533MH0001700001204143S00	4143	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3532	focus merged on sol:		3533	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3532MH0007230031204079C00	4079	13752	8.81	-0.2	0.2	37.9	0.8	255	1
3532MH0007230031204080C00	4080	13788	8.48	-0.2	0.2	36.7	0.8	223	2
3532MH0007230031204081C00	4081	13824	8.16	-0.2	0.2	35.6	0.7	191	3
3532MH0007230031204082C00	4082	13860	7.86	-0.2	0.2	34.6	0.7	159	4
3532MH0007230031204083C00	4083	13896	7.58	-0.2	0.2	33.6	0.7	127	5
3532MH0007230031204084C00	4084	13932	7.31	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	95	6
3532MH0007230031204085C00	4085	13968	7.06	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	63	7
3532MH0007230031204086C00	4086	14004	6.82	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3532 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - ~55 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3532MH0007230011204088C00				
best focus image:	3533MH0001700001204140R00	4140	motor count:		13912	range (cm):		7.5	
range map product:	3533MH0001700001204140R00	4141	acquired sequence:		mhli00723	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3532	focus merged on sol:		3533	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3532MH0007230031204090C00	4090	13768	8.66	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	255	1
3532MH0007230031204091C00	4091	13804	8.33	-0.2	0.2	36.2	0.8	223	2
3532MH0007230031204092C00	4092	13840	8.03	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	191	3
3532MH0007230031204093C00	4093	13876	7.74	-0.2	0.2	34.1	0.7	159	4
3532MH0007230031204094C00	4094	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	127	5
3532MH0007230031204095C00	4095	13948	7.20	-0.2	0.2	32.2	0.6	95	6
3532MH0007230031204096C00	4096	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	63	7
3532MH0007230031204097C00	4097	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	31	8

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Sol 3532 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target La_Manare - ~25 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3532MH0008000011204099C00				
best focus image:	3533MH0001700001204138R00	4138	motor count:		14459	range (cm):		4.6	
range map product:	3533MH0001700001204139S00	4139	acquired sequence:		mhli00800	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3532	focus merged on sol:		3533	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3532MH0008000031204101C00	4101	14243	5.48	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	255	1
3532MH0008000031204102C00	4102	14297	5.23	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	223	2
3532MH0008000031204103C00	4103	14351	5.00	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	191	3
3532MH0008000031204104C00	4104	14405	4.78	-0.1	0.1	23.7	0.3	159	4
3532MH0008000031204105C00	4105	14459	4.57	-0.1	0.1	23.0	0.3	127	5
3532MH0008000031204106C00	4106	14513	4.38	-0.1	0.1	22.3	0.3	95	6
3532MH0008000031204107C00	4107	14567	4.19	-0.1	0.1	21.7	0.3	63	7
3532MH0008000031204108C00	4108	14621	4.02	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3532 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Caruai - stereo-1 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3532MH0007090011204113C00				
best focus image:	3533MH0001700001204136R00	4136	motor count:		14255	range (cm):		5.4	
range map product:	3533MH0001700001204137S00	4137	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jul-22	merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3532	focus merged on sol:		3533	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3532MH0007090031204115C00	4115	14063	6.45	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	255	1
3532MH0007090031204116C00	4116	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	223	2
3532MH0007090031204117C00	4117	14159	5.91	-0.1	0.1	27.7	0.4	191	3
3532MH0007090031204118C00	4118	14207	5.66	-0.1	0.1	26.8	0.4	159	4
3532MH0007090031204119C00	4119	14255	5.42	-0.1	0.1	26.0	0.4	127	5
3532MH0007090031204120C00	4120	14303	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.2	0.4	95	6
3532MH0007090031204121C00	4121	14351	5.00	-0.1	0.1	24.5	0.4	63	7
3532MH0007090031204122C00	4122	14399	4.80	-0.1	0.1	23.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3532 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Caruai - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3532MH0007090011204124C00				
best focus image:	3533MH0001700001204134R00	4134	motor count:		14244	range (cm):		5.5	
range map product:	3533MH0001700001204135S00	4135	acquired sequence:		mhli00709	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	14-Jul-22	merge sequence:		mhli00170	merge type:		Basic		
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3532	focus merged on sol:		3533	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3532MH0007090031204126C00	4126	14052	6.51	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	255	1
3532MH0007090031204127C00	4127	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	223	2
3532MH0007090031204128C00	4128	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	191	3
3532MH0007090031204129C00	4129	14196	5.71	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	159	4
3532MH0007090031204130C00	4130	14244	5.48	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	127	5
3532MH0007090031204131C00	4131	14292	5.25	-0.1	0.1	25.4	0.4	95	6
3532MH0007090031204132C00	4132	14340	5.04	-0.1	0.1	24.7	0.4	63	7
3532MH0007090031204133C00	4133	14388	4.85	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Monte_Caburai- APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0002990011204153C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204275R00	4275	motor count:		13982	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204276S00	4276	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0002990021204154C00	4154	13838	8.04	-0.2	0.2	35.2	0.7	255	1
3534MH0002990021204155C00	4155	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	223	2
3534MH0002990021204156C00	4156	13910	7.47	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	191	3
3534MH0002990021204157C00	4157	13946	7.21	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	159	4
3534MH0002990021204158C00	4158	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
3534MH0002990021204159C00	4159	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	95	6
3534MH0002990021204160C00	4160	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	63	7
3534MH0002990021204161C00	4161	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Monte_Caburai- APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0002990011204163C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204273R00	4273	motor count:		13978	range (cm):		7.0	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204274S00	4274	acquired sequence:		mhli00299	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0002990021204164C00	4164	13834	8.08	-0.2	0.2	35.3	0.7	255	1
3534MH0002990021204165C00	4165	13870	7.78	-0.2	0.2	34.3	0.7	223	2
3534MH0002990021204166C00	4166	13906	7.50	-0.2	0.2	33.3	0.7	191	3
3534MH0002990021204167C00	4167	13942	7.24	-0.2	0.2	32.4	0.6	159	4
3534MH0002990021204168C00	4168	13978	6.99	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5
3534MH0002990021204169C00	4169	14014	6.75	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3534MH0002990021204170C00	4170	14050	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	63	7
3534MH0002990021204171C00	4171	14086	6.31	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Monte_Caburai - APXS spot 2 - ~1 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0004190011204173C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204271R00	4271	motor count:		15026	range (cm):		3.0	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204272S00	4272	acquired sequence:		mhli00419		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		72	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0004190021204174C00	4174	14738	3.68	-0.1	0.1	19.8	0.3	255	1
3534MH0004190021204175C00	4175	14810	3.48	-0.1	0.1	19.2	0.3	223	2
3534MH0004190021204176C00	4176	14882	3.31	-0.1	0.1	18.5	0.2	191	3
3534MH0004190021204177C00	4177	14954	3.14	-0.1	0.1	18.0	0.2	159	4
3534MH0004190021204178C00	4178	15026	2.98	-0.1	0.1	17.4	0.2	127	5
3534MH0004190021204179C00	4179	15098	2.84	-0.1	0.1	16.9	0.2	95	6
3534MH0004190021204180C00	4180	15170	2.70	-0.1	0.1	16.4	0.2	63	7
3534MH0004190021204181C00	4181	15242	2.57	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Monte_Caburai - APXS spot 1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0002990011204183C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204269R00	4269	motor count:		13992	range (cm):		6.9	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204270S00	4270	acquired sequence:		mhli00299		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		36	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0002990021204184C00	4184	13848	7.96	-0.2	0.2	34.9	0.7	255	1
3534MH0002990021204185C00	4185	13884	7.67	-0.2	0.2	33.9	0.7	223	2
3534MH0002990021204186C00	4186	13920	7.40	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	191	3
3534MH0002990021204187C00	4187	13956	7.14	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	159	4
3534MH0002990021204188C00	4188	13992	6.90	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	127	5
3534MH0002990021204189C00	4189	14028	6.66	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	95	6
3534MH0002990021204190C00	4190	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3534MH0002990021204191C00	4191	14100	6.23	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 1 of 6 - ~31 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0008530011204193C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204267R00	4267	motor count:		12927	range (cm):		33.3	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204268S00	4268	acquired sequence:		mhli00853	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0008530021204194C00	4194	12711	78.38	-13.7	21.5	282.8	61.9	255	1
3534MH0008530021204195C00	4195	12765	58.95	-8.1	11.3	214.4	34.0	223	2
3534MH0008530021204196C00	4196	12819	47.07	-5.3	6.8	172.6	21.4	191	3
3534MH0008530021204197C00	4197	12873	39.05	-3.7	4.6	144.4	14.6	159	4
3534MH0008530021204198C00	4198	12927	33.26	-2.7	3.2	124.0	10.5	127	5
3534MH0008530021204199C00	4199	12981	28.89	-2.1	2.4	108.6	7.9	95	6
3534MH0008530021204200C00	4200	13035	25.47	-1.6	1.8	96.5	6.1	63	7
3534MH0008530021204201C00	4201	13089	22.71	-1.3	1.4	86.9	4.9	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 2 of 6 - ~21 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0008530011204203C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204265R00	4265	motor count:		13087	range (cm):		22.8	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204266S00	4266	acquired sequence:		mhli00853	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0008530021204204C00	4204	12871	39.30	-3.8	4.6	145.2	14.7	255	1
3534MH0008530021204205C00	4205	12925	33.45	-2.8	3.3	124.6	10.6	223	2
3534MH0008530021204206C00	4206	12979	29.03	-2.1	2.4	109.1	8.0	191	3
3534MH0008530021204207C00	4207	13033	25.58	-1.7	1.9	96.9	6.2	159	4
3534MH0008530021204208C00	4208	13087	22.81	-1.3	1.5	87.2	4.9	127	5
3534MH0008530021204209C00	4209	13141	20.53	-1.1	1.2	79.2	4.0	95	6
3534MH0008530021204210C00	4210	13195	18.62	-0.9	1.0	72.4	3.3	63	7
3534MH0008530021204211C00	4211	13249	17.00	-0.8	0.8	66.8	2.8	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 3 of 6 - ~18 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0008530011204213C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204263R00	4263	motor count:		13151	range (cm):		20.1	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204264S00	4264	acquired sequence:		mhli00853		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0008530021204214C00	4214	12935	32.54	-2.6	3.1	121.4	10.0	255	1
3534MH0008530021204215C00	4215	12989	28.33	-2.0	2.3	106.6	7.6	223	2
3534MH0008530021204216C00	4216	13043	25.02	-1.6	1.8	95.0	5.9	191	3
3534MH0008530021204217C00	4217	13097	22.35	-1.3	1.4	85.6	4.7	159	4
3534MH0008530021204218C00	4218	13151	20.15	-1.1	1.1	77.8	3.8	127	5
3534MH0008530021204219C00	4219	13205	18.30	-0.9	0.9	71.3	3.2	95	6
3534MH0008530021204220C00	4220	13259	16.73	-0.7	0.8	65.8	2.7	63	7
3534MH0008530021204221C00	4221	13313	15.37	-0.6	0.7	61.0	2.3	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 4 of 6 - ~17 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0008530011204223C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204261R00	4261	motor count:		13171	range (cm):		19.4	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204262S00	4262	acquired sequence:		mhli00853		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0008530021204224C00	4224	12955	30.85	-2.4	2.8	115.5	9.0	255	1
3534MH0008530021204225C00	4225	13009	27.02	-1.8	2.1	102.0	6.9	223	2
3534MH0008530021204226C00	4226	13063	23.97	-1.5	1.6	91.3	5.4	191	3
3534MH0008530021204227C00	4227	13117	21.49	-1.2	1.3	82.5	4.4	159	4
3534MH0008530021204228C00	4228	13171	19.43	-1.0	1.0	75.3	3.6	127	5
3534MH0008530021204229C00	4229	13225	17.69	-0.8	0.9	69.2	3.0	95	6
3534MH0008530021204230C00	4230	13279	16.20	-0.7	0.7	63.9	2.5	63	7
3534MH0008530021204231C00	4231	13333	14.92	-0.6	0.6	59.4	2.1	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 5 of 6 - ~23 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0008530011204233C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204259R00	4259	motor count:		13039	range (cm):		25.2	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204260S00	4260	acquired sequence:		mhli00853		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0008530021204234C00	4234	12823	46.37	-5.1	6.6	170.1	20.7	255	1
3534MH0008530021204235C00	4235	12877	38.56	-3.6	4.4	142.6	14.2	223	2
3534MH0008530021204236C00	4236	12931	32.90	-2.7	3.2	122.7	10.3	191	3
3534MH0008530021204237C00	4237	12985	28.61	-2.1	2.3	107.6	7.7	159	4
3534MH0008530021204238C00	4238	13039	25.24	-1.6	1.8	95.8	6.0	127	5
3534MH0008530021204239C00	4239	13093	22.53	-1.3	1.4	86.2	4.8	95	6
3534MH0008530021204240C00	4240	13147	20.30	-1.1	1.1	78.4	3.9	63	7
3534MH0008530021204241C00	4241	13201	18.43	-0.9	0.9	71.8	3.2	31	8

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Sol 3534 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 6 of 6 - ~25 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3534MH0008530011204243C00				
best focus image:	3536MH0003690001204257R00	4257	motor count:		13005	range (cm):		27.3	
range map product:	3536MH0003690001204258S00	4258	acquired sequence:		mhli00853		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	16-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00369		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		54	acquired on sol:		3534	focus merged on sol:		3536	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3534MH0008530021204244C00	4244	12789	53.04	-6.6	8.9	193.6	27.3	255	1
3534MH0008530021204245C00	4245	12843	43.15	-4.5	5.7	158.8	17.9	223	2
3534MH0008530021204246C00	4246	12897	36.26	-3.2	3.9	134.5	12.5	191	3
3534MH0008530021204247C00	4247	12951	31.18	-2.4	2.8	116.6	9.2	159	4
3534MH0008530021204248C00	4248	13005	27.27	-1.9	2.1	102.9	7.0	127	5
3534MH0008530021204249C00	4249	13059	24.17	-1.5	1.6	92.0	5.5	95	6
3534MH0008530021204250C00	4250	13113	21.66	-1.2	1.3	83.1	4.4	63	7
3534MH0008530021204251C00	4251	13167	19.57	-1.0	1.1	75.8	3.6	31	8

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Sol 3537 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3537MH0001820011204280C00				
best focus image:	3537MH0002650001204301R00	4301	motor count:		14192	range (cm):		5.7	
range map product:	3537MH0002650001204302S00	4302	acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	19-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3537	focus merged on sol:		3537	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3537MH0001820021204281C00	4281	14096	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	255	1
3537MH0001820021204282C00	4282	14120	6.12	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	223	2
3537MH0001820021204283C00	4283	14144	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	191	3
3537MH0001820021204284C00	4284	14168	5.86	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	159	4
3537MH0001820021204285C00	4285	14192	5.73	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	127	5
3537MH0001820021204286C00	4286	14216	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.7	0.4	95	6
3537MH0001820021204287C00	4287	14240	5.50	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	63	7
3537MH0001820021204288C00	4288	14264	5.38	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3537 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3537MH0001820011204290C00				
best focus image:	3537MH0002650001204299R00	4299	motor count:		14194	range (cm):		5.7	
range map product:	3537MH0002650001204300S00	4300	acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	19-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00265		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3537	focus merged on sol:		3537	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3537MH0001820021204291C00	4291	14098	6.24	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	255	1
3537MH0001820021204292C00	4292	14122	6.11	-0.1	0.1	28.4	0.5	223	2
3537MH0001820021204293C00	4293	14146	5.97	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	191	3
3537MH0001820021204294C00	4294	14170	5.85	-0.1	0.1	27.5	0.4	159	4
3537MH0001820021204295C00	4295	14194	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	127	5
3537MH0001820021204296C00	4296	14218	5.60	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	95	6
3537MH0001820021204297C00	4297	14242	5.49	-0.1	0.1	26.2	0.4	63	7
3537MH0001820021204298C00	4298	14266	5.37	-0.1	0.1	25.8	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3539 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Surama - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3539MH0003060011204306C00					
best focus image:		3540MH0001530001204354R00		4354		motor count:		13980		range (cm):	7.0
range map product:		3540MH0001530001204355S00		4355		acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative
acquired on date:		21-Jul-22				merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54		acquired on sol:		3539		focus merged on sol:		3540	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3539MH0003060021204307C00	4307	13764	8.70	-0.2	0.2	37.5	0.8	255	1		
3539MH0003060021204308C00	4308	13818	8.21	-0.2	0.2	35.8	0.8	223	2		
3539MH0003060021204309C00	4309	13872	7.77	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3		
3539MH0003060021204310C00	4310	13926	7.36	-0.2	0.2	32.8	0.6	159	4		
3539MH0003060021204311C00	4311	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	127	5		
3539MH0003060021204312C00	4312	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	95	6		
3539MH0003060021204313C00	4313	14088	6.30	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	63	7		
3539MH0003060021204314C00	4314	14142	6.00	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	31	8		

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Sol 3539 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Surama - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff									
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3539MH0003060011204316C00					
best focus image:		3540MH0001530001204352R00		4352		motor count:		13982		range (cm):	7.0
range map product:		3540MH0001530001204353S00		4353		acquired sequence:		mhli00306	stack type:		Relative
acquired on date:		21-Jul-22				merge sequence:		mhli00153	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		54		acquired on sol:		3539		focus merged on sol:		3540	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8		
				near	far						
3539MH0003060021204317C00	4317	13766	8.68	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	255	1		
3539MH0003060021204318C00	4318	13820	8.19	-0.2	0.2	35.7	0.7	223	2		
3539MH0003060021204319C00	4319	13874	7.75	-0.2	0.2	34.2	0.7	191	3		
3539MH0003060021204320C00	4320	13928	7.34	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	159	4		
3539MH0003060021204321C00	4321	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5		
3539MH0003060021204322C00	4322	14036	6.61	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.5	95	6		
3539MH0003060021204323C00	4323	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	63	7		
3539MH0003060021204324C00	4324	14144	5.99	-0.1	0.1	28.0	0.5	31	8		

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Sol 3539 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Amajari - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3539MH0001820011204328C00			
best focus image:	3540MH0001530001204350R00	4350	motor count:		14106	range (cm):		6.2	
range map product:	3540MH0001530001204351S00	4351	acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3539	focus merged on sol:		3540	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3539MH0001820021204329C00	4329	14010	6.78	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	255	1
3539MH0001820021204330C00	4330	14034	6.63	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	223	2
3539MH0001820021204331C00	4331	14058	6.48	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	191	3
3539MH0001820021204332C00	4332	14082	6.33	-0.2	0.1	29.2	0.5	159	4
3539MH0001820021204333C00	4333	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	127	5
3539MH0001820021204334C00	4334	14130	6.06	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	95	6
3539MH0001820021204335C00	4335	14154	5.93	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	63	7
3539MH0001820021204336C00	4336	14178	5.81	-0.1	0.1	27.3	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3539 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Amajari - stereo-2 - ~45 mm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3539MH0001820011204338C00			
best focus image:	3540MH0001530001204348R00	4348	motor count:		14114	range (cm):		6.2	
range map product:	3540MH0001530001204349S00	4349	acquired sequence:		mhli00182		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	21-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00153		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3539	focus merged on sol:		3540	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3539MH0001820021204339C00	4339	14018	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	255	1
3539MH0001820021204340C00	4340	14042	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.0	0.5	223	2
3539MH0001820021204341C00	4341	14066	6.43	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	191	3
3539MH0001820021204342C00	4342	14090	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.0	0.5	159	4
3539MH0001820021204343C00	4343	14114	6.15	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	127	5
3539MH0001820021204344C00	4344	14138	6.02	-0.1	0.1	28.1	0.5	95	6
3539MH0001820021204345C00	4345	14162	5.89	-0.1	0.1	27.6	0.4	63	7
3539MH0001820021204346C00	4346	14186	5.76	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	31	8

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Sol 3541 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Benhuri_Bumoko - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3541MH0001820011204359C00				
best focus image:	3543MH0001630001204432R00	4432	motor count:		13984	range (cm):	7.0		
range map product:	3543MH0001630001204433S00	4433	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	23-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3541	focus merged on sol:		3543	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3541MH0001820021204360C00	4360	13888	7.64	-0.2	0.2	33.8	0.7	255	1
3541MH0001820021204361C00	4361	13912	7.46	-0.2	0.2	33.2	0.7	223	2
3541MH0001820021204362C00	4362	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3541MH0001820021204363C00	4363	13960	7.11	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3541MH0001820021204364C00	4364	13984	6.95	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	127	5
3541MH0001820021204365C00	4365	14008	6.79	-0.2	0.2	30.8	0.6	95	6
3541MH0001820021204366C00	4366	14032	6.64	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	63	7
3541MH0001820021204367C00	4367	14056	6.49	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3541 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Benhuri_Bumoko - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3541MH0001820011204369C00				
best focus image:	3543MH0001630001204430R00	4430	motor count:		13987	range (cm):	6.9		
range map product:	3543MH0001630001204431S00	4431	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:	Relative		
acquired on date:	23-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3541	focus merged on sol:		3543	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3541MH0001820021204370C00	4370	13891	7.62	-0.2	0.2	33.7	0.7	255	1
3541MH0001820021204371C00	4371	13915	7.44	-0.2	0.2	33.1	0.6	223	2
3541MH0001820021204372C00	4372	13939	7.26	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3541MH0001820021204373C00	4373	13963	7.09	-0.2	0.2	31.9	0.6	159	4
3541MH0001820021204374C00	4374	13987	6.93	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	127	5
3541MH0001820021204375C00	4375	14011	6.77	-0.2	0.2	30.7	0.6	95	6
3541MH0001820021204376C00	4376	14035	6.62	-0.2	0.2	30.2	0.6	63	7
3541MH0001820021204377C00	4377	14059	6.47	-0.2	0.1	29.7	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3541 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Benhori_Bumoko - ~2 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3541MH0003020011204379C00			
best focus image:	3543MH0001630001204428R00	4428	motor count:		14642	range (cm):		4.0	
range map product:	3543MH0001630001204429S00	4429	acquired sequence:		mhli00302	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3541	focus merged on sol:		3543	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3541MH0003020021204380C00	4380	14522	4.35	-0.1	0.1	22.2	0.3	255	1
3541MH0003020021204381C00	4381	14552	4.24	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	223	2
3541MH0003020021204382C00	4382	14582	4.14	-0.1	0.1	21.5	0.3	191	3
3541MH0003020021204383C00	4383	14612	4.05	-0.1	0.1	21.2	0.3	159	4
3541MH0003020021204384C00	4384	14642	3.96	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	127	5
3541MH0003020021204385C00	4385	14672	3.87	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	95	6
3541MH0003020021204386C00	4386	14702	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	63	7
3541MH0003020021204387C00	4387	14732	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	31	8

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Sol 3541 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Motocuruna - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff								
			CDPID	corresponding frame:		3541MH0001820011204393C00			
best focus image:	3543MH0001630001204426R00	4426	motor count:		14017	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3543MH0001630001204427S00	4427	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3541	focus merged on sol:		3543	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3541MH0001820021204394C00	4394	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3541MH0001820021204395C00	4395	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3541MH0001820021204396C00	4396	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3541MH0001820021204397C00	4397	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3541MH0001820021204398C00	4398	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3541MH0001820021204399C00	4399	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3541MH0001820021204400C00	4400	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3541MH0001820021204401C00	4401	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

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Sol 3541 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Motocuruna - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3541MH0001820011204403C00				
best focus image:	3543MH0001630001204424R00	4424	motor count:		14017	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3543MH0001630001204425S00	4425	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3541	focus merged on sol:		3543	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3541MH0001820021204404C00	4404	13921	7.39	-0.2	0.2	32.9	0.6	255	1
3541MH0001820021204405C00	4405	13945	7.22	-0.2	0.2	32.3	0.6	223	2
3541MH0001820021204406C00	4406	13969	7.05	-0.2	0.2	31.7	0.6	191	3
3541MH0001820021204407C00	4407	13993	6.89	-0.2	0.2	31.2	0.6	159	4
3541MH0001820021204408C00	4408	14017	6.73	-0.2	0.2	30.6	0.6	127	5
3541MH0001820021204409C00	4409	14041	6.58	-0.2	0.2	30.1	0.5	95	6
3541MH0001820021204410C00	4410	14065	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	63	7
3541MH0001820021204411C00	4411	14089	6.29	-0.1	0.1	29.1	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3541 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

	target Motocuruna - after DRT - ~2 cm standoff								
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3541MH0003020011204413C00				
best focus image:	3543MH0001630001204422R00	4422	motor count:		14733	range (cm):		3.7	
range map product:	3543MH0001630001204423S00	4423	acquired sequence:		mhli00302	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	23-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00163	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		30	acquired on sol:		3541	focus merged on sol:		3543	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3541MH0003020021204414C00	4414	14613	4.05	-0.1	0.1	21.1	0.3	255	1
3541MH0003020021204415C00	4415	14643	3.95	-0.1	0.1	20.8	0.3	223	2
3541MH0003020021204416C00	4416	14673	3.86	-0.1	0.1	20.5	0.3	191	3
3541MH0003020021204417C00	4417	14703	3.78	-0.1	0.1	20.2	0.3	159	4
3541MH0003020021204418C00	4418	14733	3.69	-0.1	0.1	19.9	0.3	127	5
3541MH0003020021204419C00	4419	14763	3.61	-0.1	0.1	19.6	0.3	95	6
3541MH0003020021204420C00	4420	14793	3.53	-0.1	0.1	19.3	0.3	63	7
3541MH0003020021204421C00	4421	14823	3.45	-0.1	0.1	19.1	0.2	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3544 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tumereng - ~25 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3544MH0006280011204435C00				
best focus image:	3544MH0001930001204468R00	4468	motor count:		13018	range (cm):		26.5	
range map product:	3544MH0001930001204469S00	4469	acquired sequence:		mhli00628	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3544	focus merged on sol:		3544	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3544MH0006280021204436C00	4436	12850	42.12	-4.3	5.4	155.2	17.0	255	1
3544MH0006280021204437C00	4437	12892	36.81	-3.3	4.0	136.5	12.9	223	2
3544MH0006280021204438C00	4438	12934	32.63	-2.6	3.1	121.8	10.1	191	3
3544MH0006280021204439C00	4439	12976	29.25	-2.1	2.5	109.9	8.1	159	4
3544MH0006280021204440C00	4440	13018	26.46	-1.8	2.0	100.0	6.6	127	5
3544MH0006280021204441C00	4441	13060	24.12	-1.5	1.6	91.8	5.5	95	6
3544MH0006280021204442C00	4442	13102	22.13	-1.3	1.4	84.8	4.6	63	7
3544MH0006280021204443C00	4443	13144	20.41	-1.1	1.2	78.8	3.9	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3544 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tumereng - stereo-1 - ~45 mm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3544MH0006730011204445C00				
best focus image:	3544MH0001930001204466R00	4466	motor count:		14104	range (cm):		6.2	
range map product:	3544MH0001930001204467S00	4467	acquired sequence:		mhli00673	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	26-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00193	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		84	acquired on sol:		3544	focus merged on sol:		3544	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3544MH0006730021204446C00	4446	13768	8.66	-0.2	0.2	37.4	0.8	255	1
3544MH0006730021204447C00	4447	13852	7.93	-0.2	0.2	34.8	0.7	223	2
3544MH0006730021204448C00	4448	13936	7.28	-0.2	0.2	32.5	0.6	191	3
3544MH0006730021204449C00	4449	14020	6.71	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	159	4
3544MH0006730021204450C00	4450	14104	6.21	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	127	5
3544MH0006730021204451C00	4451	14188	5.75	-0.1	0.1	27.2	0.4	95	6
3544MH0006730021204452C00	4452	14272	5.35	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	63	7
3544MH0006730021204453C00	4453	14356	4.98	-0.1	0.1	24.4	0.4	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3544 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Tumereng - stereo-2 - ~35 mm standoff										
		CDPID		corresponding frame:		3544MH0006730011204455C00						
best focus image:		3544MH0001930001204464R00		4464		motor count:		14301		range (cm): 5.2		
range map product:		3544MH0001930001204465S00		4465		acquired sequence:		mhli00673		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:		26-Jul-22				merge sequence:		mhli00193		merge type: Basic		
motor count interval:			84		acquired on sol:		3544		focus merged on sol:		3544	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8			
				near	far							
3544MH0006730021204456C00	4456	13965	7.08	-0.2	0.2	31.8	0.6	255	1			
3544MH0006730021204457C00	4457	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	223	2			
3544MH0006730021204458C00	4458	14133	6.05	-0.1	0.1	28.2	0.5	191	3			
3544MH0006730021204459C00	4459	14217	5.61	-0.1	0.1	26.6	0.4	159	4			
3544MH0006730021204460C00	4460	14301	5.21	-0.1	0.1	25.3	0.4	127	5			
3544MH0006730021204461C00	4461	14385	4.86	-0.1	0.1	24.0	0.4	95	6			
3544MH0006730021204462C00	4462	14469	4.53	-0.1	0.1	22.9	0.3	63	7			
3544MH0006730021204463C00	4463	14553	4.24	-0.1	0.1	21.8	0.3	31	8			

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3546 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Simoni - stereo-1 - ~4 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3546MH0002240011204474C00		
best focus image:	3547MH0002270001204534R00	4534		motor count:		14153	range (cm):	5.9	
range map product:	3547MH0002270001204535S00	4535		acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3546	focus merged on sol:		3547	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3546MH0002240021204475C00	4475	13985	6.94	-0.2	0.2	31.3	0.6	255	1
3546MH0002240021204476C00	4476	14027	6.67	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	223	2
3546MH0002240021204477C00	4477	14069	6.41	-0.2	0.1	29.5	0.5	191	3
3546MH0002240021204478C00	4478	14111	6.17	-0.1	0.1	28.6	0.5	159	4
3546MH0002240021204479C00	4479	14153	5.94	-0.1	0.1	27.8	0.5	127	5
3546MH0002240021204480C00	4480	14195	5.72	-0.1	0.1	27.0	0.4	95	6
3546MH0002240021204481C00	4481	14237	5.51	-0.1	0.1	26.3	0.4	63	7
3546MH0002240021204482C00	4482	14279	5.31	-0.1	0.1	25.6	0.4	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3546 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Simoni - stereo-2 - ~4 cm standoff							
				CDPID	corresponding frame:		3546MH0002240011204484C00		
best focus image:	3547MH0002270001204532R00	4532		motor count:		14148	range (cm):	6.0	
range map product:	3547MH0002270001204533S00	4533		acquired sequence:		mhli00224	stack type:	Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:	Basic	
motor count interval:		42	acquired on sol:		3546	focus merged on sol:		3547	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3546MH0002240021204485C00	4485	13980	6.98	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	255	1
3546MH0002240021204486C00	4486	14022	6.70	-0.2	0.2	30.5	0.6	223	2
3546MH0002240021204487C00	4487	14064	6.44	-0.2	0.1	29.6	0.5	191	3
3546MH0002240021204488C00	4488	14106	6.20	-0.1	0.1	28.7	0.5	159	4
3546MH0002240021204489C00	4489	14148	5.96	-0.1	0.1	27.9	0.5	127	5
3546MH0002240021204490C00	4490	14190	5.74	-0.1	0.1	27.1	0.4	95	6
3546MH0002240021204491C00	4491	14232	5.53	-0.1	0.1	26.4	0.4	63	7
3546MH0002240021204492C00	4492	14274	5.34	-0.1	0.1	25.7	0.4	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3546 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Lilas - after DRT - stereo-1 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3546MH0001820011204497C00				
best focus image:	3547MH0002270001204530R00	4530	motor count:		14025	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3547MH0002270001204531S00	4531	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3546	focus merged on sol:		3547	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3546MH0001820021204498C00	4498	13929	7.33	-0.2	0.2	32.7	0.6	255	1
3546MH0001820021204499C00	4499	13953	7.16	-0.2	0.2	32.1	0.6	223	2
3546MH0001820021204500C00	4500	13977	7.00	-0.2	0.2	31.5	0.6	191	3
3546MH0001820021204501C00	4501	14001	6.84	-0.2	0.2	31.0	0.6	159	4
3546MH0001820021204502C00	4502	14025	6.68	-0.2	0.2	30.4	0.6	127	5
3546MH0001820021204503C00	4503	14049	6.53	-0.2	0.1	29.9	0.5	95	6
3546MH0001820021204504C00	4504	14073	6.39	-0.2	0.1	29.4	0.5	63	7
3546MH0001820021204505C00	4505	14097	6.25	-0.1	0.1	28.9	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3546 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Lilas - after DRT - stereo-2 - ~5 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3546MH0001820011204507C00				
best focus image:	3547MH0002270001204528R00	4528	motor count:		14030	range (cm):		6.7	
range map product:	3547MH0002270001204529S00	4529	acquired sequence:		mhli00182	stack type:		Relative	
acquired on date:	28-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227	merge type:		Basic
motor count interval:		24	acquired on sol:		3546	focus merged on sol:		3547	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3546MH0001820021204508C00	4508	13934	7.30	-0.2	0.2	32.6	0.6	255	1
3546MH0001820021204509C00	4509	13958	7.13	-0.2	0.2	32.0	0.6	223	2
3546MH0001820021204510C00	4510	13982	6.96	-0.2	0.2	31.4	0.6	191	3
3546MH0001820021204511C00	4511	14006	6.80	-0.2	0.2	30.9	0.6	159	4
3546MH0001820021204512C00	4512	14030	6.65	-0.2	0.2	30.3	0.6	127	5
3546MH0001820021204513C00	4513	14054	6.50	-0.2	0.1	29.8	0.5	95	6
3546MH0001820021204514C00	4514	14078	6.36	-0.2	0.1	29.3	0.5	63	7
3546MH0001820021204515C00	4515	14102	6.22	-0.1	0.1	28.8	0.5	31	8

updated: 13_December_2022

Sol 3546 - MAHLI Onboard Focus Merge Product Information

		target Lilas - after DRT - ~1 cm standoff							
		CDPID	corresponding frame:		3546MH0004260011204517C00				
best focus image:	3547MH0002270001204526R00	4526	motor count:		15184	range (cm):		2.7	
range map product:	3547MH0002270001204527S00	4527	acquired sequence:		mhli00426		stack type: Relative		
acquired on date:	28-Jul-22			merge sequence:		mhli00227		merge type: Basic	
motor count interval:		48	acquired on sol:		3546	focus merged on sol:		3547	
Individual Focus Stack Images	CDPID	motor count	range (cm)	range uncertainty (cm)		pixel scale (µm/pixel)	pixel scale uncertainty (µm/pixel)	DN in range map	image n of 8
				near	far				
3546MH0004260021204518C00	4518	14992	3.06	-0.1	0.1	17.7	0.2	255	1
3546MH0004260021204519C00	4519	15040	2.95	-0.1	0.1	17.3	0.2	223	2
3546MH0004260021204520C00	4520	15088	2.86	-0.1	0.1	17.0	0.2	191	3
3546MH0004260021204521C00	4521	15136	2.76	-0.1	0.1	16.6	0.2	159	4
3546MH0004260021204522C00	4522	15184	2.68	-0.1	0.1	16.3	0.2	127	5
3546MH0004260021204523C00	4523	15232	2.59	-0.1	0.1	16.0	0.2	95	6
3546MH0004260021204524C00	4524	15280	2.51	0.0	0.1	15.7	0.2	63	7
3546MH0004260021204525C00	4525	15328	2.43	0.0	0.1	15.5	0.2	31	8

6 Image comment, purpose, RATIONALE_DESC

A RATIONALE_DESC accompanies each MAHLI image and each focus merge product archived with the NASA PDS. It is found in in each archived image label file (.LBL).

The RATIONALE_DESC is a text description of the purpose (rationale) behind the acquisition of each MAHLI parent image.

For onboard focus merge products, the RATIONALE_DESC includes information regarding when the merge was performed and which parent images were merged. This information is not automatically tracked by the instrument or ground data system and thus requires human intervention; this is the only pathway by which this information is conveyed to the data user through the NASA PDS archival products.

The MAHLI Team drafts each RATIONALE_DESC as the data are acquired and returned to Earth. Final editing of each RATIONALE_DESC is performed a few months before the data are archived with the NASA PDS. In some cases, an error might be detected in a RATIONALE_DESC some time after the data are first archived; in such a case, the corrections are made in a later release of MAHLI data to the PDS (as long as the mission continues and funding is available to do so).

The pages that follow capture the RATIONALE_DESC for each MAHLI image acquired and lists the ID for the best available image or focus merge product returned to Earth. Note that the RATIONALE_DESC also applies to any other child images spawned by a given parent image and thus there might be additional images, not listed here, that correspond to a given RATIONALE_DESC. In some cases, it was only necessary to return a thumbnail image; the IDs for these are given in orange text. As noted earlier, purple text indicates Image IDs for which the last two characters might differ from those in the NASA PDS archives.

Note that the text on the pages that follow is tiny. We highly recommend that the reader view this document electronically (*i.e.*, PDF file on a computer screen) and magnify the view $\geq 400\%$.

The *MAHLI Image Comment Sheets* that follow include data acquired Sol 3424–3547. During this period, the instrument obtained images and/or performed focus merges on **Sols 3424, 3425, 3427, 3428, 3429, 3432, 3433, 3436, 3439, 3440, 3442, 3444, 3447, 3449, 3451, 3453, 3454, 3456, 3458, 3459, 3461, 3462, 3465, 3466, 3469, 3471, 3472, 3473, 3474, 3476, 3478, 3480, 3481, 3483, 3485, 3488, 3491, 3492, 3493, 3503, 3505, 3508, 3511, 3512, 3528, 3530, 3531, 3532, 3533, 3534, 3535, 3536, 3537, 3539, 3540, 3541, 3543, 3544, 3546, 3547.**

updated: 25_March_2022

Sol 3424 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Mar-22	
camera position	0	Image ID:
total parent images	0	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed	5	CDPID:
total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
total parent images + focus merge products	10	

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3423 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3424MH0002270001201618R00	1618	target Breakyneck - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1610-1617 - best focus image product
		3424MH0002270001201619S00	1619	target Breakyneck - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1610-1617 - range map product
		3424MH0002270001201620R00	1620	target Breakyneck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1600-1607 - best focus image product
		3424MH0002270001201621S00	1621	target Breakyneck - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1600-1607 - range map product
		3424MH0002270001201622R00	1622	target Breakyneck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1590-1597 - best focus image product
		3424MH0002270001201623S00	1623	target Breakyneck - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1590-1597 - range map product
		3424MH0002270001201624R00	1624	target Redscarhead - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1580-1587 - best focus image product
		3424MH0002270001201625S00	1625	target Redscarhead - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1580-1587 - range map product
		3424MH0002270001201626R00	1626	target Redscarhead - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1570-1577 - best focus image product
		3424MH0002270001201627S00	1627	target Redscarhead - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3423 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1570-1577 - range map product

updated: 06_June_2022

Sol 3425 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Mar-22
camera position	74
total parent images	74
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	74

MAHLI image the DRT brushed target Donkey_Trail and the target Burn_Mouth.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Donkey_Trail before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3425MH00190001201629000	1628	autofocus sub-frame for target Donkey_Trail - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3425MH00190001201629000	1629	target Donkey_Trail - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	Donkey_Trail before DRT ~45 mm standoff	3425MH00112001201630000	1630	autofocus sub-frame for target Donkey_Trail - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 45 mm
		3425MH00112001201631000	1631	target Donkey_Trail - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 45 mm
mN00190	Burn_Mouth ~25 cm standoff	3425MH00190001201632000	1632	autofocus sub-frame for target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 25 cm
		3425MH00190001201633000	1633	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Burn_Mouth stereo 1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3425MH00173001201634000	1634	autofocus sub-frame for target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3425MH00173001201635000	1635	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3425MH00173001201636000	1636	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201637000	1637	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201638000	1638	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201639000	1639	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201640000	1640	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201641000	1641	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201642000	1642	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201643000	1643	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Burn_Mouth stereo 2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3425MH00173001201644000	1644	autofocus sub-frame for target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3425MH00173001201645000	1645	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3425MH00173001201646000	1646	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201647000	1647	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201648000	1648	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201649000	1649	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201650000	1650	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201651000	1651	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201652000	1652	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00173001201653000	1653	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00705	Burn_Mouth relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	3425MH00705001201654000	1654	autofocus sub-frame for target Burn_Mouth - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3425MH00705001201655000	1655	target Burn_Mouth - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Burn_Mouth relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3425MH00705001201656000	1656	autofocus sub-frame for target Burn_Mouth - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3425MH00705001201657000	1657	target Burn_Mouth - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Burn_Mouth relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3425MH00705001201658000	1658	autofocus sub-frame for target Burn_Mouth - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3425MH00705001201659000	1659	target Burn_Mouth - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00838	Burn_Mouth ~1 cm standoff	3425MH00838001201660000	1660	autofocus sub-frame for target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm
		3425MH00838001201661000	1661	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm
		3425MH00838001201662000	1662	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00838001201663000	1663	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00838001201664000	1664	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00838001201665000	1665	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00838001201666000	1666	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00838001201667000	1667	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00838001201668000	1668	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00838001201669000	1669	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Donkey_Trail after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3425MH00190001201670000	1670	autofocus sub-frame for target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3425MH00190001201671000	1671	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Donkey_Trail after DRT stereo 1 ~45 mm standoff	3425MH00168001201672000	1672	autofocus sub-frame for target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3425MH00168001201673000	1673	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3425MH00168001201674000	1674	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201675000	1675	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201676000	1676	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201677000	1677	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201678000	1678	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201679000	1679	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201680000	1680	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201681000	1681	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Donkey_Trail after DRT stereo 2 ~45 mm standoff	3425MH00168001201682000	1682	autofocus sub-frame for target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3425MH00168001201683000	1683	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3425MH00168001201684000	1684	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201685000	1685	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201686000	1686	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201687000	1687	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201688000	1688	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201689000	1689	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201690000	1690	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH00168001201691000	1691	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00743	Donkey_Trail after DRT ~7 mm standoff	3425MH00743001201692C00	1692	autofocus sub-frame for target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm
		3425MH00743001201693C00	1693	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm
		3425MH007430021201694C00	1694	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH007430021201695C00	1695	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH007430021201696C00	1696	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH007430021201697C00	1697	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH007430021201698C00	1698	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH007430021201699C00	1699	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH007430021201700C00	1700	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3425MH007430021201701C00	1701	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 29_March_2022

Sol 3427 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28-Mar-22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3425 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	3427MH0001630001201702N00	1702	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1694-1701 - best focus image product
		3427MH0001630001201703S00	1703	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 7 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1694-1701 - range map product
		3427MH0001630001201704N00	1704	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1684-1691 - best focus image product
		3427MH0001630001201705S00	1705	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1684-1691 - range map product
		3427MH0001630001201706N00	1706	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1674-1681 - best focus image product
		3427MH0001630001201707S00	1707	target Donkey_Trail - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1674-1681 - range map product
		3427MH0001630001201708N00	1708	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1662-1669 - best focus image product
		3427MH0001630001201709S00	1709	target Burn_Mouth - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1662-1669 - range map product
		3427MH0001630001201710N00	1710	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1646-1653 - best focus image product
		3427MH0001630001201711S00	1711	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1646-1653 - range map product
		3427MH0001630001201712N00	1712	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1636-1643 - best focus image product
		3427MH0001630001201713S00	1713	target Burn_Mouth - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3425 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1636-1643 - range map product

updated: 21_March_2023

Sol 3429 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30-Mar-23
camera position	Image ID:
total parent images	0 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
focus merges performed	12 CDPID:
total focus merge products	24 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
total parent images + focus merge products	24

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3428 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100458	Focus Merges	3429MH0004580001201838000	1838	target Broadfell - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1830-1837 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201839500	1839	target Broadfell - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1830-1837 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201840900	1840	target Broadfell - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1820-1827 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201841500	1841	target Broadfell - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1820-1827 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201842900	1842	target Broadfell - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1810-1817 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201843500	1843	target Broadfell - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1810-1817 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201844900	1844	target Venlaw - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1798-1805 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201845500	1845	target Venlaw - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1798-1805 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201846900	1846	target Venlaw - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff near 7 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1788-1795 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201847500	1847	target Venlaw - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff near 7 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1788-1795 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201848900	1848	target Venlaw - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff near 85 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1778-1785 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201849500	1849	target Venlaw - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff near 85 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1778-1785 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201850900	1850	target Venlaw - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1768-1775 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201851500	1851	target Venlaw - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1768-1775 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201852900	1852	target Venlaw - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1758-1765 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201853500	1853	target Venlaw - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1758-1765 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201854900	1854	target Venlaw - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1748-1755 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201855500	1855	target Venlaw - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1748-1755 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201856900	1856	target Venlaw - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1738-1745 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201857500	1857	target Venlaw - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1738-1745 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201858900	1858	target Venlaw - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1728-1735 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201859500	1859	target Venlaw - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1728-1735 - range map product
		3429MH0004580001201860900	1860	target Venlaw - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1718-1725 - best focus image product
		3429MH0004580001201861500	1861	target Venlaw - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3428 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1718-1725 - range map product

Sol 3432 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	2 Apr 22
camera position	12
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	75

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities
 MAHLI imaged the targets Blue_Anchor and Baa.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN100705	Blue_Anchor ~25 cm standoff	3432MH0070600120186200	1862	autofocus sub-frame for target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 25 cm		
		3432MH0070600120186300	1863	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 25 cm		
		3432MH0070600120186400	1864	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN100718	Blue_Anchor stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3432MH0070800120186500	1865	autofocus sub-frame for target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3432MH0070800120186600	1866	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3432MH0070800120186700	1867	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3432MH0070800120186800	1868	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0070800120186900	1869	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0070800120187000	1870	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0070800120187100	1871	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0070800120187200	1872	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0070800120187300	1873	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0070800120187400	1874	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0070800120187500	1875	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN100718	Blue_Anchor stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 mm standoff	3432MH0070800120187600	1876	autofocus sub-frame for target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm
				3432MH0070800120187700	1877	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm
				3432MH0070800120187800	1878	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
3432MH0070800120187900	1879			target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0070800120188000	1880			target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0070800120188100	1881			target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0070800120188200	1882			target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0070800120188300	1883			target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0070800120188400	1884			target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0070800120188500	1885			target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0070800120188600	1886			target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN100705	Blue_Anchor relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff			3432MH0070500120188700	1887	autofocus sub-frame for target Blue_Anchor - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
				3432MH0070500120188800	1888	target Blue_Anchor - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN100705	Blue_Anchor relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff			3432MH0070500120188900	1889	autofocus sub-frame for target Blue_Anchor - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3432MH0070500120189000	1890	target Blue_Anchor - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm		
mN100705	Blue_Anchor relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3432MH0070500120189100	1891	autofocus sub-frame for target Blue_Anchor - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3432MH0070500120189200	1892	target Blue_Anchor - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm		
mN100718	Blue_Anchor ~2 cm standoff	3432MH0079500120189300	1893	autofocus sub-frame for target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm		
		3432MH0079500120189400	1894	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm		
		3432MH0079500120189500	1895	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3432MH0079500120189600	1896	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0079500120189700	1897	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0079500120189800	1898	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0079500120189900	1899	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0079500120190000	1900	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0079500120190100	1901	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0079500120190200	1902	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0079500120190300	1903	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN100706	Baa ~25 cm standoff	3432MH0070600120190400	1904	autofocus sub-frame for target Baa - standoff near 25 cm
				3432MH0070600120190500	1905	target Baa - standoff near 25 cm
				3432MH0070600120190600	1906	target Baa - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN100813	Baa stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~4 cm standoff	3432MH0080800120190700	1907	autofocus sub-frame for target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3432MH0080800120190800	1908	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3432MH0080800120190900	1909	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3432MH0080800120191000	1910	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0080800120191100	1911	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0080800120191200	1912	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0080800120191300	1913	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0080800120191400	1914	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0080800120191500	1915	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0080800120191600	1916	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3432MH0080800120191700	1917	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN100813	Baa stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~4 cm standoff	3432MH0080800120191800	1918	autofocus sub-frame for target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3432MH0080800120191900	1919	target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3432MH0080800120192000	1920	target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3432MH0080800120192100	1921			target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0080800120192200	1922			target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0080800120192300	1923			target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0080800120192400	1924			target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0080800120192500	1925			target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0080800120192600	1926			target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0080800120192700	1927			target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3432MH0080800120192800	1928			target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00705	Baa relief model position 3 ~4 cm standoff	3432MH000705001201929C00	1929	autofocus sub-frame for target Baa - relief model position 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3432MH0007050011201930C00	1930	target Baa - relief model position 3 - standoff near 4 cm
mH00705	Baa relief model position 4 ~4 cm standoff	3432MH000705001201931C00	1931	autofocus sub-frame for target Baa - relief model position 4 - standoff near 4 cm
		3432MH0007050011201932C00	1932	target Baa - relief model position 4 - standoff near 4 cm
mH00705	Baa relief model position 5 ~4 cm standoff	3432MH000705001201933C00	1933	autofocus sub-frame for target Baa - relief model position 5 - standoff near 4 cm
		3432MH0007050011201934C00	1934	target Baa - relief model position 5 - standoff near 4 cm

updated: 04_April_2022

Sol 3433 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	0 Apr 22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3432 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3433MH000227000120193500	1935	target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1921-1928 - best focus image product
		3433MH0002270001201936500	1936	target Baa - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1921-1928 - range map product
		3433MH0002270001201937000	1937	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1910-1917 - best focus image product
		3433MH0002270001201938500	1938	target Baa - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1910-1917 - range map product
		3433MH0002270001201939000	1939	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1896-1903 - best focus image product
		3433MH0002270001201940500	1940	target Blue_Anchor - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1896-1903 - range map product
		3433MH0002270001201941000	1941	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1879-1886 - best focus image product
		3433MH0002270001201942500	1942	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1879-1886 - range map product
		3433MH0002270001201943000	1943	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1868-1875 - best focus image product
		3433MH0002270001201944500	1944	target Blue_Anchor - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3432 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1868-1875 - range map product

updated: 10_June_2022

Sol 3436 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	6 Apr 22
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

summary of MAHLI activities

MAHLI imaged the target Broo and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Broo ~25 cm standoff	3436MH00190001201945C0D	1945	autofocus sub-frame for target Broo - standoff near 25 cm
		3436MH00190001201946C0D	1946	target Broo - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Broo stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3436MH00168001201947C0D	1947	autofocus sub-frame for target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3436MH00168001201948C0D	1948	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3436MH00168001201949C0D	1949	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201950C0D	1950	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201951C0D	1951	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201952C0D	1952	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201953C0D	1953	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201954C0D	1954	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201955C0D	1955	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201956C0D	1956	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Broo stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3436MH00168001201957C0D	1957	autofocus sub-frame for target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3436MH00168001201958C0D	1958	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3436MH00168001201959C0D	1959	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201960C0D	1960	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201961C0D	1961	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201962C0D	1962	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201963C0D	1963	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201964C0D	1964	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201965C0D	1965	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00168001201966C0D	1966	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Broo ~2 cm standoff	3436MH00302001201967C0D	1967	autofocus sub-frame for target Broo - standoff near 2 cm
		3436MH00302001201968C0D	1968	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm
		3436MH00302001201969C0D	1969	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00302001201970C0D	1970	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00302001201971C0D	1971	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00302001201972C0D	1972	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00302001201973C0D	1973	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00302001201974C0D	1974	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00302001201975C0D	1975	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3436MH00302001201976C0D	1976	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3436MH00193001201977R0D	1977	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3436 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1969-1976 - best focus image product
		3436MH00193001201978S0D	1978	target Broo - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3436 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1969-1976 - range map product
		3436MH00193001201979R0D	1979	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3436 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1959-1966 - best focus image product
		3436MH00193001201980S0D	1980	target Broo - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3436 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1959-1966 - range map product
		3436MH00193001201981R0D	1981	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3436 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1949-1956 - best focus image product
		3436MH00193001201982S0D	1982	target Broo - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3436 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 1949-1956 - range map product

Sol 3439 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	0 Apr-22
camera position	42
total parent images	150
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	150

MAHLI imaged the targets Lodberrie and Sneuga and acquired a 1x3 mosaic from ~5 cm standoff on the target Incubony.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00706	Lodberrie ~25 cm standoff	3439MH0007060001201983C00	1983	autofocus sub-frame for target Lodberrie - standoff near 25 cm		
		3439MH0007060011201984C00	1984	target Lodberrie - standoff near 25 cm		
		3439MH0007060021201985C00	1985	target Lodberrie - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00723	Lodberrie stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3439MH0007230001201986C00	1986	autofocus sub-frame for target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3439MH0007230011201987C00	1987	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3439MH0007230021201988C00	1988	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3439MH0007230031201989C00	1989	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007230041201990C00	1990	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007230051201991C00	1991	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007230061201992C00	1992	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007230071201993C00	1993	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007230081201994C00	1994	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007230091201995C00	1995	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007230101201996C00	1996	target Lodberrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00723	Lodberrie stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3439MH0007230011201997C00	1997	autofocus sub-frame for target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3439MH0007230021201998C00	1998	target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3439MH0007230031201999C00	1999	target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3439MH0007230041202000C00	2000			target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0007230051202001C00	2001			target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0007230061202002C00	2002			target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0007230071202003C00	2003			target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0007230081202004C00	2004			target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0007230091202005C00	2005			target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0007230101202006C00	2006			target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0007230111202007C00	2007			target Lodberrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00746	Lodberrie ~2 cm standoff			3439MH0007460001202008C00	2008	autofocus sub-frame for target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm
				3439MH0007460011202009C00	2009	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm
				3439MH0007460021202010C00	2010	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3439MH0007460031202011C00	2011	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007460041202012C00	2012	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007460051202013C00	2013	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007460061202014C00	2014	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007460071202015C00	2015	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007460081202016C00	2016	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007460091202017C00	2017	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0007460101202018C00	2018	target Lodberrie - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00190	Sneuga ~25 cm standoff	3439MH0001900001202019C00	2019	autofocus sub-frame for target Sneuga - standoff near 25 cm
				3439MH0001900011202020C00	2020	target Sneuga - standoff near 25 cm
				3439MH0001900021202021C00	2021	autofocus sub-frame for target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mNI00152	Sneuga stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3439MH0001520011202022C00	2022	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3439MH0001520021202023C00	2023	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001520031202024C00	2024	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001520041202025C00	2025	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001520051202026C00	2026	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001520061202027C00	2027	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001520071202028C00	2028	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001520081202029C00	2029	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001520091202030C00	2030	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00152	Sneuga stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3439MH0001520011202031C00	2031	autofocus sub-frame for target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3439MH0001520021202032C00	2032	target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3439MH0001520031202033C00	2033	target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3439MH0001520041202034C00	2034	target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3439MH0001520051202035C00	2035	target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3439MH0001520061202036C00	2036			target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0001520071202037C00	2037			target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0001520081202038C00	2038			target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0001520091202039C00	2039			target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3439MH0001520101202040C00	2040			target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00176	Sneuga ~2 cm standoff			3439MH0001760001202041C00	2041	autofocus sub-frame for target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm
				3439MH0001760011202042C00	2042	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm
				3439MH0001760021202043C00	2043	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3439MH0001760031202044C00	2044	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH0001760041202045C00	2045	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001760051202046C00	2046	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001760061202047C00	2047	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001760071202048C00	2048	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001760081202049C00	2049	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3439MH0001760091202050C00	2050	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

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mH00190	Inchbonny ~23 cm standoff	3439MH001900011202051C00	2051	autofocus sub-frame for target Inchbonny - standoff near 23 cm
		3439MH001900011202052C00	2052	target Inchbonny - standoff near 23 cm
mH00299	Inchbonny mosaic position 1 of 3 ~4 cm standoff	3439MH002990011202053C00	2053	autofocus sub-frame for target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3439MH002990011202054C00	2054	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3439MH002990011202055C00	2055	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202056C00	2056	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202057C00	2057	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202058C00	2058	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202059C00	2059	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202060C00	2060	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202061C00	2061	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202062C00	2062	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00299	Inchbonny mosaic position 2 of 3 ~45 mm standoff	3439MH002990011202063C00	2063	autofocus sub-frame for target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm
		3439MH002990011202064C00	2064	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm
		3439MH002990011202065C00	2065	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202066C00	2066	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202067C00	2067	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202068C00	2068	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202069C00	2069	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202070C00	2070	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202071C00	2071	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202072C00	2072	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mH00299	Inchbonny mosaic position 3 of 3 ~5 cm standoff	3439MH002990011202073C00	2073	autofocus sub-frame for target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3439MH002990011202074C00	2074	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3439MH002990011202075C00	2075	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202076C00	2076	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202077C00	2077	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202078C00	2078	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202079C00	2079	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202080C00	2080	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202081C00	2081	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3439MH002990011202082C00	2082	target Inchbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 11_April_2022

Sol 3440 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-Apr-22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	9
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	18

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3439 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00536	Focus Merges	3440MH000536000120208300	2083	target Inehbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2075-2082 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120208450	2084	target Inehbonny - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2075-2082 - range map product
		3440MH000536000120208590	2085	target Inehbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2065-2072 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120208650	2086	target Inehbonny - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2065-2072 - range map product
		3440MH000536000120208700	2087	target Inehbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2055-2062 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120208850	2088	target Inehbonny - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2055-2062 - range map product
		3440MH000536000120208900	2089	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2043-2050 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120209050	2090	target Sneuga - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2043-2050 - range map product
		3440MH000536000120209100	2091	target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2033-2040 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120209250	2092	target Sneuga - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2033-2040 - range map product
		3440MH000536000120209300	2093	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2023-2030 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120209450	2094	target Sneuga - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2023-2030 - range map product
		3440MH000536000120209500	2095	target Iodherrie - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2011-2018 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120209650	2096	target Iodherrie - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2011-2018 - range map product
		3440MH000536000120209700	2097	target Iodherrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2000-2007 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120209850	2098	target Iodherrie - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2000-2007 - range map product
		3440MH000536000120209900	2099	target Iodherrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1989-1996 - best focus image product
		3440MH000536000120210050	2100	target Iodherrie - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3439 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 1989-1996 - range map product

Sol 3442 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	12_Apr_21	
		camera position	02	Image ID:
		total parent images	102	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	9	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	18	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	110	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Brackenberry and the targets Skidbladder and Up_Helly_Aa. The focus stack images were also merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Brackenberry before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3442MH0019000112021010C0	2101	autofocus sub-frame for target Brackenberry - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3442MH0019000112021020C0	2102	target Brackenberry - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	Brackenberry before DRT ~5 cm standoff	3442MH0011200112021010C0	2103	autofocus sub-frame for target Brackenberry - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0011200112021040C0	2104	target Brackenberry - before dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 5 cm
mN00190	Brackenberry after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3442MH0019000112021050C0	2105	autofocus sub-frame for target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3442MH0019000112021060C0	2106	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Brackenberry after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3442MH0016800112021070C0	2107	autofocus sub-frame for target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0016800112021080C0	2108	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0016800112021090C0	2109	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021100C0	2110	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021110C0	2111	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021120C0	2112	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021130C0	2113	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021140C0	2114	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021150C0	2115	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021160C0	2116	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Brackenberry after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3442MH0016800112021170C0	2117	autofocus sub-frame for target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0016800112021180C0	2118	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0016800112021190C0	2119	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021200C0	2120	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021210C0	2121	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021220C0	2122	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021230C0	2123	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021240C0	2124	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021250C0	2125	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0016800112021260C0	2126	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Brackenberry after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3442MH0030200112021270C0	2127	autofocus sub-frame for target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3442MH0030200112021280C0	2128	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3442MH0030200112021290C0	2129	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0030200112021300C0	2130	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0030200112021310C0	2131	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0030200112021320C0	2132	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0030200112021330C0	2133	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0030200112021340C0	2134	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0030200112021350C0	2135	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0030200112021360C0	2136	target Brackenberry - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Skidbladder mosaic position 1 of 2 ~25 cm standoff	3442MH0019000112021370C0	2137	autofocus sub-frame for target Skidbladder - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3442MH0019000112021380C0	2138	target Skidbladder - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00190	Skidbladder mosaic position 2 of 2 ~25 cm standoff	3442MH0019000112021390C0	2139	autofocus sub-frame for target Skidbladder - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3442MH0019000112021400C0	2140	target Skidbladder - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Skidbladder stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3442MH0017300112021410C0	2141	autofocus sub-frame for target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0017300112021420C0	2142	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0017300112021430C0	2143	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021440C0	2144	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021450C0	2145	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021460C0	2146	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021470C0	2147	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021480C0	2148	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021490C0	2149	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021500C0	2150	target Skidbladder - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Skidbladder stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3442MH0017300112021510C0	2151	autofocus sub-frame for target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0017300112021520C0	2152	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3442MH0017300112021530C0	2153	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021540C0	2154	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021550C0	2155	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021560C0	2156	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021570C0	2157	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021580C0	2158	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021590C0	2159	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3442MH0017300112021600C0	2160	target Skidbladder - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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updated: 13_June_2022

Sol 3444 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	16_Apr_21
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the target Dun and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00172	Dun ~20 cm standoff	3444MH0001720011202212C00	2221	autofocus sub-frame for target Dun - standoff near 20 cm
		3444MH0001720011202222C00	2222	target Dun - standoff near 20 cm
mN00306	Dun stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3444MH0003060011202232C00	2223	autofocus sub-frame for target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3444MH0003060011202242C00	2224	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3444MH0003060011202252C00	2225	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003060011202262C00	2226	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003060011202272C00	2227	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003060011202282C00	2228	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003060011202292C00	2229	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120230C00	2230	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120231C00	2231	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120232C00	2232	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00306	Dun stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3444MH000306001120233C00	2233	autofocus sub-frame for target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3444MH000306001120234C00	2234	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3444MH000306001120235C00	2235	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120236C00	2236	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120237C00	2237	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120238C00	2238	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120239C00	2239	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120240C00	2240	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120241C00	2241	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH000306001120242C00	2242	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00311	Dun ~2 cm standoff	3444MH0003110011202243C00	2243	autofocus sub-frame for target Dun - standoff near 2 cm
		3444MH0003110011202244C00	2244	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm
		3444MH0003110011202245C00	2245	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003110011202246C00	2246	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003110011202247C00	2247	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003110011202248C00	2248	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003110011202249C00	2249	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003110011202250C00	2250	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003110011202251C00	2251	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3444MH0003110011202252C00	2252	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00289	Focus Merges	3444MH0001930011202253R00	2253	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3444 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2245-2252 - best focus image product
		3444MH0001930011202254R00	2254	target Dun - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3444 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2245-2252 - range map product
		3444MH0001930011202255R00	2255	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3444 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2235-2242 - best focus image product
		3444MH0001930011202256R00	2256	target Dun - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3444 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2235-2242 - range map product
		3444MH0001930011202257R00	2257	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3444 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2225-2232 - best focus image product
		3444MH0001930011202258R00	2258	target Dun - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3444 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2225-2232 - range map product

updated: 14_October_2022

Sol 3447 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
		Camera position	4		Image ID:
		Total parent images	49		Black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		Focus merges performed	4		CPDPD:
		Total focus merge products	8		Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		Total parent images + focus merge products	57		
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Spiggie_Beach and Bains_Beach as well as the wheel-rock contact of the rover left front wheel that was obstructing mobility. The focus stack images were also merged.					
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN00290	Spiggie_Beach ~25 cm standoff	3447MH000190001120229900	2259	autofocus sub-frame for target Spiggie_Beach - standoff near 25 cm	
		3447MH000190001120226000	2260	target Spiggie_Beach - standoff near 25 cm	
mN00297	Spiggie_Beach stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3447MH00029700011202261000	2261	autofocus sub-frame for target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3447MH00029700011202262000	2262	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3447MH00029700011202263000	2263	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202264000	2264	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202265000	2265	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202266000	2266	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202267000	2267	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202268000	2268	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202269000	2269	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202270000	2270	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00297	Spiggie_Beach stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3447MH00029700011202271000	2271	autofocus sub-frame for target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3447MH00029700011202272000	2272	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm	
		3447MH00029700011202273000	2273	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202274000	2274	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202275000	2275	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202276000	2276	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202277000	2277	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202278000	2278	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202279000	2279	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00029700011202280000	2280	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00706	Bains_Beach ~23 cm standoff	3447MH00070600011202281000	2281	autofocus sub-frame for target Bains_Beach - standoff near 23 cm	
		3447MH00070600011202282000	2282	target Bains_Beach - standoff near 23 cm	
		3447MH00070600011202283000	2283	target Bains_Beach - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure	
mN00740	Bains_Beach stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3447MH00074000011202284000	2284	autofocus sub-frame for target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm	
		3447MH00074000011202285000	2285	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm	
		3447MH00074000011202286000	2286	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure	
		3447MH00074000011202287000	2287	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202288000	2288	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202289000	2289	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202290000	2290	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202291000	2291	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202292000	2292	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202293000	2293	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00740	Bains_Beach stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3447MH00074000011202294000	2294	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202295000	2295	autofocus sub-frame for target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm	
		3447MH00074000011202296000	2296	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm	
		3447MH00074000011202297000	2297	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure	
		3447MH00074000011202298000	2298	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202299000	2299	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202300000	2300	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202301000	2301	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202302000	2302	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack	
		3447MH00074000011202303000	2303	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack	
mN00262	Rover Left Front Wheel	3447MH00026200011202306001	2306	rover left front wheel contact with rock - mobility obstruction assessment - target at about 112 cm - manual focus at motor count 12660	
		3447MH00026200011202307001	2307	rover left front wheel contact with rock - mobility obstruction assessment - target at about 112 cm - manual focus at motor count 12660	
mN00817	Focus Merges	3447MH00081700011202308000	2308	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3447 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2298-2305 - best focus image product	
		3447MH00081700011202309000	2309	target Bains_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3447 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2298-2305 - range map product	
		3447MH000817000112023100000	2310	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3447 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2287-2294 - best focus image product	
		3447MH000817000112023115000	2311	target Bains_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3447 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2287-2294 - range map product	
		3447MH00081700011202312000	2312	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3447 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2273-2280 - best focus image product	
		3447MH000817000112023125000	2313	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3447 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2273-2280 - range map product	
		3447MH00081700011202314000	2314	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3447 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2263-2270 - best focus image product	
		3447MH00081700011202315500	2315	target Spiggie_Beach - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3447 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2263-2270 - range map product	

updated: 13_june_2022

Sol 3449 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13-jun-2022
camera positions	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the target Runn and the REMS UV sensor. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Runn ~25 cm standoff	3449MH000190001202316C00	2316	autofocus sub-frame for target Runn - standoff near 25 cm
		3449MH000190001202317C00	2317	target Runn - standoff near 25 cm
mN00224	Runn stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3449MH000224001202318C00	2318	autofocus sub-frame for target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3449MH000224001202319C00	2319	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3449MH000224001202320C00	2320	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202321C00	2321	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202322C00	2322	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202323C00	2323	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202324C00	2324	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202325C00	2325	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202326C00	2326	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202327C00	2327	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	Runn stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3449MH000224001202328C00	2328	autofocus sub-frame for target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3449MH000224001202329C00	2329	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3449MH000224001202330C00	2330	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202331C00	2331	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202332C00	2332	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202333C00	2333	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202334C00	2334	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202335C00	2335	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202336C00	2336	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3449MH000224001202337C00	2337	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00095	REMS UV sensor ~15 cm standoff	3449MH000095001202338C00	2338	autofocus sub-frame for REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
		3449MH000095001202339C00	2339	REMS UV sensor - characterize dust accumulation
mN00265	Focus Merges	3449MH000265001202340R00	2340	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3449 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2330-2337 - best focus image product
		3449MH000265001202341S00	2341	target Runn - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3449 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2330-2337 - range map product
		3449MH000265001202342R00	2342	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3449 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2320-2327 - best focus image product
		3449MH000265001202343S00	2343	target Runn - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3449 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2320-2327 - range map product

Sol 3451- MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-Apr-21
camera position	11
total parent images	97
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	18
total parent images + focus merge products	113

MAHLI imaged the target Rumbings, the DRT-brushed target Shandon and the target Nesting. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00842	Rumbings ~23 cm standoff	3451MH00084200112023440C0	2344	autofocus sub-frame for target Rumbings - standoff near 23 cm		
		3451MH0008420011202345C0D	2345	target Rumbings - standoff near 23 cm		
		3451MH0008420011202346C0D	2346	target Rumbings - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00843	Rumbings stereo-1 ~35 mm standoff	3451MH0008430011202347C0D	2347	autofocus sub-frame for target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm		
		3451MH0008430011202348C0D	2348	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm		
		3451MH0008430011202349C0D	2349	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3451MH0008430011202350C0D	2350	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0008430011202351C0D	2351	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0008430011202352C0D	2352	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0008430011202353C0D	2353	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0008430011202354C0D	2354	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0008430011202355C0D	2355	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0008430011202356C0D	2356	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0008430011202357C0D	2357	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00843	Rumbings stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3451MH0008430011202358C0D	2358	autofocus sub-frame for target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
				3451MH0008430011202359C0D	2359	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
3451MH0008430011202360C0D	2360			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
3451MH0008430011202361C0D	2361			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0008430011202362C0D	2362			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0008430011202363C0D	2363			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0008430011202364C0D	2364			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0008430011202365C0D	2365			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0008430011202366C0D	2366			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0008430011202367C0D	2367			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0008430011202368C0D	2368			target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00706	Shandon after DRT ~25 cm standoff			3451MH0007600011202370C0D	2369	autofocus sub-frame for target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
				3451MH0007600011202371C0D	2370	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3451MH0007600011202372C0D	2371	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00706	Shandon after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3451MH0007630011202373C0D	2372	autofocus sub-frame for target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3451MH0007630011202374C0D	2373	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3451MH0007630011202375C0D	2374	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3451MH0007630011202376C0D	2375	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0007630011202377C0D	2376	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0007630011202378C0D	2377	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0007630011202379C0D	2378	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0007630011202380C0D	2379	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0007630011202381C0D	2380	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0007630011202382C0D	2381	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH0007630011202383C0D	2382	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00706	Shandon after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3451MH0007630011202384C0D	2383	autofocus sub-frame for target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3451MH0007630011202385C0D	2384	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3451MH0007630011202386C0D	2385			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
3451MH0007630011202387C0D	2386			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0007630011202388C0D	2387			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0007630011202389C0D	2388			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0007630011202390C0D	2389			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0007630011202391C0D	2390			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0007630011202392C0D	2391			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0007630011202393C0D	2392			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3451MH0007630011202394C0D	2393			target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00824	Shandon after DRT ~2 cm standoff			3451MH000840011202394C0D	2394	autofocus sub-frame for target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
				3451MH000840011202395C0D	2395	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3451MH000840011202396C0D	2396	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3451MH000840011202397C0D	2397	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH000840011202398C0D	2398	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH000840011202399C0D	2399	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH000840011202400C0D	2400	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH000840011202401C0D	2401	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH000840011202402C0D	2402	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH000840011202403C0D	2403	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3451MH000840011202404C0D	2404	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00706	Nesting ~25 cm standoff	3451MH0007600011202405C0D	2405	autofocus sub-frame for target Nesting - standoff near 25 cm
				3451MH0007600011202406C0D	2406	target Nesting - standoff near 25 cm
3451MH0007600011202407C0D	2407			target Nesting - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		

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mH00699	Nesting stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3451MH00699001202408C00	2408	autofocus sub-frame for target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3451MH00699001202409C00	2409	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3451MH00699001202410C00	2410	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3451MH00699001202411C00	2411	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202412C00	2412	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202413C00	2413	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202414C00	2414	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202415C00	2415	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202416C00	2416	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202417C00	2417	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3451MH00699001202418C00	2418	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00699	Nesting stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3451MH00699001202419C00	2419	autofocus sub-frame for target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3451MH00699001202420C00	2420	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3451MH00699001202421C00	2421	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3451MH00699001202422C00	2422	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202423C00	2423	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202424C00	2424	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202425C00	2425	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202426C00	2426	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202427C00	2427	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00699001202428C00	2428	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3451MH00699001202429C00	2429	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00824	Nesting ~2 cm standoff	3451MH00824001202430C00	2430	autofocus sub-frame for target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm
		3451MH00824001202431C00	2431	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm
		3451MH00824001202432C00	2432	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3451MH00824001202433C00	2433	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00824001202434C00	2434	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00824001202435C00	2435	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00824001202436C00	2436	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00824001202437C00	2437	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00824001202438C00	2438	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3451MH00824001202439C00	2439	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3451MH00824001202440C00	2440	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00170	Focus Merges	3451MH00170001202441R00	2441	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2433-2440 - best focus image product
		3451MH00170001202442S00	2442	target Nesting - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2433-2440 - range map product
		3451MH00170001202443R00	2443	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2422-2429 - best focus image product
		3451MH00170001202444S00	2444	target Nesting - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2422-2429 - range map product
		3451MH00170001202445R00	2445	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2411-2418 - best focus image product
		3451MH00170001202446S00	2446	target Nesting - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2411-2418 - range map product
		3451MH00170001202447R00	2447	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2397-2404 - best focus image product
		3451MH00170001202448S00	2448	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2397-2404 - range map product
		3451MH00170001202449R00	2449	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2386-2393 - best focus image product
		3451MH00170001202450S00	2450	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2386-2393 - range map product
		3451MH00170001202451R00	2451	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2375-2382 - best focus image product
		3451MH00170001202452S00	2452	target Shandon - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2375-2382 - range map product
		3451MH00170001202453R00	2453	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2361-2368 - best focus image product
		3451MH00170001202454S00	2454	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2361-2368 - range map product
		3451MH00170001202455R00	2455	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2350-2357 - best focus image product
		3451MH00170001202456S00	2456	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3451 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2350-2357 - range map product

Sol 3453 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	26-Apr-21
camera position	75
total parent images	75
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	75

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Delting and the target Rumbings. MAHLI also imaged the rover left front wheel as a follow-up to the imaging acquired on Sol 3447.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00705	Delting after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3453MH00706001202457000	2457	autofocus sub-frame for target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3453MH00706001202458000	2458	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3453MH00706001202459000	2459	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00703	Delting after DRT stereo 1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3453MH00703001202460000	2460	autofocus sub-frame for target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00703001202461000	2461	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00703001202462000	2462	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3453MH00703001202463000	2463	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202464000	2464	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202465000	2465	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202466000	2466	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202467000	2467	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202468000	2468	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202469000	2469	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00703	Delting after DRT stereo 2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3453MH00703001202470000	2470	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202471000	2471	autofocus sub-frame for target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00703001202472000	2472	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00703001202473000	2473	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3453MH00703001202474000	2474	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202475000	2475	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202476000	2476	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202477000	2477	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202478000	2478	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00703001202479000	2479	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00705	Delting after DRT relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	3453MH00705001202480000	2480	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00705001202481000	2481	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00705001202482000	2482	autofocus sub-frame for target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Delting after DRT relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3453MH00705001202483000	2483	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00705001202484000	2484	autofocus sub-frame for target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Delting after DRT relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3453MH00705001202485000	2485	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00705001202486000	2486	autofocus sub-frame for target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00813	Delting after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3453MH00813001202487000	2487	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00813001202488000	2488	autofocus sub-frame for target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3453MH00813001202489000	2489	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3453MH00813001202490000	2490	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3453MH00813001202491000	2491	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00813001202492000	2492	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00813001202493000	2493	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00813001202494000	2494	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00813001202495000	2495	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00813001202496000	2496	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00706	Rumbings ~25 cm standoff	3453MH00813001202497000	2497	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00813001202498000	2498	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00706001202499000	2499	autofocus sub-frame for target Rumbings - standoff near 25 cm
mN00709	Rumbings stereo 1 ~5 cm standoff	3453MH00706001202500000	2500	target Rumbings - standoff near 25 cm
		3453MH00706001202501000	2501	target Rumbings - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3453MH00709001202502000	2502	autofocus sub-frame for target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00709001202503000	2503	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00709001202504000	2504	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3453MH00709001202505000	2505	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202506000	2506	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202507000	2507	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202508000	2508	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202509000	2509	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00709	Rumbings stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	3453MH00709001202510000	2510	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202511000	2511	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202512000	2512	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202513000	2513	autofocus sub-frame for target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00709001202514000	2514	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3453MH00709001202515000	2515	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3453MH00709001202516000	2516	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202517000	2517	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202518000	2518	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202519000	2519	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00709	Rumbings stereo 2 ~5 cm standoff	3453MH00709001202520000	2520	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202521000	2521	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202522000	2522	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH00709001202523000	2523	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

mNH00711	Bumblebees ~2 cm standoff	3453MH0007110001202524C00	2524	autofocus sub-frame for target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm
		3453MH0007110011202525C00	2525	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm
		3453MH0007110021202526C00	2526	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3453MH0007110031202527C00	2527	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH0007110041202528C00	2528	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH0007110051202529C00	2529	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH0007110061202530C00	2530	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH0007110071202531C00	2531	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH0007110081202532C00	2532	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3453MH0007110091202533C00	2533	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3453MH0007110101202534C00	2534	target Bumblebees - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNH00262	Rover Left Front Wheel	3453MH0002620001202535E02	2535	rover left front wheel - sol 3447 mobility obstruction assessment follow-up - target at about 112 cm - manual focus at motor count 12640

updated: 27_April_2022

Sol 3454 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	25-Apr-22
camera positions	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	12

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3453 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	3454MH001630001202536800	2536	target Rumbings - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2527-2534 - best focus image product
		3454MH001630001202537500	2537	target Rumbings - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2527-2534 - range map product
		3454MH001630001202538800	2538	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2516-2523 - best focus image product
		3454MH001630001202539500	2539	target Rumbings - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2516-2523 - range map product
		3454MH001630001202540800	2540	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2505-2512 - best focus image product
		3454MH001630001202541500	2541	target Rumbings - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2505-2512 - range map product
		3454MH001630001202542800	2542	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2491-2498 - best focus image product
		3454MH001630001202543500	2543	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2491-2498 - range map product
		3454MH001630001202544800	2544	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2474-2481 - best focus image product
		3454MH001630001202545500	2545	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2474-2481 - range map product
		3454MH001630001202546800	2546	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2463-2470 - best focus image product
		3454MH001630001202547500	2547	target Delting - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3453 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2463-2470 - range map product

updated: 13_June_2022

Sol 3456 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	27_Apr_21
camera positions	8
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	31

MAHLI imaged the target Colla_Firth and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00706	Colla_Firth ~25 cm standoff	3456MH0007060011202548C0D	2548	autofocus sub-frame for target Colla_Firth - standoff near 25 cm
		3456MH0007060011202549C0D	2549	target Colla_Firth - standoff near 25 cm
		3456MH0007060011202550C0D	2550	target Colla_Firth - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00182	Colla_Firth Stereo 1 ~45 mm standoff	3456MH00018200011202551C0D	2551	autofocus sub-frame for target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3456MH00018200011202552C0D	2552	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3456MH00018200011202553C0D	2553	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202554C0D	2554	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202555C0D	2555	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202556C0D	2556	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202557C0D	2557	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202558C0D	2558	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202559C0D	2559	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202560C0D	2560	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Colla_Firth Stereo 2 ~45 mm standoff	3456MH00018200011202561C0D	2561	autofocus sub-frame for target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3456MH00018200011202562C0D	2562	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3456MH00018200011202563C0D	2563	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202564C0D	2564	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202565C0D	2565	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202566C0D	2566	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202567C0D	2567	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202568C0D	2568	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202569C0D	2569	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3456MH00018200011202570C0D	2570	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3456MH00026500011202571R0D	2571	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3456 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2563-2570 - best focus image product
		3456MH00026500011202572R0D	2572	target Colla_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3456 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2563-2570 - range map product
		3456MH00026500011202573R0D	2573	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3456 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2553-2560 - best focus image product
		3456MH00026500011202574R0D	2574	target Colla_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3456 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2553-2560 - range map product

updated: 14_June_2022

Sol 3458 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29-Apr-21
camera position	55
total parent images	55
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	65

MAHLI imaged the targets Orton_Scar and Cow_Head and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mhl00706	Orton_Scar ~23 cm standoff	3458MH000706001202575Z00	2575	autofocus sub-frame for target Orton_Scar - standoff near 23 cm
		3458MH000706001202576Z00	2576	target Orton_Scar - standoff near 23 cm
		3458MH000706001202577Z00	2577	target Orton_Scar - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00073	Orton_Scar stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3458MH000173001202578Z00	2578	autofocus sub-frame for target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3458MH000173001202579Z00	2579	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3458MH000173001202580Z00	2580	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202581Z00	2581	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202582Z00	2582	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202583Z00	2583	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202584Z00	2584	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202585Z00	2585	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202586Z00	2586	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202587Z00	2587	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00073	Orton_Scar stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3458MH000173001202588Z00	2588	autofocus sub-frame for target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3458MH000173001202589Z00	2589	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3458MH000173001202590Z00	2590	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202591Z00	2591	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202592Z00	2592	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202593Z00	2593	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202594Z00	2594	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202595Z00	2595	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202596Z00	2596	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000173001202597Z00	2597	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00076	Cow_Head ~25 cm standoff	3458MH000706001202598Z00	2598	autofocus sub-frame for target Cow_Head - standoff near 25 cm
		3458MH000706001202599Z00	2599	target Cow_Head - standoff near 25 cm
		3458MH000706001202600Z00	2600	target Cow_Head - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mhl00182	Cow_Head stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3458MH00182001202601Z00	2601	autofocus sub-frame for target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3458MH00182001202602Z00	2602	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3458MH00182001202603Z00	2603	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202604Z00	2604	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202605Z00	2605	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202606Z00	2606	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202607Z00	2607	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202608Z00	2608	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202609Z00	2609	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202610Z00	2610	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00182	Cow_Head stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3458MH00182001202611Z00	2611	autofocus sub-frame for target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3458MH00182001202612Z00	2612	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3458MH00182001202613Z00	2613	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202614Z00	2614	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202615Z00	2615	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202616Z00	2616	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202617Z00	2617	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202618Z00	2618	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202619Z00	2619	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH00182001202620Z00	2620	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00176	Cow_Head ~2 cm standoff	3458MH000176001202621Z00	2621	autofocus sub-frame for target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm
		3458MH000176001202622Z00	2622	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm
		3458MH000176001202623Z00	2623	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000176001202624Z00	2624	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000176001202625Z00	2625	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000176001202626Z00	2626	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000176001202627Z00	2627	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000176001202628Z00	2628	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000176001202629Z00	2629	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3458MH000176001202630Z00	2630	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mhl00227	Focus Merges	3458MH000227001202631Z00	2631	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2623-2630 - best focus image product
		3458MH000227001202632Z00	2632	target Cow_Head - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2623-2630 - range map product
		3458MH000227001202633Z00	2633	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2613-2620 - best focus image product
		3458MH000227001202634Z00	2634	target Cow_Head - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2613-2620 - range map product
		3458MH000227001202635Z00	2635	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2603-2610 - best focus image product
		3458MH000227001202636Z00	2636	target Cow_Head - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2603-2610 - range map product
		3458MH000227001202637Z00	2637	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2590-2597 - best focus image product
		3458MH000227001202638Z00	2638	target Orton_Scar - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2590-2597 - range map product
		3458MH000227001202639Z00	2639	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2580-2587 - best focus image product
		3458MH000227001202640Z00	2640	target Orton_Scar - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3458 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2580-2587 - range map product

updated: 23_June_2022

Sol 3459 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30-Apr-21
camera positions	65
total parent images	65
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	65

MAHLI imaged the targets Castlecraig and Cat_Firih.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mNI00845	Castlecraig ~ 20 cm standoff	3459MH0008450011202641ZC0D	2641	autofocus sub-frame for target Castlecraig - standoff near 20 cm		
		3459MH0008450011202642ZC0D	2642	target Castlecraig - standoff near 20 cm		
		3459MH0008450011202643ZC0D	2643	target Castlecraig - standoff near 20 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00740	Castlecraig stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~ 55 mm standoff	3459MH0007400011202644ZC0D	2644	autofocus sub-frame for target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm		
		3459MH0007400011202645ZC0D	2645	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm		
		3459MH0007400011202646ZC0D	2646	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3459MH0007400011202647ZC0D	2647	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202648ZC0D	2648	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202649ZC0D	2649	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202650ZC0D	2650	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202651ZC0D	2651	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202652ZC0D	2652	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202653ZC0D	2653	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202654ZC0D	2654	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202655ZC0D	2655	autofocus sub-frame for target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm		
		3459MH0007400011202656ZC0D	2656	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm		
		3459MH0007400011202657ZC0D	2657	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
mNI00740	Castlecraig stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~ 55 mm standoff	3459MH0007400011202658ZC0D	2658	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202659ZC0D	2659	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202660ZC0D	2660	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202661ZC0D	2661	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202662ZC0D	2662	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202663ZC0D	2663	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202664ZC0D	2664	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0007400011202665ZC0D	2665	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00705	Castlecraig relief model position 3 ~ 55 mm standoff	3459MH0007050011202666ZC0D	2666	autofocus sub-frame for target Castlecraig - relief model position 3 - standoff near 55 mm
				3459MH0007050011202667ZC0D	2667	target Castlecraig - relief model position 3 - standoff near 55 mm
		mNI00705	Castlecraig relief model position 4 ~ 55 mm standoff	3459MH0007050011202668ZC0D	2668	autofocus sub-frame for target Castlecraig - relief model position 4 - standoff near 55 mm
				3459MH0007050011202669ZC0D	2669	target Castlecraig - relief model position 4 - standoff near 55 mm
		mNI00705	Castlecraig relief model position 5 ~ 55 mm standoff	3459MH0007050011202670ZC0D	2670	autofocus sub-frame for target Castlecraig - relief model position 5 - standoff near 55 mm
				3459MH0007050011202671ZC0D	2671	target Castlecraig - relief model position 5 - standoff near 55 mm
mNI00844	Castlecraig ~ 35 mm standoff	3459MH0008440011202672ZC0D	2672	autofocus sub-frame for target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm		
		3459MH0008440011202673ZC0D	2673	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm		
		3459MH0008440011202674ZC0D	2674	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3459MH0008440011202675ZC0D	2675	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0008440011202676ZC0D	2676	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0008440011202677ZC0D	2677	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0008440011202678ZC0D	2678	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0008440011202679ZC0D	2679	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0008440011202680ZC0D	2680	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0008440011202681ZC0D	2681	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH0008440011202682ZC0D	2682	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mNI00706	Cat_Firih ~ 25 cm standoff	3459MH0007060011202683ZC0D	2683	autofocus sub-frame for target Cat_Firih - standoff near 25 cm
				3459MH0007060011202684ZC0D	2684	target Cat_Firih - standoff near 25 cm
				3459MH0007060011202685ZC0D	2685	target Cat_Firih - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00182	Cat_Firih stereo-1 ~ 5 cm standoff	3459MH001820011202686ZC0D	2686	autofocus sub-frame for target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3459MH001820011202687ZC0D	2687	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3459MH001820011202688ZC0D	2688	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202689ZC0D	2689	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202690ZC0D	2690	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202691ZC0D	2691	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202692ZC0D	2692	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202693ZC0D	2693	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202694ZC0D	2694	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202695ZC0D	2695	target Cat_Firih - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202696ZC0D	2696	autofocus sub-frame for target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3459MH001820011202697ZC0D	2697	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3459MH001820011202698ZC0D	2698	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202699ZC0D	2699	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mNI00182	Cat_Firih stereo-2 ~ 5 cm standoff	3459MH001820011202700ZC0D	2700	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202701ZC0D	2701	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202702ZC0D	2702	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202703ZC0D	2703	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202704ZC0D	2704	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3459MH001820011202705ZC0D	2705	target Cat_Firih - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 03_May_2022

Sol 3461 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	2-May-22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3459 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3461MH0002270001202706R00	2706	target Cat_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2698-2705 - best focus image product
		3461MH0002270001202707S00	2707	target Cat_Firth - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2698-2705 - range map product
		3461MH0002270001202708R00	2708	target Cat_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2688-2695 - best focus image product
		3461MH0002270001202709S00	2709	target Cat_Firth - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2688-2695 - range map product
		3461MH0002270001202710R00	2710	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2675-2682 - best focus image product
		3461MH0002270001202711S00	2711	target Castlecraig - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2675-2682 - range map product
		3461MH0002270001202712R00	2712	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2658-2665 - best focus image product
		3461MH0002270001202713S00	2713	target Castlecraig - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2658-2665 - range map product
		3461MH0002270001202714R00	2714	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2647-2654 - best focus image product
		3461MH0002270001202715S00	2715	target Castlecraig - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3459 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2647-2654 - range map product

updated: 17_June_2022

Sol 3462 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	3-May-22
camera position	2
total parent images	54
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	64

MAHLI imaged the targets Gran_Sabana and Berlicce and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Gran_Sabana ~25 cm standoff	3462MH001900011202716000	2716	autofocus sub-frame for target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 25 cm
		3462MH001900011202717000	2717	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 25 cm
mN00299	Gran_Sabana stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3462MH002990011202718000	2718	autofocus sub-frame for target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3462MH002990011202719000	2719	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3462MH002990011202720000	2720	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202721000	2721	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202722000	2722	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202723000	2723	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202724000	2724	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202725000	2725	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202726000	2726	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202727000	2727	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Gran_Sabana stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3462MH002990011202728000	2728	autofocus sub-frame for target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3462MH002990011202729000	2729	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3462MH002990011202730000	2730	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202731000	2731	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202732000	2732	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202733000	2733	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202734000	2734	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202735000	2735	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202736000	2736	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH002990011202737000	2737	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00311	Gran_Sabana ~2 cm standoff	3462MH003110011202738000	2738	autofocus sub-frame for target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm
		3462MH003110011202739000	2739	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm
		3462MH003110011202740000	2740	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003110011202741000	2741	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003110011202742000	2742	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003110011202743000	2743	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003110011202744000	2744	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003110011202745000	2745	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003110011202746000	2746	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003110011202747000	2747	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00172	Berlicce ~20 cm standoff	3462MH001720011202748000	2748	autofocus sub-frame for target Berlicce - standoff near 20 cm
		3462MH001720011202749000	2749	target Berlicce - standoff near 20 cm
mN00363	Berlicce stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	3462MH003630011202750000	2750	autofocus sub-frame for target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3462MH003630011202751000	2751	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3462MH003630011202752000	2752	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202753000	2753	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202754000	2754	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202755000	2755	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202756000	2756	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202757000	2757	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202758000	2758	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202759000	2759	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00363	Berlicce stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	3462MH003630011202760000	2760	autofocus sub-frame for target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		3462MH003630011202761000	2761	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		3462MH003630011202762000	2762	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202763000	2763	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202764000	2764	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202765000	2765	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202766000	2766	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202767000	2767	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202768000	2768	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3462MH003630011202769000	2769	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00227	Focus Merges	3462MH00022700011202770000	2770	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2762-2769 - best focus image product
		3462MH00022700011202771000	2771	target Berlicce - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2762-2769 - range map product
		3462MH00022700011202772000	2772	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2752-2759 - best focus image product
		3462MH00022700011202773000	2773	target Berlicce - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2752-2759 - range map product
		3462MH00022700011202774000	2774	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2740-2747 - best focus image product
		3462MH00022700011202775000	2775	target Gran_Sabana - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2740-2747 - range map product
		3462MH00022700011202776000	2776	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2730-2737 - best focus image product
		3462MH00022700011202777000	2777	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2730-2737 - range map product
		3462MH00022700011202778000	2778	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2720-2727 - best focus image product
		3462MH00022700011202779000	2779	target Gran_Sabana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3462 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2720-2727 - range map product

updated: 17_June_2022

Sol 3465 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	6-May-22
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	39

MAHLI imaged the targets Firina (2x1 mosaic) and Bartica and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00846	Firina mosaic position 1 of 2 ~20 cm standoff	3465MH0008460011202780C0D	2780	autofocus sub-frame for target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm		
		3465MH0008460011202781C0D	2781	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm		
		3465MH0008460011202782C0D	2782	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202783C0D	2783	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202784C0D	2784	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202785C0D	2785	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202786C0D	2786	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202787C0D	2787	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202788C0D	2788	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202789C0D	2789	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202790C0D	2790	autofocus sub-frame for target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm		
		3465MH0008460011202791C0D	2791	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm		
		3465MH0008460011202792C0D	2792	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202793C0D	2793	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00846	Firina mosaic position 2 of 2 ~24 cm standoff	3465MH0008460011202794C0D	2794	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202795C0D	2795	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202796C0D	2796	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202797C0D	2797	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202798C0D	2798	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3465MH0008460011202799C0D	2799	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00190	Bartica ~24 cm standoff	3465MH0001900011202800C0D	2800	autofocus sub-frame for target Bartica - standoff near 24 cm
				3465MH0001900011202801C0D	2801	target Bartica - standoff near 24 cm
		mN00224	Bartica ~4 cm standoff	3465MH0002240011202802C0D	2802	autofocus sub-frame for target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm
				3465MH0002240011202803C0D	2803	target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm
				3465MH0002240011202804C0D	2804	target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3465MH0002240011202805C0D	2805	target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3465MH0002240011202806C0D	2806	target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3465MH0002240011202807C0D	2807	target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3465MH0002240011202808C0D	2808			target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3465MH0002240011202809C0D	2809			target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3465MH0002240011202810C0D	2810			target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3465MH0002240011202811C0D	2811			target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00289	Focus Merges			3465MH0001930001202812B0D	2812	target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3465 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2804-2811 - best focus image product
				3465MH0001930001202813S0D	2813	target Bartica - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3465 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2804-2811 - range map product
				3465MH0001930001202814K0D	2814	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3465 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2792-2799 - best focus image product
				3465MH0001930001202815J0D	2815	target Firina - mosaic position 2 of 2 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3465 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2792-2799 - range map product
		3465MH0001930001202816M0D	2816	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3465 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2782-2789 - best focus image product		
		3465MH0001930001202817S0D	2817	target Firina - mosaic position 1 of 2 - standoff near 20 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3465 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2782-2789 - range map product		

Sol 3466 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	7 May 22	
		camera positions	12	Image ID:
		total parent images	75	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	6	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	13	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	84	
summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the targets Bonfim, Kurupukari (x1 mosaic) and Oshi and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Bonfim ~25 cm standoff	3466MH00190001202818C0D	2818	autofocus sub-frame for target Bonfim - standoff near 25 cm
		3466MH00190001202819C0D	2819	target Bonfim - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Bonfim stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3466MH00173001202820C0D	2820	autofocus sub-frame for target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3466MH00173001202821C0D	2821	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3466MH00173001202822C0D	2822	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202823C0D	2823	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202824C0D	2824	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202825C0D	2825	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202826C0D	2826	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202827C0D	2827	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202828C0D	2828	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202829C0D	2829	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Bonfim stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3466MH00173001202830C0D	2830	autofocus sub-frame for target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3466MH00173001202831C0D	2831	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3466MH00173001202832C0D	2832	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202833C0D	2833	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202834C0D	2834	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202835C0D	2835	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202836C0D	2836	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202837C0D	2837	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202838C0D	2838	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00173001202839C0D	2839	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00176	Bonfim ~2 cm standoff	3466MH00176001202840C0D	2840	autofocus sub-frame for target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm
		3466MH00176001202841C0D	2841	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm
		3466MH00176001202842C0D	2842	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00176001202843C0D	2843	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00176001202844C0D	2844	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00176001202845C0D	2845	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00176001202846C0D	2846	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00176001202847C0D	2847	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00176001202848C0D	2848	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00176001202849C0D	2849	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Kurupukari mosaic position 1 of 4 ~22 cm standoff	3466MH00190001202850C0D	2850	autofocus sub-frame for target Kurupukari - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 22 cm
		3466MH00190001202851C0D	2851	target Kurupukari - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 22 cm
mN00190	Kurupukari mosaic position 2 of 4 ~23 cm standoff	3466MH00190001202852C0D	2852	autofocus sub-frame for target Kurupukari - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 23 cm
		3466MH00190001202853C0D	2853	target Kurupukari - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 23 cm
mN00190	Kurupukari mosaic position 3 of 4 ~23 cm standoff	3466MH00190001202854C0D	2854	autofocus sub-frame for target Kurupukari - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 23 cm
		3466MH00190001202855C0D	2855	target Kurupukari - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 23 cm
mN00190	Kurupukari mosaic position 4 of 4 ~23 cm standoff	3466MH00190001202856C0D	2856	autofocus sub-frame for target Kurupukari - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 23 cm
		3466MH00190001202857C0D	2857	target Kurupukari - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 23 cm
mN00190	Oshi ~25 cm standoff	3466MH00190001202858C0D	2858	autofocus sub-frame for target Oshi - standoff near 25 cm
		3466MH00190001202859C0D	2859	target Oshi - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Oshi stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3466MH00182001202860C0D	2860	autofocus sub-frame for target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3466MH00182001202861C0D	2861	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3466MH00182001202862C0D	2862	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202863C0D	2863	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202864C0D	2864	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202865C0D	2865	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202866C0D	2866	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202867C0D	2867	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202868C0D	2868	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202869C0D	2869	target Oshi - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Oshi stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3466MH00182001202870C0D	2870	autofocus sub-frame for target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3466MH00182001202871C0D	2871	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3466MH00182001202872C0D	2872	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202873C0D	2873	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202874C0D	2874	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202875C0D	2875	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202876C0D	2876	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202877C0D	2877	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202878C0D	2878	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00182001202879C0D	2879	target Oshi - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

mH00426	Osh -1 cm standoff	3466MH00426001202885C00	2880	autofocus sub-frame for target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm
		3466MH00426001202881C00	2881	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm
		3466MH00426001202882C00	2882	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00426001202883C00	2883	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00426001202884C00	2884	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00426001202885C00	2885	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00426001202886C00	2886	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00426001202887C00	2887	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3466MH00426001202888C00	2888	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3466MH00426001202889C00	2889	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00163	Focus Merge	3466MH001630001202890R00	2890	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2882-2889 - best focus image product
		3466MH001630001202891S00	2891	target Osh1 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2882-2889 - range map product
		3466MH001630001202892R00	2892	target Osh1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2872-2879 - best focus image product
		3466MH001630001202893S00	2893	target Osh1 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2872-2879 - range map product
		3466MH001630001202894R00	2894	target Osh1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2862-2869 - best focus image product
		3466MH001630001202895S00	2895	target Osh1 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2862-2869 - range map product
		3466MH001630001202896R00	2896	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2842-2849 - best focus image product
		3466MH001630001202897S00	2897	target Bonfim - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2842-2849 - range map product
		3466MH001630001202898R00	2898	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2832-2839 - best focus image product
		3466MH001630001202899S00	2899	target Bonfim - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2832-2839 - range map product
		3466MH001630001202900R00	2900	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2822-2829 - best focus image product
		3466MH001630001202901S00	2901	target Bonfim - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3466 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2822-2829 - range map product

updated: 17_August_2022

Sol 3469 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	10-May-22
camera positions	6
total parent images	45
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	53

MAHLI imaged the targets El_Oso and Parima and the focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	El_Oso ~25 cm standoff	3469MH0001900011202902C0D	2902	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Oso - standoff near 25 cm
		3469MH0001900011202903C0D	2903	target El_Oso - standoff near 25 cm
mN00224	El_Oso stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3469MH0002240011202904C0D	2904	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3469MH0002240011202905C0D	2905	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3469MH0002240011202906C0D	2906	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202907C0D	2907	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202908C0D	2908	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202909C0D	2909	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202910C0D	2910	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202911C0D	2911	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202912C0D	2912	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202913C0D	2913	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00224	El_Oso stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3469MH0002240011202914C0D	2914	autofocus sub-frame for target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3469MH0002240011202915C0D	2915	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3469MH0002240011202916C0D	2916	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202917C0D	2917	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202918C0D	2918	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202919C0D	2919	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202920C0D	2920	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202921C0D	2921	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202922C0D	2922	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0002240011202923C0D	2923	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Parima ~25 cm standoff	3469MH0001900011202924C0D	2924	autofocus sub-frame for target Parima - standoff near 25 cm
		3469MH0001900011202925C0D	2925	target Parima - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Parima stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3469MH0001730011202926C0D	2926	autofocus sub-frame for target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3469MH0001730011202927C0D	2927	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3469MH0001730011202928C0D	2928	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202929C0D	2929	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202930C0D	2930	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202931C0D	2931	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202932C0D	2932	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202933C0D	2933	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202934C0D	2934	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202935C0D	2935	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Parima stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3469MH0001730011202936C0D	2936	autofocus sub-frame for target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3469MH0001730011202937C0D	2937	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
		3469MH0001730011202938C0D	2938	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202939C0D	2939	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202940C0D	2940	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202941C0D	2941	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202942C0D	2942	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202943C0D	2943	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202944C0D	2944	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3469MH0001730011202945C0D	2945	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00153	Focus Merges	3469MH0001530011202946C0D	2946	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3469 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2938-2945 - best focus image product
		3469MH0001530011202947C0D	2947	target Parima - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3469 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2938-2945 - range map product
		3469MH0001530011202948C0D	2948	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3469 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2928-2935 - best focus image product
		3469MH0001530011202949C0D	2949	target Parima - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3469 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2928-2935 - range map product
		3469MH0001530011202950C0D	2950	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3469 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2916-2923 - best focus image product
		3469MH0001530011202951C0D	2951	target El_Oso - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3469 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2916-2923 - range map product
		3469MH0001530011202952C0D	2952	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3469 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2906-2913 - best focus image product
		3469MH0001530011202953C0D	2953	target El_Oso - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3469 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 2906-2913 - range map product

Sol 3471 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	12-May-22
camera position	65
total parent images	85
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	85

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPD:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the DRT-brushed target Pastora and the target Tama_Tama.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Pastora after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3471MH0001900001202954C00	2954	autofocus sub-frame for target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3471MH0001900011202955C00	2955	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Pastora after DRT stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3471MH0001730011202956C00	2956	autofocus sub-frame for target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0001730011202957C00	2957	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0001730011202958C00	2958	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202959C00	2959	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202960C00	2960	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202961C00	2961	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202962C00	2962	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202963C00	2963	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202964C00	2964	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202965C00	2965	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Pastora after DRT stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3471MH0001730011202966C00	2966	autofocus sub-frame for target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0001730011202967C00	2967	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0001730011202968C00	2968	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202969C00	2969	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202970C00	2970	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202971C00	2971	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202972C00	2972	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202973C00	2973	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202974C00	2974	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001730011202975C00	2975	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00705	Pastora after DRT relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	3471MH0007050011202976C00	2976	autofocus sub-frame for target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0007050011202977C00	2977	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Pastora after DRT relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3471MH0007050011202978C00	2978	autofocus sub-frame for target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0007050011202979C00	2979	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Pastora after DRT relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3471MH0007050011202980C00	2980	autofocus sub-frame for target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0007050011202981C00	2981	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00174	Pastora after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3471MH0001740011202982C00	2982	autofocus sub-frame for target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3471MH0001740011202983C00	2983	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3471MH0001740011202984C00	2984	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001740011202985C00	2985	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001740011202986C00	2986	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001740011202987C00	2987	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001740011202988C00	2988	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001740011202989C00	2989	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001740011202990C00	2990	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001740011202991C00	2991	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Tama_Tama ~25 cm standoff	3471MH0001900001202992C00	2992	autofocus sub-frame for target Tama_Tama - standoff near 25 cm
		3471MH0001900011202993C00	2993	target Tama_Tama - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Tama_Tama stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3471MH0001680011202994C00	2994	autofocus sub-frame for target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0001680011202995C00	2995	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0001680011202996C00	2996	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011202997C00	2997	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011202998C00	2998	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011202999C00	2999	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203000C00	3000	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203001C00	3001	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203002C00	3002	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203003C00	3003	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Tama_Tama stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3471MH0001680011203004C00	3004	autofocus sub-frame for target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0001680011203005C00	3005	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3471MH0001680011203006C00	3006	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203007C00	3007	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203008C00	3008	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203009C00	3009	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203010C00	3010	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203011C00	3011	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203012C00	3012	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3471MH0001680011203013C00	3013	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 16_May_2022

Sol 3472 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	13-May-22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3471 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3472MH0002270001203014N00	3034	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3006-3013 - best focus image product
		3472MH0002270001203015S00	3035	target Tama_Tama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3006-3013 - range map product
		3472MH0002270001203016R00	3036	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2996-3003 - best focus image product
		3472MH0002270001203017S00	3037	target Tama_Tama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2996-3003 - range map product
		3472MH0002270001203018N00	3038	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2984-2991 - best focus image product
		3472MH0002270001203019S00	3039	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2984-2991 - range map product
		3472MH0002270001203020N00	3030	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2968-2975 - best focus image product
		3472MH0002270001203021S00	3021	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2968-2975 - range map product
		3472MH0002270001203022N00	3022	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2958-2965 - best focus image product
		3472MH0002270001203023S00	3023	target Pastora - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3471 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 2958-2965 - range map product

updated: 16_May_2022

Sol 3474 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	15-May-22
camera position	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	5
total focus merge products	10
total parent images + focus merge products	10

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities

Focus stack images from Sol 3473 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3474MH000227000120307800	3078	target Pedra_Pintada - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3070-3077 - best focus image product
		3474MH000227000120307950	3079	target Pedra_Pintada - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3070-3077 - range map product
		3474MH000227000120308000	3080	target Pedra_Pintada - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3060-3067 - best focus image product
		3474MH000227000120308150	3081	target Pedra_Pintada - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3060-3067 - range map product
		3474MH000227000120308200	3082	target San_Pedro - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3048-3055 - best focus image product
		3474MH000227000120308350	3083	target San_Pedro - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3048-3055 - range map product
		3474MH000227000120308400	3084	target San_Pedro - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3038-3045 - best focus image product
		3474MH000227000120308550	3085	target San_Pedro - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3038-3045 - range map product
		3474MH000227000120308600	3086	target San_Pedro - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3028-3035 - best focus image product
		3474MH000227000120308750	3087	target San_Pedro - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3473 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3028-3035 - range map product

updated: 22_June_2022

Sol 3476 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	17-May-22
camera positions	2
total parent images	23
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	26

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Aratana and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Aratana ~24 cm standoff	3476MH0001900011203088C00	3088	autofocus sub-frame for target Aratana - standoff near 24 cm
		3476MH0001900011203089C00	3089	target Aratana - standoff near 24 cm
mN00841	Aratana stereo-1 ~14 cm standoff	3476MH00084100211203090C00	3090	autofocus sub-frame for target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm
		3476MH00084100211203091C00	3091	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm
		3476MH00084100211203092C00	3092	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203093C00	3093	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203094C00	3094	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203095C00	3095	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203096C00	3096	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203097C00	3097	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203098C00	3098	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203099C00	3099	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00841	Aratana stereo-2 ~14 cm standoff	3476MH00084100211203100C00	3100	autofocus sub-frame for target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		3476MH00084100211203101C00	3101	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm
		3476MH00084100211203102C00	3102	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203103C00	3103	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203104C00	3104	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203105C00	3105	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203106C00	3106	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203107C00	3107	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203108C00	3108	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3476MH00084100211203109C00	3109	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00265	Focus Merges	3476MH00026500012031109D00	3110	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3476 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3102-3109 - best focus image product
		3476MH000265000120311150D00	3111	target Aratana - stereo-2 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3476 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3102-3109 - range map product
		3476MH000265000120311290D00	3112	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3476 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3092-3099 - best focus image product
		3476MH000265000120311350D00	3113	target Aratana - stereo-1 - standoff near 14 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3476 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3092-3099 - range map product

Sol 3480 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	21-May-22
camera position	75
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	75

MAHLI imaged the targets Maple_Creek and Apoteri as well as the DRT-brushed target Bamboo_Creek.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Maple_Creek ~25 cm standoff	3480MH00190001203224C0D	3224	autofocus sub-frame for target Maple_Creek - standoff near 25 cm
		3480MH00190001203225C0D	3225	target Maple_Creek - standoff near 25 cm
		3480MH00173001203226C0D	3226	autofocus sub-frame for target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00173	Maple_Creek stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3480MH00173001203227C0D	3227	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3480MH00173001203228C0D	3228	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00173001203229C0D	3229	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00173001203230C0D	3230	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00173001203231C0D	3231	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00173001203232C0D	3232	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00173001203233C0D	3233	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00173001203234C0D	3234	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00173001203235C0D	3235	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00173	Maple_Creek stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3480MH00173001203236C0D
3480MH00173001203237C0D	3237			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3480MH00173001203238C0D	3238			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00173001203239C0D	3239			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00173001203240C0D	3240			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00173001203241C0D	3241			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00173001203242C0D	3242			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00173001203243C0D	3243			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00173001203244C0D	3244			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00173001203245C0D	3245			target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Apoteri ~24 cm standoff	3480MH00190001203246C0D	3246	autofocus sub-frame for target Apoteri - standoff near 24 cm
		3480MH00190001203247C0D	3247	target Apoteri - standoff near 24 cm
		3480MH00152001203248C0D	3248	autofocus sub-frame for target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
mN00152	Apoteri stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3480MH00152001203249C0D	3249	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3480MH00152001203250C0D	3250	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00152001203251C0D	3251	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00152001203252C0D	3252	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00152001203253C0D	3253	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00152001203254C0D	3254	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00152001203255C0D	3255	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00152001203256C0D	3256	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00152001203257C0D	3257	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00152	Apoteri stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3480MH00152001203258C0D
3480MH00152001203259C0D	3259			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
3480MH00152001203260C0D	3260			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00152001203261C0D	3261			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00152001203262C0D	3262			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00152001203263C0D	3263			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00152001203264C0D	3264			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00152001203265C0D	3265			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00152001203266C0D	3266			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00152001203267C0D	3267			target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Bamboo_Creek after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3480MH00190001203268C0D	3268	autofocus sub-frame for target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3480MH00190001203269C0D	3269	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3480MH00182001203270C0D	3270	autofocus sub-frame for target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00182	Bamboo_Creek after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3480MH00182001203271C0D	3271	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3480MH00182001203272C0D	3272	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00182001203273C0D	3273	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00182001203274C0D	3274	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00182001203275C0D	3275	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00182001203276C0D	3276	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00182001203277C0D	3277	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00182001203278C0D	3278	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH00182001203279C0D	3279	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
		mN00182	Bamboo_Creek after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3480MH00182001203280C0D
3480MH00182001203281C0D	3281			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3480MH00182001203282C0D	3282			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00182001203283C0D	3283			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00182001203284C0D	3284			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00182001203285C0D	3285			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00182001203286C0D	3286			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00182001203287C0D	3287			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00182001203288C0D	3288			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3480MH00182001203289C0D	3289			target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mH00743	Bamboo_Creek after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3480MH00743001203296C00	3290	autofocus sub-frame for target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3480MH00743001203291C00	3291	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3480MH007430021203292C00	3292	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH007430021203293C00	3293	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH007430021203294C00	3294	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH007430021203295C00	3295	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH007430021203296C00	3296	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH007430021203297C00	3297	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH007430021203298C00	3298	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3480MH007430021203299C00	3299	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

updated: 24_May_2022

Sol 3481 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	22-May-22
camera positions	0
total parent images	0
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	14

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3480 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00171	Focus Merges	3481MH00171000120330000	3300	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3292-3299 - best focus image product
		3481MH001710001203301500	3301	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3292-3299 - range map product
		3481MH001710001203302000	3302	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3282-3289 - best focus image product
		3481MH001710001203303500	3303	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3282-3289 - range map product
		3481MH001710001203304000	3304	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3272-3279 - best focus image product
		3481MH001710001203305500	3305	target Bamboo_Creek - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3272-3279 - range map product
		3481MH001710001203306000	3306	target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3260-3267 - best focus image product
		3481MH001710001203307500	3307	target Apoteri - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3260-3267 - range map product
		3481MH001710001203308000	3308	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3250-3257 - best focus image product
		3481MH001710001203309500	3309	target Apoteri - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3250-3257 - range map product
		3481MH001710001203310000	3310	target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3238-3245 - best focus image product
		3481MH001710001203311500	3311	target Maple_Creek - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3238-3245 - range map product
		3481MH001710001203312000	3312	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3228-3235 - best focus image product
		3481MH001710001203313500	3313	target Maple_Creek - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3480 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3228-3235 - range map product

updated: 24_June_2022

Sol 3483 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	24-May-22
camera positions	4
total parent images	33
focus merges performed	3
total focus merge products	6
total parent images + focus merge products	38

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Imataca and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Imataca after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3483MH000190001202914C00	3314	autofocus sub-frame for target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3483MH000190001202915C00	3315	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00173	Imataca after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3483MH0001700012029316C00	3316	autofocus sub-frame for target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3483MH0001700012029317C00	3317	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3483MH0001700012029318C00	3318	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029319C00	3319	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029320C00	3320	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029321C00	3321	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029322C00	3322	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029323C00	3323	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029324C00	3324	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029325C00	3325	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00173	Imataca after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3483MH0001700012029326C00	3326	autofocus sub-frame for target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3483MH0001700012029327C00	3327	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3483MH0001700012029328C00	3328	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029329C00	3329	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029330C00	3330	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029331C00	3331	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029332C00	3332	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029333C00	3333	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029334C00	3334	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH0001700012029335C00	3335	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00337	Imataca after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3483MH00033700012029336C00	3336	autofocus sub-frame for target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3483MH00033700012029337C00	3337	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3483MH00033700012029338C00	3338	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH00033700012029339C00	3339	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH00033700012029340C00	3340	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH00033700012029341C00	3341	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH00033700012029342C00	3342	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH00033700012029343C00	3343	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH00033700012029344C00	3344	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3483MH00033700012029345C00	3345	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3483MH000190001202948R00	3346	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3483 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3336-3345 - best focus image product
		3483MH000190001202947S00	3347	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3483 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3338-3345 - range map product
		3483MH000190001202948R00	3348	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3483 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3328-3335 - best focus image product
		3483MH000190001202949S00	3349	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3483 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3328-3335 - range map product
		3483MH000190001202939R00	3350	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3483 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3318-3325 - best focus image product
		3483MH000190001202935S00	3351	target Imataca - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3483 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3318-3325 - range map product

updated: 17_August_2022

Sol 3485 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		acquired/performed date(s)	26-May-22			
		camera positions	5	Image ID:		
		total parent images	55	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received		
		focus merges performed	5	CDPID:		
		total focus merge products	10	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
		total parent images + focus merge products	60			
MAHLI imaged the target Cabo_Sobral, which included a 3x3 mosaic, and the focus stack images were merged.						
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00359	Cabo_Sobral mosaic position 1 of 3 ~24 cm standoff	3485MH0003590012029352C00	3352	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm		
		3485MH0003590012029353C00	3353	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm		
		3485MH0003590012029354C00	3354	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029355C00	3355	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029356C00	3356	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029357C00	3357	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029358C00	3358	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029359C00	3359	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029360C00	3360	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029361C00	3361	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029362C00	3362	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm		
		3485MH0003590012029363C00	3363	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm		
		3485MH0003590012029364C00	3364	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029365C00	3365	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00359	Cabo_Sobral mosaic position 2 of 3 ~23 cm standoff	3485MH0003590012029366C00	3366	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029367C00	3367	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029368C00	3368	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029369C00	3369	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029370C00	3370	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0003590012029371C00	3371	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00359	Cabo_Sobral mosaic position 3 of 3 ~22 cm standoff	3485MH0003590012029372C00	3372	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm
				3485MH0003590012029373C00	3373	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm
				3485MH0003590012029374C00	3374	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3485MH0003590012029375C00	3375	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3485MH0003590012029376C00	3376	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3485MH0003590012029377C00	3377	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3485MH0003590012029378C00	3378	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3485MH0003590012029379C00	3379	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
3485MH0003590012029380C00	3380			target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3485MH0003590012029381C00	3381			target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00847	Cabo_Sobral stereo-1 ~7 cm standoff			3485MH0008470012029382C00	3382	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm
				3485MH0008470012029383C00	3383	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm
				3485MH0008470012029384C00	3384	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3485MH0008470012029385C00	3385	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3485MH0008470012029386C00	3386	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0008470012029387C00	3387	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0008470012029388C00	3388	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0008470012029389C00	3389	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0008470012029390C00	3390	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3485MH0008470012029391C00	3391	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00847	Cabo_Sobral stereo-2 ~7 cm standoff	3485MH0008470012029392C00	3392	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm
				3485MH0008470012029393C00	3393	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm
				3485MH0008470012029394C00	3394	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
				3485MH0008470012029395C00	3395	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
3485MH0008470012029396C00	3396			target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3485MH0008470012029397C00	3397			target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3485MH0008470012029398C00	3398			target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3485MH0008470012029399C00	3399			target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3485MH0008470012029400C00	3400			target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3485MH0008470012029401C00	3401			target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00227	Focus Merges			3485MH0002270012029402C00	3402	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3394-3401 - best focus image product
				3485MH0002270012029403C00	3403	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-2 - standoff near 7 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3394-3401 - range map product
				3485MH0002270012029404C00	3404	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3384-3391 - best focus image product
				3485MH0002270012029405C00	3405	target Cabo_Sobral - stereo-1 - standoff near 7 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3384-3391 - range map product
		3485MH0002270012029406C00	3406	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3374-3381 - best focus image product		
		3485MH0002270012029407C00	3407	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 22 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3374-3381 - range map product		
		3485MH0002270012029408C00	3408	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3364-3371 - best focus image product		
		3485MH0002270012029409C00	3409	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 23 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3364-3371 - range map product		
		3485MH0002270012029410C00	3410	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3354-3361 - best focus image product		
		3485MH0002270012029411C00	3411	target Cabo_Sobral - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 24 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3485 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3354-3361 - range map product		

updated: 27_June_2022

Sol 3488 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	30-May-22
camera position	6
total parent images	58
focus merges performed	4
total focus merge products	8
total parent images + focus merge products	58

Image ID:
 black = best, best-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the non-brushed region of the target Pitinga as well as the DRT-brushed region of the target Pitinga. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Pitinga no DRT APXS spot 1 ~25 cm standoff	3488MH00190001203412C00	3412	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
		3488MH00190001203413C00	3413	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Pitinga no DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3488MH00168001203414C00	3414	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3488MH00168001203415C00	3415	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3488MH00168001203416C00	3416	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203417C00	3417	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203418C00	3418	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203419C00	3419	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203420C00	3420	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203421C00	3421	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203422C00	3422	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203423C00	3423	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Pitinga after DRT APXS spot 2 ~25 cm standoff	3488MH00190001203424C00	3424	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3488MH00190001203425C00	3425	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Pitinga after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 relief model position 1 ~5 cm standoff	3488MH00168001203426C00	3426	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3488MH00168001203427C00	3427	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3488MH00168001203428C00	3428	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203429C00	3429	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203430C00	3430	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203431C00	3431	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203432C00	3432	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203433C00	3433	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203434C00	3434	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203435C00	3435	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Pitinga after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 relief model position 2 ~5 cm standoff	3488MH00168001203436C00	3436	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3488MH00168001203437C00	3437	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3488MH00168001203438C00	3438	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203439C00	3439	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203440C00	3440	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203441C00	3441	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203442C00	3442	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203443C00	3443	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203444C00	3444	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00168001203445C00	3445	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00705	Pitinga after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 3 ~5 cm standoff	3488MH00705001203446C00	3446	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 3 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Pitinga after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 4 ~5 cm standoff	3488MH00705001203448C00	3448	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 4 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00705	Pitinga after DRT - APXS spot 2 relief model position 5 ~5 cm standoff	3488MH00705001203450C00	3450	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - relief model position 5 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00848	Pitinga after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3488MH00848001203452C00	3452	autofocus sub-frame for target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3488MH00848001203453C00	3453	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3488MH00848001203454C00	3454	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00848001203455C00	3455	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00848001203456C00	3456	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00848001203457C00	3457	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00848001203458C00	3458	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00848001203459C00	3459	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00848001203460C00	3460	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3488MH00848001203461C00	3461	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00153	Focus Merges	3488MH00153001203462R00	3462	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3488 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3454-3461 - best focus image product
		3488MH00153001203463S00	3463	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3488 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3454-3461 - range map product
		3488MH00153001203464R00	3464	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3488 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3438-3445 - best focus image product
		3488MH00153001203465S00	3465	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3488 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3438-3445 - range map product
		3488MH00153001203466R00	3466	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3488 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3428-3435 - best focus image product
		3488MH00153001203467S00	3467	target Pitinga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3488 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3428-3435 - range map product
		3488MH00153001203468R00	3468	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3488 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3416-3423 - best focus image product
		3488MH00153001203469S00	3469	target Pitinga - no dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3488 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3416-3423 - range map product

updated: 27_June_2022

Sol 3491 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	2-Jun-22
camera position	6
total parent images	64
focus merges performed	6
total focus merge products	12
total parent images + focus merge products	76

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Parepona and the target Cabadiscana. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Parepona after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3491MH0001900001203470C00	3470	autofocus sub-frame for target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3491MH000190001203471C00	3471	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Parepona after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3491MH0001820001203472C00	3472	autofocus sub-frame for target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3491MH0001820001203473C00	3473	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3491MH0001820001203474C00	3474	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203475C00	3475	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203476C00	3476	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203477C00	3477	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203478C00	3478	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203479C00	3479	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203480C00	3480	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203481C00	3481	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Parepona after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3491MH0001820001203482C00	3482	autofocus sub-frame for target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3491MH0001820001203483C00	3483	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3491MH0001820001203484C00	3484	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203485C00	3485	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203486C00	3486	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203487C00	3487	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203488C00	3488	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203489C00	3489	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203490C00	3490	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0001820001203491C00	3491	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00302	Parepona after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3491MH0003020001203492C00	3492	autofocus sub-frame for target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3491MH0003020001203493C00	3493	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3491MH0003020001203494C00	3494	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003020001203495C00	3495	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003020001203496C00	3496	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003020001203497C00	3497	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003020001203498C00	3498	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003020001203499C00	3499	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003020001203500C00	3500	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003020001203501C00	3501	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00190	Cabadiscana ~25 cm standoff	3491MH0001900001203502C00	3502	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabadiscana - standoff near 25 cm
		3491MH000190001203503C00	3503	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 25 cm
mN00299	Cabadiscana stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3491MH0002990001203504C00	3504	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3491MH0002990001203505C00	3505	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3491MH0002990001203506C00	3506	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203507C00	3507	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203508C00	3508	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203509C00	3509	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203510C00	3510	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203511C00	3511	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203512C00	3512	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203513C00	3513	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00299	Cabadiscana stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3491MH0002990001203514C00	3514	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3491MH0002990001203515C00	3515	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3491MH0002990001203516C00	3516	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203517C00	3517	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203518C00	3518	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203519C00	3519	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203520C00	3520	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203521C00	3521	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203522C00	3522	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0002990001203523C00	3523	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00311	Cabadiscana ~2 cm standoff	3491MH0003110001203524C00	3524	autofocus sub-frame for target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm
		3491MH0003110001203525C00	3525	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm
		3491MH0003110001203526C00	3526	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003110001203527C00	3527	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003110001203528C00	3528	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003110001203529C00	3529	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003110001203530C00	3530	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003110001203531C00	3531	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003110001203532C00	3532	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3491MH0003110001203533C00	3533	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

Continued on Next Page...

m000163	Focus Merge	3491MH001630001203534900	3534	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3526-3533 - best focus image product
		3491MH001630001203535500	3535	target Cabadiscana - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3526-3533 - range map product
		3491MH001630001203536900	3536	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3516-3523 - best focus image product
		3491MH001630001203537500	3537	target Cabadiscana - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3516-3523 - range map product
		3491MH001630001203538900	3538	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3504-3513 - best focus image product
		3491MH001630001203539500	3539	target Cabadiscana - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3504-3513 - range map product
		3491MH001630001203540900	3540	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3494-3501 - best focus image product
		3491MH001630001203541500	3541	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3494-3501 - range map product
		3491MH001630001203542900	3542	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3484-3491 - best focus image product
		3491MH001630001203543500	3543	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3484-3491 - range map product
		3491MH001630001203544900	3544	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3474-3481 - best focus image product
		3491MH001630001203545500	3545	target Parepona - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3491 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3474-3481 - range map product

updated: 03_june_2022

Sol 3492 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	3 Jun 22	Image ID:	
camera position:	25	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	25	CDPID:	
focus merges performed:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products:	0		
total parent images + focus merge products:	25		

MAHLI imaged 2 360° of the 3 left wheels and right front wheel.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3492MH00769001.203546E01	3546	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3492MH00770001.203547E01	3547	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3492MH00771001.203548E01	3548	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 1 of 5	3492MH00772001.203549E01	3549	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 1 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3492MH00769001.203550E01	3550	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3492MH00770001.203551E01	3551	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3492MH00771001.203552E01	3552	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 2 of 5	3492MH00772001.203553E01	3553	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 2 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3492MH00769001.203554E01	3554	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3492MH00770001.203555E01	3555	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3492MH00771001.203556E01	3556	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 3 of 5	3492MH00772001.203557E01	3557	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 3 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3492MH00769001.203558E01	3558	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3492MH00770001.203559E01	3559	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3492MH00771001.203560E01	3560	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 4 of 5	3492MH00772001.203561E01	3561	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 4 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm
mnh00769	Left Rear Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3492MH00769001.203562E01	3562	cover left rear wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 170 cm
mnh00770	Left Middle Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3492MH00770001.203563E01	3563	cover left middle wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 112 cm
mnh00771	Left Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3492MH00771001.203564E01	3564	cover left front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff of about 135 cm
mnh00772	Right Front Wheel - top view Wheel Inspection Position 5 of 5	3492MH00772001.203565E01	3565	cover right front wheel inspection - top view looking downward on wheel - position 5 of 5 of campaign performed on sol 3492 - manual focus assumes standoff about 124 cm

mh000743	Issano after DRT ~1 cm standoff	3493MH000743001203634C00	3634	autofocus sub-frame for target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3493MH000743001203635C00	3635	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
		3493MH000743001203636C00	3636	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3493MH000743001203637C00	3637	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3493MH000743001203638C00	3638	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3493MH000743001203639C00	3639	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3493MH000743001203640C00	3640	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3493MH000743001203641C00	3641	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3493MH000743001203642C00	3642	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3493MH000743001203643C00	3643	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mh000771	Focus Merges	3493MH0001710001203644R00	3644	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3636-3643 - best focus image product
		3493MH0001710001203645S00	3645	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3636-3643 - range map product
		3493MH0001710001203646R00	3646	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3620-3627 - best focus image product
		3493MH0001710001203647S00	3647	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - relief model position 2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3620-3627 - range map product
		3493MH0001710001203648R00	3648	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3610-3617 - best focus image product
		3493MH0001710001203649S00	3649	target Issano - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - relief model position 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3610-3617 - range map product
		3493MH0001710001203650R00	3650	target Tabaco - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3598-3605 - best focus image product
		3493MH0001710001203651S00	3651	target Tabaco - mosaic position 4 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3598-3605 - range map product
		3493MH0001710001203652R00	3652	target Tabaco - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3588-3595 - best focus image product
		3493MH0001710001203653S00	3653	target Tabaco - mosaic position 3 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3588-3595 - range map product
		3493MH0001710001203654R00	3654	target Tabaco - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3578-3585 - best focus image product
		3493MH0001710001203655S00	3655	target Tabaco - mosaic position 2 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3578-3585 - range map product
		3493MH0001710001203656R00	3656	target Tabaco - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3568-3575 - best focus image product
		3493MH0001710001203657S00	3657	target Tabaco - mosaic position 1 of 4 - standoff near 16 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3493 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDS 3568-3575 - range map product

Sol 3503 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	14 Jun 22
camera position	150
total parent images	8
focus merges performed	8
total focus merge products	16
total parent images + focus merge products	316

MAHLI imaged the ChemCam RWEb window and internal hardware, the target Wandapa, on which a 3x3 mosaic was acquired, and the DRT-brushed target Omai. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mHN0020	ChemCam RWEb diagnostic imaging MAHLI at 45° angle to ChemCam ~25 cm standoff	3503MH005200012036580C0	3658	autofocus sub-frame for ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm		
		3503MH005200012036590C0	3659	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm		
		3503MH005200012036600C0	3660	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036610C0	3661	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036620C0	3662	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036630C0	3663	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036640C0	3664	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036650C0	3665	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036660C0	3666	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036670C0	3667	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036680C0	3668	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 9 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036690C0	3669	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 10 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036700C0	3670	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 11 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036710C0	3671	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 12 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036720C0	3672	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 13 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036730C0	3673	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 14 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036740C0	3674	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 15 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036750C0	3675	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - image 16 in 16-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036760C0	3676	auto-exposure sub-frame for ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - focused manually on interior hardware for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm		
		3503MH005200012036770C0	3677	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - using exposure determined by preceding sub-frame - focused manually on interior hardware for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm		
		3503MH005200012036780C0	3678	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036790C0	3679	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036800C0	3680	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036810C0	3681	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036820C0	3682	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036830C0	3683	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036840C0	3684	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH005200012036850C0	3685	ChemCam remote warm electronics box (RWEb) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mHN00706	Wandapa ~24 cm standoff	3503MH007060012036860C0	3686	autofocus sub-frame for target Wandapa - standoff near 24 cm
				3503MH007060012036870C0	3687	target Wandapa - standoff near 24 cm
				3503MH007060012036880C0	3688	target Wandapa - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		mHN00740	Wandapa mosaic position 1 of 3 ~45 mm standoff	3503MH007400012036890C0	3689	autofocus sub-frame for target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm
3503MH007400012036900C0	3690			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm		
3503MH007400012036910C0	3691			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
3503MH007400012036920C0	3692			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012036930C0	3693			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012036940C0	3694			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012036950C0	3695			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012036960C0	3696			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012036970C0	3697			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012036980C0	3698			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012036990C0	3699			target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mHN00740	Wandapa mosaic position 2 of 3 ~4 cm standoff			3503MH007400012037000C0	3700	autofocus sub-frame for target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm
		3503MH007400012037010C0	3701	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3503MH007400012037020C0	3702	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3503MH007400012037030C0	3703	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH007400012037040C0	3704	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH007400012037050C0	3705	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH007400012037060C0	3706	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH007400012037070C0	3707	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH007400012037080C0	3708	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH007400012037090C0	3709	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3503MH007400012037100C0	3710	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mHN00740	Wandapa mosaic position 3 of 3 ~45 mm standoff	3503MH007400012037110C0	3711	autofocus sub-frame for target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm
3503MH007400012037120C0	3712			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm		
3503MH007400012037130C0	3713			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - alternative auto-exposure		
3503MH007400012037140C0	3714			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012037150C0	3715			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012037160C0	3716			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012037170C0	3717			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012037180C0	3718			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012037190C0	3719			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012037200C0	3720			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3503MH007400012037210C0	3721			target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mHN00706	Omai after DRT ~25 cm standoff			3503MH007060012037220C0	3722	autofocus sub-frame for target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3503MH007060012037230C0	3723	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm		
		3503MH007060012037240C0	3724	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		

mH00723	Omai after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3503MH0072300120372500	3725	autofocus sub-frame for target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3503MH0072300120372600	3726	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3503MH0072300120372700	3727	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3503MH0072300120372800	3728	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120372900	3729	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120373000	3730	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120373100	3731	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120373200	3732	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120373300	3733	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120373400	3734	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3503MH0072300120373500	3735	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00723	Omai after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3503MH0072300120373600	3736	autofocus sub-frame for target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3503MH0072300120373700	3737	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3503MH0072300120373800	3738	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3503MH0072300120373900	3739	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120374000	3740	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120374100	3741	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120374200	3742	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120374300	3743	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120374400	3744	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0072300120374500	3745	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3503MH0072300120374600	3746	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00656	Omai after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3503MH0065600120374700	3747	autofocus sub-frame for target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3503MH0065600120374800	3748	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3503MH0065600120374900	3749	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3503MH0065600120375000	3750	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0065600120375100	3751	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0065600120375200	3752	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0065600120375300	3753	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0065600120375400	3754	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0065600120375500	3755	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3503MH0065600120375600	3756	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3503MH0065600120375700	3757	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mH00850	Focus Merges	3503MH0085000120375800	3758	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3750-3757 - best focus image product
		3503MH0085000120375900	3759	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3750-3757 - range map product
		3503MH0085000120376000	3760	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3739-3746 - best focus image product
		3503MH0085000120376100	3761	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3739-3746 - range map product
		3503MH0085000120376200	3762	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3728-3735 - best focus image product
		3503MH0085000120376300	3763	target Omai - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3728-3735 - range map product
		3503MH0085000120376400	3764	target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3714-3721 - best focus image product
		3503MH0085000120376500	3765	target Wandapa - mosaic position 3 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3714-3721 - range map product
		3503MH0085000120376600	3766	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3703-3710 - best focus image product
		3503MH0085000120376700	3767	target Wandapa - mosaic position 2 of 3 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3703-3710 - range map product
		3503MH0085000120376800	3768	target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3692-3699 - best focus image product
		3503MH0085000120376900	3769	target Wandapa - mosaic position 1 of 3 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3692-3699 - range map product
		3503MH0085000120377000	3770	ChemCan remote warm electronics box (RHEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3678-3685 - best focus image product
		3503MH0085000120377100	3771	ChemCan remote warm electronics box (RHEB) window and mirror - for diagnostic inspection - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3678-3685 - range map product
		3503MH0085000120377200	3772	ChemCan remote warm electronics box (RHEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3662-3669 - best focus image product
		3503MH0085000120377300	3773	ChemCan remote warm electronics box (RHEB) window and mirror - monitor dust accumulation - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3503 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3662-3669 - range map product

Sol 3508 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	19 Jun 22
camera positions	8
total parent images	83
focus merges performed	7
total focus merge products	14
total parent images + focus merge products	97

MAHLI imaged the targets Kukul, Salto_Angel, and Opadai. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00781	Kukul ~25 cm standoff	3508MH007810011203810C00	3810	autofocus sub-frame for target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm		
		3508MH007810011203811C00	3811	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm		
		3508MH007810011203812C00	3812	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3508MH007810011203813C00	3813	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007810011203814C00	3814	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007810011203815C00	3815	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007810011203816C00	3816	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007810011203817C00	3817	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007810011203818C00	3818	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007810011203819C00	3819	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007810011203820C00	3820	target Kukul - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00798	Kukul stereo-1 ~9 cm standoff	3508MH007980011203821C00	3821	autofocus sub-frame for target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
				3508MH007980011203822C00	3822	target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
				3508MH007980011203823C00	3823	target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3508MH007980011203824C00	3824			target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH007980011203825C00	3825			target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH007980011203826C00	3826			target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH007980011203827C00	3827			target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH007980011203828C00	3828			target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH007980011203829C00	3829			target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH007980011203830C00	3830			target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH007980011203831C00	3831			target Kukul - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00798	Kukul stereo-2 ~9 cm standoff			3508MH007980011203832C00	3832	autofocus sub-frame for target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
				3508MH007980011203833C00	3833	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
				3508MH007980011203834C00	3834	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3508MH007980011203835C00	3835	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007980011203836C00	3836	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007980011203837C00	3837	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007980011203838C00	3838	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007980011203839C00	3839	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007980011203840C00	3840	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007980011203841C00	3841	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH007980011203842C00	3842	target Kukul - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00796	Salto_Angel ~24 cm standoff	3508MH007960011203843C00	3843	autofocus sub-frame for target Salto_Angel - standoff near 24 cm
				3508MH007960011203844C00	3844	target Salto_Angel - standoff near 24 cm
				3508MH007960011203845C00	3845	target Salto_Angel - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00852	Salto_Angel stereo-1 ~9 cm standoff			3508MH008520011203846C00	3846	autofocus sub-frame for target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		3508MH008520011203847C00	3847	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm		
		3508MH008520011203848C00	3848	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
		3508MH008520011203849C00	3849	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH008520011203850C00	3850	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH008520011203851C00	3851	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH008520011203852C00	3852	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH008520011203853C00	3853	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH008520011203854C00	3854	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH008520011203855C00	3855	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3508MH008520011203856C00	3856	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00852	Salto_Angel stereo-2 ~9 cm standoff	3508MH008520011203857C00	3857	autofocus sub-frame for target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
				3508MH008520011203858C00	3858	target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
				3508MH008520011203859C00	3859	target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - alternative auto-exposure
3508MH008520011203860C00	3860			target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH008520011203861C00	3861			target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH008520011203862C00	3862			target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH008520011203863C00	3863			target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH008520011203864C00	3864			target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH008520011203865C00	3865			target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH008520011203866C00	3866			target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3508MH008520011203867C00	3867			target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00796	Opadai ~24 cm standoff			3508MH007960011203868C00	3868	autofocus sub-frame for target Opadai - standoff near 24 cm
				3508MH007960011203869C00	3869	target Opadai - standoff near 24 cm
				3508MH007960011203870C00	3870	target Opadai - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure

mHN00851	Opadai stereo-1 "9 cm standoff	350BMH0008510001203874C00	3871	autofocus sub-frame for target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		350BMH0008510011203872C00	3872	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm
		350BMH0008510001203873C00	3873	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		350BMH0008510011203874C00	3874	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510001203875C00	3875	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510011203876C00	3876	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510001203877C00	3877	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510011203878C00	3878	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510001203879C00	3879	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510011203880C00	3880	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
350BMH0008510001203881C00	3881	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mHN00851	Opadai stereo-2 "9 cm standoff	350BMH0008510001203882C00	3882	autofocus sub-frame for target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		350BMH0008510001203883C00	3883	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm
		350BMH0008510011203884C00	3884	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		350BMH0008510001203885C00	3885	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510011203886C00	3886	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510001203887C00	3887	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510011203888C00	3888	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510001203889C00	3889	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510011203890C00	3890	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		350BMH0008510001203891C00	3891	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
350BMH0008510011203892C00	3892	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mHN00171	Focus Merges	350BMH0001710001203893R00	3893	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3885-3892 - best focus image product
		350BMH0001710001203894S00	3894	target Opadai - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3885-3892 - range map product
		350BMH0001710001203895R00	3895	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3874-3881 - best focus image product
		350BMH0001710001203896S00	3896	target Opadai - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3874-3881 - range map product
		350BMH0001710001203897R00	3897	target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3866-3867 - best focus image product
		350BMH0001710001203898S00	3898	target Salto_Angel - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3866-3867 - range map product
		350BMH0001710001203899R00	3899	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3849-3856 - best focus image product
		350BMH0001710001203900S00	3900	target Salto_Angel - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3849-3856 - range map product
		350BMH0001710001203901R00	3901	target Kukui - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3835-3842 - best focus image product
		350BMH0001710001203902S00	3902	target Kukui - stereo-2 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3835-3842 - range map product
		350BMH0001710001203903R00	3903	target Kukui - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3824-3831 - best focus image product
		350BMH0001710001203904S00	3904	target Kukui - stereo-1 - standoff near 9 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3824-3831 - range map product
		350BMH0001710001203905R00	3905	target Kukui - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3813-3820 - best focus image product
		350BMH0001710001203906S00	3906	target Kukui - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3508 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3813-3820 - range map product

updated: 21_March_2023

Sol 3511 - MAHLI Images

		acquired/performed date(s)	23-Jan-23	
		camera positions	48	Image ID:
		total parent images	48	black - best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange - only a thumbnail has been received
		focus merges performed	4	CDPID:
		total focus merge products	8	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels
		total parent images + focus merge products	56	
summary of MAHLI activities				
MAHLI imaged the intended drill target Avanavero before and after DRT and after a drill bit preload test; then the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Avanavero before DRT ~25 cm standoff	3511MH00190001202907000	3907	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3511MH00190001202908000	3908	intended Avanavero drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00122	Avanavero before DRT APXS spot 2 ~5 cm standoff	3511MH00122001202909000	3909	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill site - before dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3511MH00122001202910000	3910	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 5 cm
mN00190	Avanavero after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3511MH00190001202911000	3911	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
		3511MH00190001202912000	3912	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 25 cm
mN00182	Avanavero after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3511MH00182001202913000	3913	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3511MH00182001202914000	3914	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3511MH00182001202915000	3915	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202916000	3916	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202917000	3917	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202918000	3918	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202919000	3919	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202920000	3920	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202921000	3921	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202922000	3922	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Avanavero after DRT APXS spot 2 stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3511MH00182001202923000	3923	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3511MH00182001202924000	3924	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3511MH00182001202925000	3925	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202926000	3926	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202927000	3927	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202928000	3928	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202929000	3929	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202930000	3930	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202931000	3931	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202932000	3932	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00796	Avanavero after DRT APXS spot 2 ~1 cm standoff	3511MH00796001202933000	3933	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3511MH00796001202934000	3934	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm
		3511MH00796001202935000	3935	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00796001202936000	3936	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00796001202937000	3937	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00796001202938000	3938	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00796001202939000	3939	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00796001202940000	3940	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00796001202941000	3941	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00796001202942000	3942	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Avanavero after DRT APXS spot 1 ~5 cm standoff	3511MH00182001202943000	3943	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3511MH00182001202944000	3944	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3511MH00182001202945000	3945	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202946000	3946	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202947000	3947	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202948000	3948	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202949000	3949	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202950000	3950	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202951000	3951	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3511MH00182001202952000	3952	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00465	Avanavero after DRT after drill bit preload test ~35 cm standoff	3511MH000465001202953000	3953	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3511 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
		3511MH000465001202954000	3954	intended Avanavero drill site - drill bit preload test - image acquired after preload - after sol 3511 dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 35 cm
mN00133	Focus Merges	3511MH00133001202955000	3955	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3511 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3945-3952 - best focus image product
		3511MH00133001202956000	3956	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3511 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3945-3952 - range map product
		3511MH00133001202957000	3957	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3511 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3935-3942 - best focus image product
		3511MH00133001202958000	3958	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3511 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3935-3942 - range map product
		3511MH00133001202959000	3959	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3511 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3925-3932 - best focus image product
		3511MH00133001202960000	3960	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3511 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3925-3932 - range map product
		3511MH00133001202961000	3961	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3511 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3915-3922 - best focus image product
		3511MH00133001202962000	3962	intended Avanavero drill site - after dust removal tool (DRT) - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3511 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 3915-3922 - range map product

updated: 30_June_2022

Sol 3512 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	29 Jun 22			
camera positions	0	Image ID:		
total parent images	2	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received		
focus merges performed	0	CDPID:		
total focus merge products	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels		
total parent images + focus merge products	2			
summary of MAHLI activities: Drill preparation activities at the planned Avanavero sample extraction site. MAHLI imaged the intended site for the Avanavero sample discard pile.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	
			Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)	
mN002190	Intended Avanavero Drill Sample Discard Site Before Discard ~25 cm standoff	3512MH001900011203963CD	3963	autofocus sub-frame for intended Avanavero drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 25 cm
		3512MH001900011203964CD	3964	intended Avanavero drill sample discard site - before drill attempt and before discard - standoff near 25 cm

updated: 11_july_2022

Sol 3528 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	20 Jul 22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	0

Image ID:
 black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID:
 Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the Avanavero drill hole and cuttings.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00187	Avanavero drill hole drilled on Sol 3512 ~24 cm standoff	3528MH00197001.1203965C00	3965	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Avanavero - drilled sol 3512 - standoff near 24 cm
		3528MH00197001.1203966C00	3966	drill hole in rock named Avanavero - drilled sol 3512 - standoff near 24 cm
mN00774	Avanavero drill hole drilled on Sol 3512 ~9 cm standoff	3528MH00774001.1203967C00	3967	autofocus sub-frame for drill hole in rock named Avanavero - drilled sol 3512 - sub-frame positioned to focus on surface outside hole - standoff near 9 cm
		3528MH00774001.1203968C00	3968	drill hole in rock named Avanavero - drilled sol 3512 - focus based on preceding autofocus sub-frame - standoff near 9 cm
mN00122	Avanavero drill cuttings ~4 cm standoff	3528MH00122001.1203969C00	3969	autofocus sub-frame for Avanavero drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm
		3528MH00122001.1203970C00	3970	Avanavero drill cuttings - standoff near 4 cm

updated: 18_july_2022

Sol 3530 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	18 Jul 22
camera position	4
total parent images	25
focus merges performed	2
total focus merge products	4
total parent images + focus merge products	29

MAHLI imaged the Avanavero drill cuttings and the target La_Laja. The focus stack images were also merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONAL_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00122	Avanavero drill cuttings ~55 mm standoff	3530MH00122001203974C00	3971	autofocus sub-frame for Avanavero drill cuttings - standoff near 55 mm
		3530MH00122001203975C00	3972	Avanavero drill cuttings - standoff near 55 mm
mN00190	La_Laja ~24 cm standoff	3530MH00190001203973C00	3973	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Laja - standoff near 24 cm
		3530MH00190001203974C00	3974	target La_Laja - standoff near 24 cm
mN00306	La_Laja stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3530MH00306001203975C00	3975	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3530MH00306001203976C00	3976	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3530MH00306001203977C00	3977	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203978C00	3978	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203979C00	3979	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203980C00	3980	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203981C00	3981	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203982C00	3982	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203983C00	3983	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203984C00	3984	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00306	La_Laja stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3530MH00306001203985C00	3985	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3530MH00306001203986C00	3986	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3530MH00306001203987C00	3987	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203988C00	3988	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203989C00	3989	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203990C00	3990	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203991C00	3991	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203992C00	3992	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203993C00	3993	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3530MH00306001203994C00	3994	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00306	Focus Merges	3530MH00265001203995S00	3995	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3530 with NEEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3987-3994 - best focus image product
		3530MH00265001203996S00	3996	target La_Laja - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3530 with NEEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3987-3994 - range map product
		3530MH00265001203997S00	3997	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3530 with NEEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3977-3984 - best focus image product
		3530MH00265001203998S00	3998	target La_Laja - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3530 with NEEL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 3977-3984 - range map product

updated: 18_july_2022

Sol 3531 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	13 Jul 22
camera positions:	4
total parent images:	33
focus merges performed:	3
total focus merge products:	6
total parent images + focus merge products:	39

MAHLI imaged the target Uai_Uai and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Uai_Uai ~25 cm standoff	3531MH00190001203999CD	3999	autofocus sub-frame for target Uai_Uai - standoff near 25 cm
		3531MH00190001204000CD	4000	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 25 cm
mN00168	Uai_Uai stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3531MH00168001204001CD	4001	autofocus sub-frame for target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3531MH00168001204002CD	4002	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3531MH00168001204003CD	4003	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204004CD	4004	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204005CD	4005	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204006CD	4006	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204007CD	4007	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204008CD	4008	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204009CD	4009	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204010CD	4010	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00168	Uai_Uai stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3531MH00168001204011CD	4011	autofocus sub-frame for target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3531MH00168001204012CD	4012	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3531MH00168001204013CD	4013	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204014CD	4014	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204015CD	4015	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204016CD	4016	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204017CD	4017	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204018CD	4018	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204019CD	4019	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00168001204020CD	4020	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00743	Uai_Uai ~1 cm standoff	3531MH00743001204021CD	4021	autofocus sub-frame for target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm
		3531MH00743001204022CD	4022	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm
		3531MH00743001204023CD	4023	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00743001204024CD	4024	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00743001204025CD	4025	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00743001204026CD	4026	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00743001204027CD	4027	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00743001204028CD	4028	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00743001204029CD	4029	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3531MH00743001204030CD	4030	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00193	Focus Merges	3531MH0019300120403100	4031	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3531 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4023-4030 - best focus image product
		3531MH0019300120403200	4032	target Uai_Uai - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3531 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4023-4030 - range map product
		3531MH0019300120403300	4033	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3531 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4013-4020 - best focus image product
		3531MH0019300120403400	4034	target Uai_Uai - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3531 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4013-4020 - range map product
		3531MH0019300120403500	4035	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3531 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4003-4010 - best focus image product
		3531MH0019300120403600	4036	target Uai_Uai - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3531 with MSL_CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4003-4010 - range map product

Sol 3532 - MAHLI Images

acquired(performed date(s))	18 Jul 22
camera position	11
total parent images	97
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	97

MAHLI imaged the DRT brushed target Serriga, the target La_Manare, and the target Caroul.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDP	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mNI00706	Serriga after DRT ~25 cm standoff	3532MH0007060011204073C00	4037	autofocus sub-frame for target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3532MH0007060011204038C00	4038	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm
		3532MH0007060011204039C00	4039	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00834	Serriga after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3532MH0008340011204040C00	4040	autofocus sub-frame for target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3532MH0008340011204041C00	4041	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm
		3532MH0008340011204042C00	4042	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3532MH0008340011204043C00	4043	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204044C00	4044	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204045C00	4045	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204046C00	4046	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204047C00	4047	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204048C00	4048	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204049C00	4049	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204050C00	4050	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00834	Serriga after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3532MH0008340011204051C00	4051	autofocus sub-frame for target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3532MH0008340011204052C00	4052	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
		3532MH0008340011204053C00	4053	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3532MH0008340011204054C00	4054	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204055C00	4055	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204056C00	4056	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204057C00	4057	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204058C00	4058	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204059C00	4059	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204060C00	4060	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008340011204061C00	4061	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00813	Serriga after DRT ~2 cm standoff	3532MH0008130011204062C00	4062	autofocus sub-frame for target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3532MH0008130011204063C00	4063	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm
		3532MH0008130011204064C00	4064	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - alternative auto-exposure
		3532MH0008130011204065C00	4065	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008130011204066C00	4066	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008130011204067C00	4067	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008130011204068C00	4068	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008130011204069C00	4069	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008130011204070C00	4070	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008130011204071C00	4071	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0008130011204072C00	4072	target Serriga - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00706	La_Manare ~25 cm standoff	3532MH0007060011204073C00	4073	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Manare - standoff near 25 cm
		3532MH0007060011204074C00	4074	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 cm
		3532MH0007060011204075C00	4075	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNI00723	La_Manare stereo-1 ~55 mm standoff	3532MH0007230011204076C00	4076	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3532MH0007230011204077C00	4077	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm
		3532MH0007230011204078C00	4078	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3532MH0007230011204079C00	4079	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204080C00	4080	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204081C00	4081	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204082C00	4082	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204083C00	4083	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204084C00	4084	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204085C00	4085	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204086C00	4086	target La_Manare - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNI00723	La_Manare stereo-2 ~55 mm standoff	3532MH0007230011204087C00	4087	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		3532MH0007230011204088C00	4088	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm
		3532MH0007230011204089C00	4089	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3532MH0007230011204090C00	4090	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204091C00	4091	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204092C00	4092	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204093C00	4093	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204094C00	4094	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204095C00	4095	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204096C00	4096	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH0007230011204097C00	4097	target La_Manare - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack

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mNH0080	La_Manare *25 mm standoff	3532MH000800001204098C00	4098	autofocus sub-frame for target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm
		3532MH0008000011204099C00	4099	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm
		3532MH000800001204100C00	4100	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3532MH000800001204101C00	4101	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000800001204102C00	4102	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000800001204103C00	4103	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000800001204104C00	4104	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000800001204105C00	4105	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000800001204106C00	4106	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000800001204107C00	4107	target La_Manare - standoff near 25 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNH0076	Caruai *23 cm standoff	3532MH000760001204109C00	4109	autofocus sub-frame for target Caruai - standoff near 23 cm
		3532MH0007600011204110C00	4110	target Caruai - standoff near 23 cm
		3532MH000760001204111C00	4111	target Caruai - standoff near 23 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mNH0079	Caruai stereo-1 *35 mm standoff	3532MH000790001204112C00	4112	autofocus sub-frame for target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3532MH0007900011204113C00	4113	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm
		3532MH000790001204114C00	4114	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3532MH000790001204115C00	4115	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204116C00	4116	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204117C00	4117	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204118C00	4118	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204119C00	4119	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204120C00	4120	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204121C00	4121	target Caruai - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
mNH0079	Caruai stereo-2 *35 mm standoff	3532MH000790001204123C00	4123	autofocus sub-frame for target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3532MH000790001204124C00	4124	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3532MH000790001204125C00	4125	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - alternative auto-exposure
		3532MH000790001204126C00	4126	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204127C00	4127	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204128C00	4128	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204129C00	4129	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204130C00	4130	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204131C00	4131	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3532MH000790001204132C00	4132	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
3532MH000790001204133C00	4133	target Caruai - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 15_July_2022

Sol 3533 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	ES-00-22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	8
total focus merge products:	18
total parent images + focus merge products:	18

summary of MAHLI activities: The focus stack images from Sol 3532 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00170	Focus Merges	3533MH00170001204134900	4134	target Carui - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4126-4133 - best focus image product
		3533MH00170001204135500	4135	target Carui - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4126-4133 - range map product
		3533MH00170001204136900	4136	target Carui - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4115-4122 - best focus image product
		3533MH00170001204137500	4137	target Carui - stereo-1 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4115-4122 - range map product
		3533MH00170001204138900	4138	target Ia_Manaro - standoff near 25 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4101-4108 - best focus image product
		3533MH00170001204139500	4139	target Ia_Manaro - standoff near 25 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4101-4108 - range map product
		3533MH00170001204140900	4140	target Ia_Manaro - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4090-4097 - best focus image product
		3533MH00170001204141500	4141	target Ia_Manaro - stereo-2 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4090-4097 - range map product
		3533MH00170001204142900	4142	target Ia_Manaro - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4079-4086 - best focus image product
		3533MH00170001204143500	4143	target Ia_Manaro - stereo-1 - standoff near 55 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4079-4086 - range map product
		3533MH00170001204144900	4144	target Seringa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4065-4072 - best focus image product
		3533MH00170001204145500	4145	target Seringa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4065-4072 - range map product
		3533MH00170001204146900	4146	target Seringa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4054-4061 - best focus image product
		3533MH00170001204147500	4147	target Seringa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4054-4061 - range map product
		3533MH00170001204148900	4148	target Seringa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4043-4050 - best focus image product
		3533MH00170001204149500	4149	target Seringa - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3532 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4043-4050 - range map product

updated: 20_April_2023

Sol 3535 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	27 Jul 22	Image ID:	
camera positions:	4	black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received	
total parent images:	5	CDPID:	
focus merges performed:	0	Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels	
total focus merge products:	0		
total parent images + focus merge products:	5		

summary of MAHLI activities:	At night, MAHLI imaged inside the CheMin inlet for cleanliness.
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Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00312	MAHLI 12.4 cm working distance above CheMin inlet mesh; inlet cover open; position 1 of 3; imaging at night	3535MH000312001204252C00	4252	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00326	position 2 of 3, otherwise same as above	3535MH0003120011204253C00	4253	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at mesh at 124 mm working distance
mN00325	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3535MH000326001204254C00	4254	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00325	position 3 of 3, otherwise same as two above	3535MH000326001204255C00	4255	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at funnel throat below mesh at 163 mm working distance
mN00228	~19 cm above open CheMin inlet	3535MH000228001204256C00	4256	CheMin sample inlet - cover open - cleanliness inspection - at night with white light LEDs on - manual focus at 19 cm working distance

updated: 23_March_2023

Sol 3536 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	28 Jul 22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	10
total focus merge products:	20
total parent images + focus merge products:	20

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3534 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100389	Focus Merges	3536MH00369001204257900	4257	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4244-4251 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204258500	4258	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 6 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4244-4251 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204259900	4259	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4234-4241 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204260500	4260	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 5 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4234-4241 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204261900	4261	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4224-4231 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204262500	4262	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 4 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4224-4231 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204263900	4263	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4214-4221 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204264500	4264	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 3 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4214-4221 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204265900	4265	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4204-4211 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204266500	4266	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 2 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4204-4211 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204267900	4267	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4194-4201 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204268500	4268	target Ilha_Novo_Destino - mosaic position 1 of 6 - standoff between 17 cm and 32 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4194-4201 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204269900	4269	target Monte_Cabural - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4184-4191 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204270500	4270	target Monte_Cabural - APXS spot 1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4184-4191 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204271900	4271	target Monte_Cabural - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4174-4181 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204272500	4272	target Monte_Cabural - APXS spot 2 - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4174-4181 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204273900	4273	target Monte_Cabural - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4164-4171 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204274500	4274	target Monte_Cabural - APXS spot 2 - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4164-4171 - range map product
		3536MH00369001204275900	4275	target Monte_Cabural - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4154-4161 - best focus image product
		3536MH00369001204276500	4276	target Monte_Cabural - APXS spot 2 - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3534 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4154-4161 - range map product

updated: 21_July_2022

Sol 3537 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	29 Jul 22
camera positions:	8
total parent images:	23
focus merges performed:	7
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	30

MAHLI imaged the target Cerro_Raya and the focus stack images were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00190	Cerro_Raya ~24 cm standoff	3537MH00190001204277C0D	4277	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Raya - standoff near 24 cm
		3537MH00190001204278C0D	4278	target Cerro_Raya - standoff near 24 cm
mN00182	Cerro_Raya stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3537MH00182001204279C0D	4279	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3537MH00182001204280C0D	4280	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm
		3537MH00182001204281C0D	4281	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204282C0D	4282	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204283C0D	4283	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204284C0D	4284	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204285C0D	4285	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204286C0D	4286	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204287C0D	4287	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204288C0D	4288	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00182	Cerro_Raya stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3537MH00182001204289C0D	4289	autofocus sub-frame for target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3537MH00182001204290C0D	4290	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
		3537MH00182001204291C0D	4291	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204292C0D	4292	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204293C0D	4293	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204294C0D	4294	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204295C0D	4295	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204296C0D	4296	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204297C0D	4297	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3537MH00182001204298C0D	4298	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00205	Focus Merges	3537MH00205001204299R0D	4299	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3537 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4291-4298 - best focus image product
		3537MH00205001204300S0D	4300	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3537 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4291-4298 - range map product
		3537MH00205001204301R0D	4301	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3537 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4281-4288 - best focus image product
		3537MH00205001204302S0D	4302	target Cerro_Raya - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3537 with NSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4281-4288 - range map product

Sol 3539 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	23 Jul 22
camera position:	7
total parent images:	45
focus merges performed:	0
total focus merge products:	0
total parent images + focus merge products:	45

MAHLI imaged the targets Surama and Amajari as well as the wheel-surface interface of the rover right middle wheel.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00190	Surama ~25 cm standoff	3539MH00190001204303CD	4303	autofocus sub-frame for target Surama - standoff near 25 cm		
		3539MH00190001204304CD	4304	target Surama - standoff near 25 cm		
mN00206	Surama stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3539MH00306001204305CD	4305	autofocus sub-frame for target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3539MH00306001204306CD	4306	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3539MH00306001204307CD	4307	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00306001204308CD	4308	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00306001204309CD	4309	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00306001204310CD	4310	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00306001204311CD	4311	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00306001204312CD	4312	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00306001204313CD	4313	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00306001204314CD	4314	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00206	Surama stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3539MH00306001204315CD	4315	autofocus sub-frame for target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3539MH00306001204316CD	4316	target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
3539MH00306001204317CD	4317			target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00306001204318CD	4318			target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00306001204319CD	4319			target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00306001204320CD	4320			target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00306001204321CD	4321			target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00306001204322CD	4322			target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00306001204323CD	4323			target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00306001204324CD	4324			target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00190	Amajari ~24 cm standoff			3539MH00190001204325CD	4325	autofocus sub-frame for target Amajari - standoff near 24 cm
				3539MH00190001204326CD	4326	target Amajari - standoff near 24 cm
mN00182	Amajari stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3539MH00182001204327CD	4327	autofocus sub-frame for target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		3539MH00182001204328CD	4328	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm		
		3539MH00182001204329CD	4329	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00182001204330CD	4330	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00182001204331CD	4331	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00182001204332CD	4332	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00182001204333CD	4333	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00182001204334CD	4334	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00182001204335CD	4335	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3539MH00182001204336CD	4336	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00182	Amajari stereo-2 ~45 mm standoff	3539MH00182001204337CD	4337	autofocus sub-frame for target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
				3539MH00182001204338CD	4338	target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm
3539MH00182001204339CD	4339			target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00182001204340CD	4340			target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00182001204341CD	4341			target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00182001204342CD	4342			target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00182001204343CD	4343			target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00182001204344CD	4344			target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00182001204345CD	4345			target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3539MH00182001204346CD	4346			target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00201	Rover Right Middle Wheel			3539MH0020100120434701	4347	rover right middle wheel contact with surface - mobility obstruction assessment - target at about 274 cm - manual focus at motor count 12582

updated: 25_july_2022

Sol 3540 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	23_jul_22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	4
total focus merge products:	8
total parent images + focus merge products:	8

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received

CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3539 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m100013	Focus Merges	3540MH00153000120434800	4348	target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4339-4346 - best focus image product
		3540MH00153000120434950	4349	target Amajari - stereo-2 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4339-4346 - range map product
		3540MH00153000120435000	4350	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4329-4336 - best focus image product
		3540MH00153000120435150	4351	target Amajari - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4329-4336 - range map product
		3540MH00153000120435200	4352	target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4317-4324 - best focus image product
		3540MH00153000120435350	4353	target Surama - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4317-4324 - range map product
		3540MH00153000120435400	4354	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4307-4314 - best focus image product
		3540MH00153000120435500	4355	target Surama - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3539 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4307-4314 - range map product

updated: 26_july_2022

Sol 3543 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	25 Jul 22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	6
total focus merge products:	12
total parent images + focus merge products:	12

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3541 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
m1N00163	Focus Merges	3543MH001630001204422R0	4422	target Motocouruna - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4414-4421 - best focus image product
		3543MH001630001204423S0	4423	target Motocouruna - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4414-4421 - range map product
		3543MH001630001204424R0	4424	target Motocouruna - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4404-4411 - best focus image product
		3543MH001630001204425S0	4425	target Motocouruna - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4404-4411 - range map product
		3543MH001630001204426R0	4426	target Motocouruna - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4394-4401 - best focus image product
		3543MH001630001204427S0	4427	target Motocouruna - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4394-4401 - range map product
		3543MH001630001204428R0	4428	target Benhori_Bumoko - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4380-4387 - best focus image product
		3543MH001630001204429S0	4429	target Benhori_Bumoko - standoff near 2 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4380-4387 - range map product
		3543MH001630001204430R0	4430	target Benhori_Bumoko - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4370-4377 - best focus image product
		3543MH001630001204431S0	4431	target Benhori_Bumoko - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4370-4377 - range map product
		3543MH001630001204432R0	4432	target Benhori_Bumoko - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4360-4367 - best focus image product
		3543MH001630001204433S0	4433	target Benhori_Bumoko - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3541 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4360-4367 - range map product

updated: 10_October_2022

Sol 3544 - MAHLI Images

summary of MAHLI activities		acquired/performed date(s)	26 Sep 22	
		camera positions	2	
		total parent images	35	
		focus merges performed	3	
		total focus merge products	6	
		total parent images + focus merge products	39	
MAHLI imaged the target Tumereng and the focus stack images were merged.				
Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPD	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for POS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00628	Tumereng ~25 cm standoff	3544MH0006730011204430C0	4434	autofocus sub-frame for target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm
		3544MH0006730011204435C0	4435	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm
		3544MH0006730011204436C0	4436	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204437C0	4437	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204438C0	4438	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204439C0	4439	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204440C0	4440	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204441C0	4441	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204442C0	4442	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204443C0	4443	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00673	Tumereng stereo-1 ~45 mm standoff	3544MH0006730011204444C0	4444	autofocus sub-frame for target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3544MH0006730011204445C0	4445	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm
		3544MH0006730011204446C0	4446	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204447C0	4447	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204448C0	4448	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204449C0	4449	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204450C0	4450	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204451C0	4451	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204452C0	4452	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204453C0	4453	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00673	Tumereng stereo-2 ~35 mm standoff	3544MH0006730011204454C0	4454	autofocus sub-frame for target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3544MH0006730011204455C0	4455	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm
		3544MH0006730011204456C0	4456	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204457C0	4457	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204458C0	4458	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204459C0	4459	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204460C0	4460	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204461C0	4461	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204462C0	4462	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3544MH0006730011204463C0	4463	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack
mN00189	Focus Merges	3544MH001930011204464R0	4464	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3544 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4456-4463 - best focus image product
		3544MH001930011204465R0	4465	target Tumereng - stereo-2 - standoff near 35 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3544 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4456-4463 - range map product
		3544MH001930011204466R0	4466	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3544 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4446-4453 - best focus image product
		3544MH001930011204467R0	4467	target Tumereng - stereo-1 - standoff near 45 mm - focus stack acquired sol 3544 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4446-4453 - range map product
		3544MH001930011204468R0	4468	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3544 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4436-4443 - best focus image product
3544MH001930011204469R0	4469	target Tumereng - standoff near 25 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3544 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_IDs 4436-4443 - range map product		

updated: 10_October_2022

Sol 3546 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s)	28 Jul 22
camera position	7
total parent images	55
focus merges performed	0
total focus merge products	0
total parent images + focus merge products	55

Image ID: black = best, least-compressed version receive as of date at upper left; orange = only a thumbnail has been received
 CPDPID: Camera Data Product Identifier = MSL-CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID in PDS archive product labels

summary of MAHLI activities: MAHLI imaged the target Simoni and the DRT for ushed target Lilas.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CPDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)		
mN00706	Simoni ~24 cm standoff	3546MH00070600120447000	4470	autofocus sub-frame for target Simoni - standoff near 24 cm		
		3546MH00070600120447100	4471	target Simoni - standoff near 24 cm		
		3546MH00070600120447200	4472	target Simoni - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure		
mN00024	Simoni stereo-1 ~4 cm standoff	3546MH0002400120447300	4473	autofocus sub-frame for target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3546MH0002400120447400	4474	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm		
		3546MH0002400120447500	4475	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH0002400120447600	4476	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH0002400120447700	4477	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH0002400120447800	4478	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH0002400120447900	4479	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH0002400120448000	4480	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH0002400120448100	4481	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH0002400120448200	4482	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00024	Simoni stereo-2 ~4 cm standoff	3546MH0002400120448300	4483	autofocus sub-frame for target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3546MH0002400120448400	4484	target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm
				3546MH0002400120448500	4485	target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3546MH0002400120448600	4486			target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH0002400120448700	4487			target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH0002400120448800	4488			target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH0002400120448900	4489			target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH0002400120449000	4490			target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH0002400120449100	4491			target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH0002400120449200	4492			target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00706	Lilas after DRT ~24 cm standoff			3546MH00070600120449300	4493	autofocus sub-frame for target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
				3546MH00070600120449400	4494	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm
				3546MH00070600120449500	4495	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 24 cm - alternative auto-exposure
mN00182	Lilas after DRT stereo-1 ~5 cm standoff	3546MH00018200120449600	4496	autofocus sub-frame for target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3546MH00018200120449700	4497	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm		
		3546MH00018200120449800	4498	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00018200120449900	4499	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00018200120450000	4500	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00018200120450100	4501	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00018200120450200	4502	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00018200120450300	4503	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00018200120450400	4504	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00018200120450500	4505	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		mN00182	Lilas after DRT stereo-2 ~5 cm standoff	3546MH00018200120450600	4506	autofocus sub-frame for target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3546MH00018200120450700	4507	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm
				3546MH00018200120450800	4508	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
3546MH00018200120450900	4509			target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH00018200120451000	4510			target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH00018200120451100	4511			target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH00018200120451200	4512			target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH00018200120451300	4513			target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH00018200120451400	4514			target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
3546MH00018200120451500	4515			target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		
mN00426	Lilas after DRT ~1 cm standoff			3546MH00042600120451600	4516	autofocus sub-frame for target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
				3546MH00042600120451700	4517	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm
				3546MH00042600120451800	4518	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 1 in 8-image relative focus stack
		3546MH00042600120451900	4519	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 2 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00042600120452000	4520	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 3 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00042600120452100	4521	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 4 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00042600120452200	4522	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 5 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00042600120452300	4523	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 6 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00042600120452400	4524	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 7 in 8-image relative focus stack		
		3546MH00042600120452500	4525	target Lilas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - image 8 in 8-image relative focus stack		

updated: 29_july_2022

Sol 3547 - MAHLI Images

acquired/performed date(s):	29 Jul 22
camera position:	0
total parent images:	0
focus merges performed:	5
total focus merge products:	10
total parent images + focus merge products:	10

summary of MAHLI activities: Focus stack images from Sol 3546 were merged.

Sequence	Camera Position	Image ID	CDPID	Image Comment/Purpose (RATIONALE_DESC for PDS archive products; 400 character limit)
mN00227	Focus Merges	3547MH0002270001204526R00	4526	target Lillas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4518-4525 - best focus image product
		3547MH0002270001204527S00	4527	target Lillas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - standoff near 1 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4518-4525 - range map product
		3547MH0002270001204528R00	4528	target Lillas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4508-4515 - best focus image product
		3547MH0002270001204529S00	4529	target Lillas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-2 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4508-4515 - range map product
		3547MH0002270001204530R00	4530	target Lillas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4498-4505 - best focus image product
		3547MH0002270001204531S00	4531	target Lillas - after dust removal tool (DRT) - stereo-1 - standoff near 5 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4498-4505 - range map product
		3547MH0002270001204532R00	4532	target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4485-4492 - best focus image product
		3547MH0002270001204533S00	4533	target Simoni - stereo-2 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4485-4492 - range map product
		3547MH0002270001204534R00	4534	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4475-4482 - best focus image product
		3547MH0002270001204535S00	4535	target Simoni - stereo-1 - standoff near 4 cm - focus stack acquired sol 3546 with MSL CAMERA_PRODUCT_Ids 4475-4482 - range map product

7 Definitions, conventions, and acronyms

7.1 Definitions and conventions

absolute focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a commanded (manual) focus setting. The starting focus position (a stepper motor count), and the incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack, are specified by instrument commanding.

best focus image product

A *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *best focus image product* is a color JPEG that combines the in-focus (or closest to in-focus) elements of the up to 8 *parent images* into a single image. The onboard focus merge software also creates a *range map product*.

focus merge product

Using the methods described by Edgett *et al.* (2012), *focus merge products* are created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. Two products are created, a *best focus image product* and a *range map product*.

MAHLI toolframe +X distance

Same as *standoff distance*. See *standoff distance*.

parent and child images

Every MAHLI image has a *parent image*, the picture originally commanded to be acquired. Upon command, the parent image can spawn children (each a *child image*) onboard the instrument. Examples of children include *thumbnail images*, focus merge products, and any version of the image that is compressed differently than the parent (Edgett *et al.* 2012). While a parent can be an image that was compressed during image acquisition, our best practice since landing on Mars has been to acquire and store (onboard the instrument) most MAHLI images in uncompressed 8-bit form. An uncompressed 8-bit parent image can be commanded for compression some time after acquisition and storage, whereas a parent that was compressed at the time of acquisition cannot be further compressed onboard the instrument. When a parent is stored onboard in uncompressed form, it can be used to create multiple versions of the image, each time with a different compression scheme, for downlink to Earth. Thus, if the image received is over-compressed, we have the option to retrieve it again (as many times as necessary) in a less compressed form. Indeed, the majority of MAHLI images received from Mars have been losslessly compressed children of an uncompressed, 8-bit parent.

range

Used here in the context of describing a focus merge range map product, this term refers to the distance between the front lens element and in-focus elements of the imaged subject in a given MAHLI focus merge product. As each MAHLI focus stack is acquired at a fixed *working distance*, the range denotes the distance between the camera and the relief elements of the target (*i.e.*, subject), as indicated by grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) in the range map product.

range map product

A grayscale JPEG image *focus merge product* created onboard the MAHLI instrument from up to 8 *parent images* acquired as a focus stack. The *range map product* accompanies a *best focus image product*. The grayscale pixel values (data number, DN) can be correlated with knowledge of instrument focus, *working distance*, *range*, and pixel scale.

RATIONALE_DESC

The term, RATIONALE_DESC, comes from the NASA PDS archivists. The RATIONALE_DESC for a given MAHLI image is a text description of the rationale or purpose behind the acquisition of a given MAHLI parent image or onboard focus merge product. Each parent image RATIONALE_DESC provides information that the MAHLI team desired to communicate to data users, such as the intended image target, intended working or standoff distance, intended purpose of the image (e.g., stereo, mosaic, autofocus sub-frame, range-finding), image position in a focus stack, as well as information regarding how the image supports observations made by other MSL science instruments, especially APXS and ChemCam. The RATIONALE_DESC for a focus merge product tells the user which images were merged (on what sol they were acquired and images of which CDPIDs were merged), as well as the focus merge product type (best focus or range map product).

relative focus stack

A MAHLI focus stack acquired using a starting focus position determined by a preceding instrument command. Usually, this is a focus setting based upon a focus position determined by a preceding autofocus command. The incremental change in focus position (a stepper motor count interval) between frames in the focus stack is specified by instrument commanding.

RP distance

RP refers to Rover Planners, the personnel who drive the Curiosity rover and operate its robotic arm. RP distance is equivalent to *standoff distance*. See definition of *standoff distance*.

sol

A Martian day; duration of ~1.027 Earth days.

Sol

A specific Martian sol during the MSL Curiosity mission. Because it landed during local afternoon, the sol that Curiosity arrived on Mars was designated Sol 0 and the first full sol after landing was Sol 1.

standoff distance

Also known as the MAHLI *toolframe distance* and *RP distance*, this is range between the subject photographed and the Y, Z plane defined by the two MAHLI contact sensor probe tips when they are not in contact with a surface. In the MAHLI toolframe, the X axis is equivalent to the instrument's optic (z) axis; the distance between the Y, Z plane and the subject is +X; the – X-axis goes from the Y, Z plane into the camera. *Standoff distance* and *RP distance* are equivalent to the +X MAHLI toolframe distance. MAHLI *standoff distance* is 1.9 cm less than *working distance*.

thumbnail images

Reduced-size versions of MAHLI *parent images* and *focus merge products*, approximately 1/8th size in terms of pixel dimensions. Under most circumstances, a *thumbnail image* is returned to Earth for every *parent image* acquired or *focus merge product* created, whether a full-size version of the *parent image* (or a *child image*) or *focus merge product* is returned or not.

working distance

A photography term that refers to the range between the front lens element of a camera and the subject imaged. MAHLI working distance is 1.9 cm greater than the toolframe (also known as standoff or RP) distance.

7.2 Acronyms

APXS

Alpha Particle X-ray Spectrometer (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CDPID or MSL:CAMERA_PRODUCT_ID

Each MAHLI parent image acquired or onboard focus merge product created and stored in the instrument's DEA flash memory is assigned a Camera Data Product ID (CDPID). This identifier, plus the time at which (or sol on which) the data were acquired, uniquely identify each image. The CDPID and sol are incorporated into the image ID. Data acquired by the camera but not stored in the DEA have less unique CDPIDs; these acquisitions have generally been rare and easy for the operations team to track (*i.e.*, 12 such images were obtained during Interplanetary Cruise, only one such image was obtained during the first 1000 sols of operations on Mars).

ChemCam

Chemistry Camera; Laser Induced Breakdown Spectrometer (LIBS) and Remote Microscopic Imager (RMI) (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CheMin

Chemistry and Mineralogy x-ray diffraction (XRD) and x-ray fluorescence (XRF) sample analysis investigation (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

CHIMRA

Collection and Handling for Interior Martian Rock Analysis (sample handling and processing subsystem on Curiosity's robotic arm)

DEA

Digital Electronics Assembly, the MAHLI electronics housed inside Curiosity's rover body.

DN

data number (image pixel value)

DOF

image depth of field

DRT

Dust Removal Tool (wire brush tool on Curiosity's robotic arm)

EDR

Experiment Data Record

Hazcam(s)

Hazard cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

ID or image ID

Image identifier (NASA PDS image identifier for MAHLI images and focus merge products).

JPL-Caltech

Jet Propulsion Laboratory, California Institute of Technology, Pasadena, California, USA

MAHLI

Mars Hand Lens Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MARDI

Mars Descent Imager (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-34 (also M-34 and M34)

34 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

Mastcam-100 (also M-100 and M100)

100 mm focal length Mast Camera (science instrument aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

MSL

Mars Science Laboratory

MSSS

Malin Space Science Systems, San Diego, California, USA

NASA

National Aeronautics and Space Administration (USA space agency)

Navcam(s)

Navigation cameras (engineering cameras aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

PDS

Planetary Data System (NASA planetary science data archives)

QMS

Quadrupole Mass Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

RDR

Reduced Data Record

REMS

Rover Environment and Monitoring Station (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

SAM

Sample Analysis at Mars (science instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

TLS

Tunable Laser Spectrometer (part of the SAM instrument suite aboard MSL Curiosity rover)

USA

United States of America

UTC

Coordinated Universal Time

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